

Cairo University

**MANAGING ENVIRONMENTAL DESIGN STRATEGIES
TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF
TOURISM PROJECTS URBANISM
(CASE STUDY: THE SYRIAN COASTAL ZONE)**

By
Khuloud Jamil Ali

A Thesis Submitted to the
Faculty of Engineering at Cairo University
in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements for the Degree of

MASTER OF SCIENCE

In
ARCHITECTURAL ENGINEERING

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Title of Thesis:

Managing Environmental Design Strategies towards Sustainable Development of Tourism Projects Urbanism (Case Study: The Syrian Coastal Zone)

Summary:

As most coastal areas are home to over 50% of the world population, the additional millions of tourists visiting these areas add to the growing environmental concern. The rapidly growing population in coastal areas and the increasing number of visitors deserves further attention than it currently receives. Coastal environments are under increasing pressure and their problems can no longer be avoided or deferred.

In Syria, with increasing population (especially during the current Syrian conflicts), visitors and economic activities the coastal zone is facing serious problems caused by the congested uses and conflicting usage demand which are often damaging the environment and scenery, in addition, the coastline is threatened in some parts by coastal erosion resulting from development projects and engineering works

This research aims to study wide range of complex and related issues that affect the level of human activity a particular environment can sustain. The key issues discussed include land, energy, materials, water and waste treatment. For the purpose of this Study, environment refers to all aspects of the environment, excluding people to state a conceptual guideline for achieving sustainable tourism development by environmental design strategies in the course of project life cycle. It could be a first stage in the process of developing environmentally friendly management of resources, and could also highlight the challenges of sustainable tourism in Syrian coast.

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Abbreviations

CFCs	<i>Chlorofluorocarbons</i>
CSIRO	<i>Australia's National Science Agency</i>
EIF	<i>Enhanced Integrated Framework</i>
GATS	<i>General Agreement on Trade in Services</i>
GDP	<i>Gross Domestic Product</i>
ICZM	<i>Integrated Coastal Zone Management</i>
LATA	<i>The International Air Transport Association</i>
LCA	<i>Life Cycle Assessment</i>
LDES	<i>Least Developed Countries</i>
LEED	<i>leadership in Energy & Environmental Design</i>
MBNMS	<i>Monterey Bay National Marine Sanctuary</i>
MTMS	<i>Master of Tourism Management</i>
ODSS	<i>Ozone Depleting Substances</i>
ORVS	<i>Off-Road Vehicles</i>
PVC	<i>Polyvinyl Chloride</i>
RTAS	<i>Regional Trade Agreements</i>
TPRG	<i>Tourism Planning Research Group</i>
UNCTAD	<i>The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development</i>
UNWTO	<i>The United Nations World Tourism Organization</i>
VOC	<i>Volatile Organic Compounds</i>
WCED	<i>World Commission on Environment and Development</i>
WFF	<i>The World Wildlife Fund</i>
WTTC	<i>World Travel & Tourism Council</i>

Abstract

As most coastal areas are home to over 50% of the world population, the additional millions of tourists visiting these areas add to the growing environmental concern. The rapidly growing population in coastal areas and the increasing number of visitors deserves further attention than it currently receives. Coastal environments are under increasing pressure and their problems can no longer be avoided or deferred.

In Syria, with increasing population (especially during the current Syrian conflicts), visitors and economic activities the coastal zone is facing serious problems caused by the congested uses and conflicting usage demand which are often damaging the environment and scenery, in addition, the coastline is threatened in some parts by coastal erosion resulting from development projects and engineering works

This research aims to study wide range of complex and related issues that affect the level of human activity a particular environment can sustain. The key issues discussed include land, energy, materials, water and waste treatment. For the purpose of this Study, environment refers to all aspects of the environment, excluding people to state a conceptual guideline for achieving sustainable tourism development by environmental design strategies in the course of project life cycle. It could be a first stage in the process of developing environmentally friendly management of resources, and could also highlight the challenges of sustainable tourism in Syrian coast.

In this research analytical analysis and comparative analysis between several tourism projects were conducted to conclude conceptual guidelines to achieve sustainable development of tourism projects in coastal zone. Applied studies were conducted by using these guidelines to observe the vulnerability and exposure of the Syrian Coast projects (Porto Tartous and Rotana Afamia) to the negative impacts of tourism. The research had also conducted a questionnaire in order to examine the preferences sub-actions regarding the proposed design guidelines that both designers and developers show towards each environmental element.

The negative impacts of tourism development can gradually destroy environmental resources on which it depends. However, the relationship of tourism with the environment is complex but by efficient environmental management of tourism facilities (e.g. water and energy saving measures, waste minimization, and use of environmentally friendly material) and by planning sustainable tourism development strategy at an early stage prevents damages and decrease the environmental impact of tourism.

Chapter One

Introduction (Research Framework)

1.1 Background

"With 760 million international arrivals recorded in 2004, accounting for almost US\$622 billion of receipts, tourism is a major global activity that has grown by 25 per cent in the past 10 years"¹. In 2014, the industry contributed US\$7,580 billion in GDP and 277 million jobs to the global economy². Sustainable tourism development should follow the basic principles of sustainable development, and it also should be responsive to the needs of visitors. By managing the impacts of a development, an environmental design can provide both, first, an opportunity to bring visitors physically closer to the natural and cultural values of a site and, second, benefit both the locals and the community.

Countries and regions, where the economy is motivated by the tourism industry, have become increasingly alarmed with the environmental problems connected with unsustainable tourism. And therefore, there is an increasing demand to promote sustainable tourism development to minimize its negative environmental impact and maximize its socio-economic overall benefits³.

While tourism delivers considerable and valuable economic benefits for many countries, regions and communities, its rapid expansion can cause a charge of harm environmental impact, and a pressure on the availability and prices of resources, consumed by local residents such as energy, food and basic raw materials, the main natural resources which will be at risk from tourism development are land, freshwater and marine resources. Without concert about land-use planning, for example, rapid tourism development can ram up rivalry for land resources with other uses and lead to rising land prices and increased pressure to build on agricultural land⁴.

As most coastal areas are home to over 50% of the world population, the additional millions of tourists visiting these areas add to the growing environmental concern. The rapidly growing population in coastal areas and the increasing number of visitors

¹ *United Nations Environment Programme. World Tourism Organization. 2005*

² *World Travel & Tourism Council WTTC. The Economic Impact of Travel & Tourism. 2015*

³ *United Nation. Achieving Sustainable Development and Promoting Development Cooperation.*

⁴ *World Tourism Organisation. Tourism Investing in energy and resource efficiency. United Nations Environment Programme, 2011*

deserves further attention than it currently receives. Coastal environments are under increasing pressure and their problems can no longer be avoided or deferred⁵.

In Syria, the coastal zone is facing serious problems caused by the congested uses and conflicting usage demand which are often damaging the environment and scenery, in addition, the coastline is threatened in some parts by coastal erosion resulting from development projects and engineering works. Such works have accelerated erosion of the adjacent shoreline because they did not adequately account for coastal dynamics and processes, sea level rise resulting from the changing climate may also aggravate this erosion in the future⁶.

That is why this coastal zone should be managed in a complimentary manner to the existing local, sectoral and maritime legislative and administrative tools. This doesn't mean the discontinuation of existing administration tools, but rather supplementing and integrating them, with coastal zone management tools. However, efforts for an integrated approach in coastal tourism policy should be extended to support sustainable tourism development⁷.

While existing frameworks for sustainable tourism development are seen as leading to the management of all resources, this thesis intends to focus attention on sustainable tourism development in coastal areas with Syrian coast as an example. The objective is to highlight the increasing vulnerability of the coastal environment caused by tourism and attempt to recommend regulatory frameworks akin to the included coastal planning and management (ICPM) as tools for sustainable coastal zone management with tourism as a backbone.

The thesis will illustrate a range of possible actions that will ensure sustainable and beneficial outcomes, these actions will be divided into three main categories: planning, construction, and operation. And it will be examined through case studies in the Syrian coast.

1.2 Problem Statement

The coastal zone in Syria, which is a narrow window to the sea, is considered one of the scarce natural resources of the country. The considerable increase in the tourism in Syrian coast facilities caused additional negative impacts on the already exhausted resources in some natural sites where land are overloaded with activities that didn't take into consideration the sustainability measures.

The idea of sustainable development is only since 1990, the Concept of Sustainable tourism is even younger, and still isn't reached. Despite the great interest in

⁵ Lawal Mohammed Marafa. *Integrating Sustainable Tourism Development in Coastal and Marine Zone Environment*. 2008

⁶ UNEP/MAP-METAP SMAP III Project *Promoting awareness and enabling a policy framework for environment and development integration in the Mediterranean with focus on Integrated Coastal Zone Management*. 2006

⁷ Klara Brandl. *Environment Agency Austria. Sustainable Tourism & Nature Conservation. SURF-nature project*. 2011

sustainable development tourism there is still a level of uncertainty about how to make tourism more sustainable.

This thesis will focus on sustainability of tourism through environmental design strategies as the approach that can be used to achieve conservation and management of resources, especially those that are non-renewable or are munificent in terms of supporting life. This thesis could be a first stage in the process of developing environmentally friendly management of resources, and could also highlight the challenges of sustainable tourism in Syrian coast.

1.3 Research Objectives

1.3.1 Main Objective

This thesis isn't a lawful planning document. The main objective of this thesis is to illustrate a range of possible environmental architectural design actions in the course of the project life cycle to manage sustainable tourism projects development in the Syrian coast, and play an important role during the development assessment process in the Syrian Coast. Their use by developers and assessment authorities will enable a shared understanding of the key issues involved in the design of a sustainable development for tourism projects.

The use of these documents, by developers and assessment authorities, will enable a shared understanding of the key issues involved in the design of a sustainable tourism projects.

1.3.2 Secondary Objectives

The secondary objectives can be stated as the following:

- Concentrate on the negative impact of tourism on the built environment at the coastal zone
- Study the positive and negative effects of tourism development to support the decision-makers when to intervene in the development in these area

1.4 Research Scope

The Syrian coastal zone signifies a vitally importance area to the country, and present a strategic access to the world.

This importance includes national security, entertainment use by locals, Arabs and foreign tourists. The coastal zone therefore provides important economic, transport, residential and recreational functions, all of which relay on its physical characteristics; appealing landscape, cultural heritage, natural resources, and rich marine and biological diversity of the plan. This resource base is thus the foundation for the well-being and economic viability of present and future generations of its residents.

The dynamics of natural coastal processes, including weather systems, sediment transport mechanisms, as well as the hydrological links between the catchments and the coast, are factors that affect the ability of the coast to sustain human activities. Sea level rise, whether as a result of climate change or erosion, will present increased threats and costs to sustaining infrastructure and human settlement. Human actions exacerbated these problems through the inappropriate location of developments and the overexploitation of coastal resources. Human pressures threaten habitats and natural resources of the coastal zone, and with them, the ability of the coastal zone to implement many of its primary functions. Growing population, both resident and transient, is leading to increased conflict between the competing uses in the coastal zone. Low impact uses are frequently being replaced by intensive use that is more profitable in the short-term but it will weak the long-term potential of the coast by reducing its flexibility. Unfortunately, there is no indicates that inappropriate uses of the coastal zone are becoming less frequent.

In fact, with increasing population (especially during the current Syrian conflicts), visitors and economic activities, the pressures are increasing. this thesis have been prepared as a way to identify, structure and manage environmental actions that are not intended to form a checklist, but rather to indicate appropriate ways a sustainable tourism development in Syrian Coastline might respond to a range of development issues and impacts.

1.5 Research Methodology

Analytical Method: Theoretical studies analysis to determine the impact of tourism on the environment and define the concept of sustainable tourism and the concept of sustainable tourism development. In addition comparative analysis between several tourism projects erected on the coastline that took into account the preserving the environment to draw Environmental Guidelines in the course of projects life cycle to achieve Sustainable Tourism Development in coastal areas.

Applied Method: these guidelines will be used to observe the vulnerability and exposure of the Syrian Coast projects to the negative impacts of tourism and assess the possible implementation of these strategies and design guidelines at different stages in the projects life cycle.

1.6 Thesis Outline

- The first introductory chapter will present the objectives of the research and the most important definitions that were used in it, as well as the reasons for the importance of the thesis and the main goal of this dissertation. In addition, this part will include the research problem, Methodology, and the thesis structure.
- Chapter two will be based on literature review and secondary data to state the environmental Impacts of tourism investigating the physical impacts, the impacts though to tourist activities, and the direct environmental impacts.

Chapter two will also provide a general introduction to the concept, goals, and principles of sustainable tourism, and begin to explore some of the key issues involved in the design of a sustainable tourism development.

- Chapter three will concentrate on the coast value and costal tourism, and will provide different international examples to demonstrate tourism developments throughout the world which display elements of sustainable design, construction, and operation. These examples will highlight unique design responses to a range of environmental issues.
- Chapter four is most relevant for developments which are in close proximity to sensitive natural environments. It aims to study the wide range of complex and related issues that affect the level of human activity a particular environment can sustain. The key issues discussed include land, energy, materials, water and waste treatment. For the purpose of this part, environment refers to all aspects of the environment, excluding people. The second part of this chapter will state a conceptual guideline for achieving sustainable tourism development by environmental design strategies in the course of project life cycle.
- Chapter five will be based on multi case study approach to examine the vulnerability of two different tourism development projects in the Syrian Coastal zone, Rotana resort and Porto Tartous resort. This examination and assessment plan will be based on the framework that was conducted in the previous chapter.
- Chapter six will conclude findings and recommendations that have been reached by theoretical and practical studies in this thesis.

Figure 00: Research Structure

Chapter Two

Environmental Impacts of Tourism

2.1 Tourism Dynamism and Growth

Tourism is a major global activity that has grown by 25 percent from 1995 to 2005. In 2004, 760 million international arrivals were recorded, which represent almost \$622 billion of receipts.⁸

In 2014, the industry contributed US\$7,580 billion in GDP and 277 million jobs to the global economy. During 2015, the industry's contribution to global GDP is forecast to grow by 3.7% and employment by 2.6%. This demonstrates the sector's enduring ability to generate economic growth and create jobs at a faster rate than the global economy, which is due to grow by 2.9% in 2015.

By the end of 2015, the Travel & Tourism sector will contribute US\$7,860 billion, 10% of global GDP⁹, once all direct, indirect and induced impacts are taken into account. The sector will account for 284 million jobs, 9.5% of total employment, or one in eleven of all jobs on the planet¹⁰.

Expected growth rates remain high and, tourism has shown a strong and rapid ability to recover although global and regional patterns have changed from year to year (most recently owing to fears over terrorism, health crisis and natural disasters). Because of millions of tourists with different customs travel from place to place in the world every year and affect the economic, the tourism plays an important role for economic development and financial balance. This can be achieved by creating job opportunities and improving income level of different classes of communities¹¹.

⁸ MTMS/WTO/UNEP, 2005.

⁹ GDP (Gross Domestic Product) The monetary value of all the finished goods and services produced within a country's borders in a specific time period, though GDP is usually calculated on an annual basis.

¹⁰ WTTC Report, 2015, the World Travel & Tourism Council is the global authority on the economic and social contribution of Travel & Tourism. It promotes sustainable growth for the industry, working with governments and international institutions to create jobs, to drive exports and to generate prosperity. WTTC's annual Global Summit brings together over 1,000 delegates to discuss the opportunities, challenges and issues facing the industry, while its Tourism for Tomorrow Awards recognize the industry's power to be a positive force in sustainability.

¹¹ MTMS/UNEP/WTO, 2005.

More and more people have the aspiration and means to travel, and the World Tourism Organization (WTO) is expecting over 1 500 million international arrivals by 2020. Forecasts to the year 2020 expect growth in tourism in all regions of the world, with the strongest relative growth occurring in parts of the developing world. Although Europe, the Americas, and East Asia and the Pacific will acquire for 80 percent of total arrivals, and thus continue to dominate in terms of volume. International travel is only one aspect of tourism. In many countries, local tourism is more important than international arrivals in terms of size and income generated¹².

This is also forecast to grow strongly. Tourism is also a major source of employment, its role in development and growth of a country is considerable and have undeniable role in improving living level quality, supporting 74 million jobs directly according to a World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) estimate, and 215 million (8.1 percent of the world total) if all the indirect economic effects of the sector are taken into account. It represents US\$4 218 billion of GDP (10.4 percent of the world total), with travel and tourism making a particularly significant contribution to international trade, at over 12 per cent of total exports.

There is a sharp rise in international travel (for leisure, recreation, and business), and it has become one of the fastest growing economic activities worldwide (Figure 1). International tourists recorded 25 million in 1950, 277 million in 1980, and 528 million in 1995¹³.

Figure 1: Growth in international travel¹⁴

¹² World Travel & Tourism Council WTTC. *The Economic Impact of Travel & Tourism*. 2015

¹³ UNWTO 2012

¹⁴ UNWTO and UNEP 2012

In 2012 for the first time in the history the number of international tourist arrivals reached an annual figure of over one billion¹⁵.

International tourism ranks fourth after fuels, chemicals and automotive products in global exports. The expected International tourists are to reach 1.8 billion by 2030¹⁶.

The tourism industry has a value of US\$ one trillion a year and accounts for 30 percent of the world's exports of commercial services or six per cent of total exports¹⁷. Tourism considered as a major contributor to the global economy In terms of both direct and indirect impacts. It accounts for more than nine percent of global gross domestic product (GDP) and almost nine per cent of jobs globally¹⁸. As a result, tourism is one of the largest categories of international trade in services.

Because of tourism provides an effect transfer of income from developed to developing economies, it is a capable source of income for developing countries. According to the UNWTO, in recent years, developing country destinations have grown faster than destinations in developed countries.

This orientation is set to remain. International arrivals in countries with emerging economies between 2010 and 2030 are expected to increase at trends, challenges and opportunities double the rate (4.4 percent annually), compared to those of developed economies (2.2 percent annually). Yet, the market share of the comprehensive tourism industry in developing countries has increased from 30 per cent in 1980 to 47 per cent in 2011. It is expected to reach 57 per cent by 2030, equal in value over one billion international tourist arrivals¹⁹.

In many developing countries, tourism is an important source of foreign currency and foreign investment. In Malaysia, for example, using a value-chain analysis, the Tourism Planning Research Group (TPRG) has found that economic benefits which received by local people account, on average, for 34 per cent of total income generated by tourism.

Enhanced Integrated Framework (EIF) conducted studies that identified the tourism as a priority sector for development in 90 percent of Least Developed Countries (LDCs),

¹⁵ UNWTO 2013

¹⁶ *United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO).2011. United Nations agency responsible for the promotion of responsible, sustainable and universally accessible tourism. The UNWTO is the leading international organization in the field of tourism, which promotes tourism as a driver of economic growth, inclusive development and environmental sustainability and offers leadership and support to the sector in advancing knowledge and tourism policies worldwide.*

¹⁷ *The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). 2011. UNEP is an agency of the United Nations that coordinates its environmental activities, assisting developing countries in implementing environmentally sound policies and practices.*

¹⁸ WTTC 2012

¹⁹ UNWTO 2012

and found that tourism is becoming an important industry for many LDCs with a direct link to poorness extirpation²⁰. Specially, developing countries such as Botswana, Cape Verde and Maldives the tourism can play a key role to transition out of the LDC category²¹

Figure 2: International tourism receipts in developing countries (billion US\$)²²

Tourism is deemed as an export industry that national regulations governed it since foreign tourists who travel abroad obtaining goods and services with money from their home countries.

The liberalization of trade in tourism and travel-related services can also take place through the General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS) of the World Trade Organization (WTO), at the multilateral level, as well as through regional trade agreements (RTAs) covering trade in services at the regional level. Regulatory commitments under these agreements by reducing regulatory barriers through these agreements, can play an important role in enhancing tourism, including intra-regional tourism between developing countries and enhancing the profits from tourism trade for firms, workers and consumers (UNCTAD 2010).

²⁰ United Nation Development Programme. *Tourism and Poverty Reduction Strategies in the Integrated Framework for Least Developed Countries*. 2011

²¹ *Tourism as a key export*: URL: <http://www.unep.org/greeneconomy/Portals/88/GETReport/pdf/Chapitre%207%20Tourism.pdf>.

²² Source: UNWTO 2010

2.2 Impacts of Tourism Development on the Environment

Tourism industry is directly related to the environment. The quality of the environment, both natural and man-made, is essential to tourism. However, the relationship of tourism with the environment is complex. It involves many activities that can have adverse environmental effects. The negative impacts of tourism development can gradually destroy environmental resources on which it depends.

The environment is absolutely affected by tourism industry. Its negative impact is very dangerous for the posterity and the environment. Therefore planning and sustainable tourism industry is very necessary for every country²³.

Tourism can be seen as an economic activity which makes a range of negative and positive impacts. Nevertheless Sustainable tourism aims to achieve the optimal balance between social, economic benefits, and environmental costs. In order to plan and develop tourism effectively, social, economic, and environmental aspects of tourism must be well understood (Swarbrooke 1999)²⁴

A framework developed from the industrial ecology literature to assess the impacts of the tourism industry on the environment. Three categories of impact are discussed: direct impacts, including impacts from the tourist activities at that destination (hiking or boating, the travel to a destination) and from the establishment, operation, and upkeep of facilities that meet the needs of the tourist.

“Downstream” impacts, where service providers can influence the behavior or consumption patterns of customers and “Upstream” impacts, resulting from travel service providers’ ability to influence suppliers (Sarah Cahill and Terry Davies 2000)²⁴.

Socio-cultural changes of tourism relate to sense of place, and local quality of life. Positive changes in the quality of life could be: personal income growths, supports the diversity of restaurants and other cultural entertainment supports to increase living standards for those more directly involved in industry, street furniture, park areas are often improved and design criteria introduced, new opportunities, greater attention and care placed on over all environmental quality etc. And on the other side the negative changes in the quality of life could be petty theft from accommodation and cars, local shops overcharging, more serious personal assault etc. (Clarke and Godfrey, 2000)²⁴.

The significance of the host community in relation to sustainability: “Human communities represent both a primary resource upon which tourism depends, and their existence in a particular place at a particular time may be used to justify the development of tourism itself. Communities are a basic reason for tourists to travel, to

²³ P.R. Dingwall and G.R. Cessford. *An approach to assessing the environmental impacts of tourism*. 1998

²⁴ Md, GhulamRabbany. Sharmin Afrin. Airin Rahman. Faijul Islam. Fazlul Hoque. *ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS OF TOURISM*. *American Journal of Environment*. 2013

experience the way of life and material products of different communities”(Hall and Richards 2000)²⁴.

“For sustainable tourism to occur, it must be closely integrated with all other activities that occur in the host region”. According to this declaration it can be concluded that there is an accountability that lies on the industry but also on great organizations within the destination. Control and management therefore seems essential to be able to add sustainability in tourism development (Hunter 2002)²⁵.

The quality of the environment, both man-made and natural is essential to tourism. Even though, the relationship of tourism with the environment is complex. It involves many activities that can have negative environmental effects. Many of these impacts are linked with the tourism facilities, including hotels, resorts, restaurants, golf courses, shops and marinas, and of construction of general infrastructure such as airports and roads. The negative impacts of tourism development can gradually damage environmental resources on which it depends (Ugur Sunlu concluded in his research 2003)²⁴.

The growth of mass tourism has led to a variety of problems, which have become clearer over the recent years. It includes cultural, social and environmental poverty. These problems are often linked with mass tourism, even though there is evidence from studies concerning the impacts from tourism which indicates that new forms of tourism also suffer from similar problems (Munt and Mowforth 2003)²⁶.

If tourism is well planned, managed, and developed in a socially responsible method, it can bring several kinds of socio-cultural benefits. For example increase the living standards of people and help pay for enhancements to services and community services if the economic benefits of tourism are well distributed.

A possible way to achieve this development is to promote and invest in sustainable tourism; another form of tourism that could help to save the social, natural, and cultural environment of a destination. This form of tourism whether it is called eco-tourism, responsible travel or other, is a response of the results of mass tourism (Williams and Shaw 2004)²⁷.

The motives for travel are many but a common cause is the curiosity. “Curiosity leads the travelers to search for all kind of experiences in all parts of the world. To see other people, other cultures and other political systems is a prime motivational force for travel” (Williams 2004)²⁶.

²⁵ U.S. Ambassador’s Youth Council. *Strategies and challenges for pursuing sustainable tourism in Cambodia. 2014*

²⁶ Munt,Ian. Mowforth,Martin. *New Tourism in the Third World. 2003*

²⁷ Shaw ,Gareth. Allan, M, Williams. *Tourism and Tourism Spaces. SAGE Publications Ltd . 2004*

In the Ecologically Critical Areas in Cox's Bazar²⁸, draft report of Department of Environment for the management of sustainable tourism (2008) noticed that the pattern of current tourism is exclude locals, poor communities in the area are receiving no significant benefits from tourism rather than paying some of the environmental and social costs of this activity.

It also mentions that involving locals in management can be done either by making sure that government planning processes are responsive and participatory to local needs or by giving tourism rights to community level.

2.2.1 The Effect of Tourism on the Nature

Negative impacts from tourism occur when the level of visitor use is greater than the environment's ability to cope with this use within the acceptable limits of change. Uncontrolled conventional tourism poses potential threats to many natural areas around the world.

It can put enormous pressure on an area and lead to impacts such as soil erosion, increased pollution, discharges into the sea, natural habitat loss, increased pressure on endangered species and heightened vulnerability to forest fires.

It often puts a strain on water resources, and it can force local populations to compete for the use of critical resources. Environmental Impacts of tourism investigating the direct impacts, physical impacts and the impacts though to eco-tourist activities²⁹.

2.2.1.1 Direct Environmental Impacts

A. Air Quality

Most tourism-related air pollution comes from automobiles (Andereck, 1993). Most carbon monoxide of all transportation modes are produced by far by Automobiles. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency [EPA], 1998, December emitted 1.7 million short tons from recreational marine vehicles, compared with 26 million short tons of carbon monoxide, and 1 million from aircraft. Transportation contributed more than half of the carbon monoxide and nitrogen oxides, and almost a quarter of the hydrocarbons emitted into our air (Union of Concerned Scientists 2013)³⁰.

Specific information on tour bus emissions was not available, but all heavy-duty diesel vehicles (most tour buses fall into this category) emitted 1.4 million short tons in 1997. Kuo and Chen (2009) explored Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to measure carbon emissions of tourism in transportation, accommodation and recreation

²⁸ Cox's Bazar is a town, a fishing port and district headquarters in Bangladesh. It is one of the world's longest uninterrupted natural sandy sea beaches. The beach in Cox's Bazar is an unbroken 125 km sandy sea beach with a gentle slope.

²⁹ Leisanyane, Mamahooana. Malabeja, Michael. Cheyo, Robert. *Impact of Tourism on Wildlife* www.environmental-auditing.org Conservation. INTOSAI Working Group on Environmental Auditing (WGEA). 2013

³⁰ Source: Union of Concerned Scientists, URL: http://www.ucsusa.org/clean_vehicles/why-clean-cars/air-pollution-and-health

activities. They showed the transportation sector consumes the largest CO₂ emissions (67%) followed by accommodation 17% and recreation activities 16%.

The International Air Transport Association (IATA) released an industry traffic forecast showing that airlines expect to welcome some 3.6 billion passengers in 2016. That's about 800 million more than the 2.8 billion passengers carried by airlines in 2011 (IATA 2012)³¹.

Transport by road, rail, and air is on-going increasing in response to the growing number of tourists and their better mobility.

As a result of this increase in the air transport the tourism currently is constitute for more than 60% of air travel and is therefore responsible for a significant share of air emissions. One study estimated that a single transatlantic return flight emits almost half the CO emissions produced by all other sources (lighting, heating, car use, etc.) that an average person consumes per year (ICAO, 2001).

B. Solid Waste and Littering

Littering and solid waste can cause the death of marine animals and damage the physical appearance of the shoreline and the water (UNEP, 1997).

In mountain areas, hiking tourists produce a great deal of waste. Tourists leave behind their camping equipment, garbage, and even oxygen cylinders on their expedition. In remote areas and far suburbs, that have few garbage collection or disposal facilities, these practices along with all the detritus typical of the developed world will damage the environment³².

Waste removal is a very serious problem in areas with attractive natural attractions and high intensity of tourist activities, and wrong disposal can be the most important despoiler of the natural environment, roadsides, rivers, and scenic areas. For example, Volumes of sewage for a typical cruise ship have been estimated at 8.4 gallons per person per day, or 147,000 gallons per week and produces an estimated 1,190,000 gallons of gray water per week (MBNMS 2014)³².

C. Water Quality

Tourist infrastructure raises the pressure on current sewage treatment plants and could lead to overflows during top tourist times. The water quality is affected by tourism industry during the construction and maintenance of tourist infrastructure, entertaining boating, and other kinds of activities of the cruise industry.

The most important problem from the point of human health view connects with water quality and recreational boating is when the sewage discharging into water

³¹ Source: *The International Air Transport Association IATA URL:*
<http://www.iata.org/pressroom/pr/pages/2012-12-06-01.aspx>

³² Source: *Monterey Bay National Marine Sanctuary URL:*
<http://montereybay.noaa.gov/intro/welcome.html>

bodies with incomplete flushing, where the discharge appears near the shellfish beds' location. There are different kind of diseases that can transmitted to human (such as dysentery, typhoid fever, nonspecific gastroenteritis, and infectious hepatitis) caused by ingestion of contaminated shellfish (Sea bloom, Plews, & Cox, 1989)³³.

D. Habitat/Ecosystem Alteration and Fragmentation

Tourist activities, tourist infrastructure, the cruise industry and recreational boating can damage the natural habitat and ecosystem. Cruise vessels and recreational boats could damage aquatic vegetation by cutting it with their propellers or otherwise damaging it when running aground. Cruise vessels and recreational boats could cut aquatic vegetation because of their propellers.

In order to build tourist relevant infrastructure, such as roads, marinas, and airports, the wetlands have been destroyed (Andereck, 1993). The tourist's activities like hiking and snorkeling can harm ecosystems by trampling coral and vegetation, and littering. This kind of damage is cumulative in nature. One or two tourists may not cause apparent harm, but hundreds over time can do substantial damage³⁴.

E. Noise Pollution

The noise pollution from buses, airplanes, and cars, plus recreational vehicles such as sand jet skis and snow mobile, is a big problem of modern life. In addition to causing ordeal to wildlife, especially in sensitive areas, it causes stress, annoyance, and even losing the ability to hear for humans³⁵.

F. Impacts on Wildlife

Wildlife can be negatively affected by building and maintenance the infrastructure for tourism and by tourist activities. The impact of tourist's infrastructure could be direct, or indirect. The peak of the tourist season coincides with the nesting season for the vulnerable Loggerhead Turtles (EC, 2002).

The two main ways in which tourist activities interrupt wildlife are by changing their habitat, and by changing their feeding patterns and eating habits, when the tourist feeds animals the feeding patterns will directly change, on the other hand the littering cause indirectly changed which encourages wildlife to scrounge for food³⁶. So the

³³ *Tourism's Three Main Impact Areas. United Nation Environmental programme URL: <http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Business/SectoralActivities/Tourism/FactsandFigures/aboutTourism/ImpactsofTourism/EnvironmentalImpacts/TourismsThreeMainImpactAreas/tabid/78776/Default.aspx>.*

³⁴ *Camarda. Grassini. Environments and agriculture in the Mediterranean region. 2003*

³⁵ *Source: United Nation Environmental programme, URL: <http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Home/Business/SectoralActivities/Tourism/tabid/78766/Default.aspx>*

³⁶ *Steckenreuter,Andre. How does Australia's largest dolphin-watching industry affect the behaviour of a small and resident population of Indo-Pacific bottlenose dolphins.2011*

wild life habitat is changed by tourists ORVs³⁷. The use of off-road vehicles and by trampling"

G. Loss of Biological Diversity

There are many effects on loss of biodiversity such as:

- It interferes with needed ecological functions such as soil formation, greenhouse gas absorption, and species balance.
- It decreases productivity of ecosystems.
- It threatens our sources of energy, wood, and medicines, opportunities for recreation and tourism, and food supplies.
- It weakens ecosystems' ability to deal with natural disasters such as hurricanes, floods, and droughts, and with human-caused stresses, such as climate change, and pollution, and it also destabilizes ecosystems. Tourism is closely linked to the attractions created by a varied and rich environment, and it also linked to biodiversity.

It can also cause loss of biodiversity when impacts on mountain, vegetation, wildlife, marine, coastal environments and water resources exceed their carrying capacity, and when resources and land are strained by excessive use. This loss of biodiversity in fact means loss of tourism potential³⁸.

Introduction of exotic types which suppliers and tourists can bring in species (wild and cultivated plants, insects, and diseases) that are not native to the local environment can cause destruction of ecosystems and even huge disruption.(WWF, 1992; WWF, 1994).

H. Climate Change

Because of an increase in the greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, which trap heat from sun, the climate scientists now agree that the Earth's surface temperatures have risen steadily in recent years.

One of the most significant of these gases is carbon dioxide (CO₂), which is generated when there are changes in land use, such as deforestation and when fossil fuels, such as oil, coal and natural gas are burned (e.g. in automobiles, industry, and electricity generation). In the long run, increasing CO₂ and other greenhouse gases in the

³⁷ ORVs: *n* off-road vehicle is considered to be any type of vehicle which is capable of driving on and off paved or gravel surface.

³⁸ *Environmental Impacts of Tourism - Global Level-URL:*
<http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Business/SectoralActivities/Tourism/FactsandFigures/aboutTourism/ImpactsOfTourism/EnvironmentalImpacts/EnvironmentalImpactsOfTourism-GlobalLevel/tabid/78777/Default.aspx>

atmosphere can cause global climate change a process that may already be occurring. Air travel itself is a main contributor to the greenhouse effect. Passenger jets are the fastest growing source of greenhouse gas emissions³⁹.

I. Cultural and Aesthetic Impacts

Tourism can reduce the aesthetic appeal of a destination through the construction of buildings that clash with the surrounding environment, creating “architectural” or “visual” pollution (Andereck, 1993). For example the island of Mykonos (Greece) is a well-known international tourist resort, which has experienced rapid tourist development during the last 30 years Parallel to the expansion of the tourist industry (accommodation, bars, etc.)⁴⁰. This growth was followed by the expansion of the infrastructure (enlargement of the port, improvement of the road network construction of a surface dam, etc.).

These investments have further boosted the island’s capacity to accommodate tourists and other visitors. Problems and some signs of saturation have already appeared. The two traditional settlements in the island together with other newly developed villages on which the tourist industry was based mainly during the first phase of development have already been transformed in scale, volume of built-up areas, character and environmental quality as a result of uncontrolled and rapid development of tourism (EC 2002)⁴¹.

J. Depletion of the Ozone Layer

The life in the earth protected by the ozone layer that located in upper atmosphere, this layer plays an important role in absorbing the harmful wavelengths of the sun's ultraviolet (UV) radiation. Ozone depleting substances (ODSs) such as halons and CFCs (chlorofluorocarbons) have contributed to the devastation of this layer.

The tourism industry may be a part of this problem; starting with the construction of new developments and continue during daily management and operations.

Also Propellants in aerosol spray cans, Refrigerators, and air conditioners, amongst others, contain ODSs and are widely used in the hotel and tourism industry. Emissions from jet aircraft are also an important source of ODSs.

In 1993, a study of toxic emissions at Chicago's Midway Airport revealed that arriving and departing planes released more pollutants than the industrial pollution sources in the surrounding 16-square-mile area. A more recent study at London's

³⁹ *Smale, Robin. Krahe, Max. Johnson, Tim. Aviation report market based mechanisms to curb greenhouse gas emissions from international aviation. Gland, Switzerland: WWF International, 2012*

⁴⁰ *Sustainable Tourism: URL: http://www.biodiversity.ru/coastlearn/tourism-eng/why_problems.html*

⁴¹ *EC: the European Commission is the EU's executive body. It represents the interests of the European Union as a whole (not the interests of individual countries).*

Heathrow airport showed that aircraft contributed between 16 and 35 percent of ground level NO_x⁴² concentrations (NASA 2008)⁴³.

2.2.1.2 Physical Impacts

Attractive landscape sites, such as mountain tops and slopes, riversides, lakes, and sandy beaches, are often transitional zones, characterized by rich- species ecosystems. Typical physical impacts include the Deterioration of such ecosystems. An ecosystem is a geographic area containing all the living organisms (microorganisms, animals, plants, and people), their physical surroundings (such as air, soil, and water), and the natural cycles that sustain them.

The ecosystems most threatened with Deterioration are ecologically brittle areas such as wetlands, alpine regions, mangroves, rain forests, sea grass beds, and coral reefs. Pressures on and threats to these ecosystems are often severe because places like that are very attractive to both developers and tourists.

Physical impacts are caused not only by tourism-related land clearing and construction, but also by continuing tourist activities and long-term changes in local economies and ecologies⁴⁴.

A. Physical Impacts of Tourism Development

Infrastructure development and construction activities: Road and airport construction may lead to degradation of scenery, land deterioration and loss of wildlife habitats. Also development of tourism facilities such as water supplies, recreation facilities, restaurants, and accommodation can involve beach and sand erosion, extensive paving, soil erosion, and sand mining.

Unsustainable use of land or Deforestation: There are a lot of activities that cause erosion and severe disturbance of the local ecosystem in addition destruction in the long term. For example, Coastal wetlands are often filled and exhausted due to lack of infrastructure, and suitable sites for construction of tourism facilities. Construction of ski resort facilities and accommodation frequently requires clearing forested land⁴⁵.

⁴² NO_x is a generic term for the mono-nitrogen oxides NO and NO₂. They are produced from the reaction of nitrogen and oxygen gases in the air during combustion, especially at high temperatures.

⁴³ Glenn Research Reduces Harmful Aircraft Emissions: URL:
<http://www.nasa.gov/centers/glenn/about/fs10grc.html>

⁴⁴ Tourism's Three Main Impact Areas: URL
<http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Business/SectoralActivities/Tourism/FactsandFigures/aboutTourism/ImpactsofTourism/EnvironmentalImpacts/TourismsThreeMainImpactAreas/tabid/78776/Default.aspx>

⁴⁵ UNWTO. UNEP. *Tourism in the Green Economy*. World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). 2012

B. Marina Development

Development of breakwaters and marinas can cause changes in coastlines and currents. Moreover, extraction of building materials such as sand has an impact on hinterland forests, coral reefs, and mangroves, leading to destruction and erosion of habitats. In the Maldives and the Philippines, mining and dynamiting of coral for resort building materials has depleted the fisheries and damaged fragile coral reefs (Hall, 2001).

Coral reefs are especially fragile marine ecosystems and are suffering worldwide from reef-based tourism developments. Extensive paving and overbuilding of shorelines can consequence in disruption of land-sea connections and destruction of habitats (sea-turtle nesting spots). Evidence lights a variety of impacts to coral result from shoreline development, fishing with explosives and poisons that destroy the coral habitat, trampling by divers and tourists, increased sediments in the water, ship groundings, pollution from sewage, and over-fishing (Hall, 2001)⁴⁶.

C. Physical Impacts from Tourist Activities

Trampling: Tourists using the similar trail over and over again walk over the vegetation and soil, at the end causing destruction that lead to loss of biodiversity and other impacts. This damage can be even more extensive when visitors stray off established trails. Trampling impacts on vegetation and soil causing Change in species composition Accelerated erosion and reduced plant vigor Reduction in soil macro porosity - Loss of ground cover Increase in run off - Reduced regeneration Decrease in water and air permeability⁴⁷.

Anchoring and other marine activities: In marine areas (beach and shoreline, around coastal waters, offshore waters, reefs, lagoons and uplands) many tourist activities arise in or around brittle ecosystems. Anchoring, scuba diving and sport fishing, snorkeling, cruising and yachting, are some of the activities that can be a reason for direct deterioration of marine ecosystems such as coral reefs, and following impacts on fisheries and coastal protection (Hall, 2001)⁴⁵.

D. Wildlife Disturbance Effects

Visitors can interfere with wildlife in a variety of ways, through their visual presence, noise, their movement and behavior. Different types will see the consequent disturbance for different reasons and in different ways. Wild life response and tolerance, and any impact results, will vary between different types, settings and times. Reasons contributing to these variations can contain ecological niche competition, breeding seasons and behaviors; different feeding patterns; life cycle

⁴⁶ *Tourism's Three Main Impact Areas: URL*
<http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Business/SectoralActivities/Tourism/FactsandFiguresaboutTourism/ImpactsofTourism/EnvironmentalImpacts/TourismsThreeMainImpactAreas/tabid/78776/Default.aspx>

⁴⁷ *Source: Source: United Nation Environmental programme, URL:*
<http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Home/Business/SectoralActivities/Tourism/tabid/78766/Default.aspx>

maturity; alarm behaviors; and territoriality. Some visitor effects may be incidental to wildlife, whereas others may be exactly directed at wildlife.

Additional visitor-related effects can also arise from the ways in which wildlife responds to the existence of staff; any of their related construction, maintenance and research activities; and the effects connected to the presence of facilities and structures (e.g. signs, lighting, color, noise, and tracks)⁴⁸.

E. Hazard Introduction Effects

The visitors can really harmful substance, biota, and external material when they come to the natural environment. The visitors may accidentally introduce hazard sources such as predators, diseases, and exotic weeds. Also they may introduce hazards from adverse behaviors such as inappropriate fire practices; bringing dogs; littering; or fuel leakage or disposal.

These may be direct effects, like leach ate from timber; chemicals from material degeneration, and exotic seeds in track fill or building materials. Or they may be indirect effects, like providing focal points for visitor congregation, fire potential, and providing access routes for predators⁴⁸.

F. Sewage

The health of humans and animals can be endangered by Sewage pollution. Construction of hotels and other facilities often result increased wastewater pollution. Sewage pollutes lakes and seas surrounding tourist attractions, causing damage in the fauna and flora. Sewage's flow causes severe damage to coral reefs because it contains lots of nutrients that stimulate the growth of algae, which cover the filter-feeding corals, preventing their ability to survive. Changes in transparency and salinity can have extensive impacts on coastal environments.

2.2.1.3 Eco-Tourist Activities

A. Snorkeling and Diving

Many tourist activities occur in fragile ecosystems, such as coral reefs, which are affected as a result of the market for souvenirs and because of the tourists that break off pieces of coral themselves (Gartner, 1996). Direct physical damage from snorkeling and diving has been the subject of extensive study and is well documented. The damage inflicted by divers and snorkelers consists mostly of breaking fragile, branched corals or causing lesions to massive corals. Most divers and snorkelers cause little damage; only a few cause severe or widespread damage.

Research indicates that reef degradation and change of reef community structure occurs once a certain level of use by divers and snorkelers is exceeded (UNEP 2005). As a rule of thumb it is recommended that the level of 5,000 to 6,000 dives per sites

⁴⁸ Md, GhulamRabbany. Sharmin Afrin. Airin Rahman. Faijul Islam. Fazlul Hoque. ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS OF TOURISM. American Journal of Environment. 2013

per year should not be exceeded. Training and briefing of divers and snorkelers will greatly help to reduce negative impacts.

The greatest impact of tourists on vegetation usually happens during first contact with an area, which most sensitive types affected first. Increased visitation at Arches National Park has contributed to the deterioration of the soil there, which can take up to 250 years to recover after being trampled⁴⁹.

B. Recreational Boating

The main problem linked with water quality and recreational boating is the discharge of sewage into water bodies nearby shellfish beds. Sewage contains pathogens which has a negative effect on the human health and can pollute shellfish. The following diseases that can probably transmit through human contact with ingestion of polluted shellfish and/or fecal discharge include dysentery, typhoid fever, nonspecific gastroenteritis, and infectious hepatitis (Seabloom, et al., 1989). Boating can cause direct physical damage to reefs, and fishing and collecting can contribute to over-exploitation of reef species and threaten local survival of endangered species. Indirect impacts relate to the development, construction and operation of tourism infrastructure as a whole for example resorts, marinas, ports and airports⁵⁰

Table 1: Activities with direct impact on the environment⁵⁰

N	Activities with direct impacts	Actual and/or potential impacts
1	Snorkeling	- Physical damage (breakage, lesions) Kicking up sediment
2	SCUBA diving	- Physical damage (breakage, lesions)
3	Motor boating and yachting	- Physical damage from anchoring - Physical damage from boat groundings
4	Fishing	- Contribute to over-exploitation of reef fish stocks Compete with local fishers
5	Collecting (shells, lobsters, conch, coral)	- Threatening local survival of rare species Contributing to over-exploitation and competing with local fishers

⁴⁹ Government Accountability Office and General Accounting (GAO). 2008.

⁵⁰ Recourse: UNEP 2005

2.3 Introduction of Sustainable Tourism

There is a narrow view for Sustainable tourism as a special kind of tourism that requests to a particular market niche that is take into account environmental and social impacts, although it is much more than a discreet or special form of tourism, It refers to an ultimate goal to make all tourism more sustainable.

It is on-going process of improvement, which applies evenly on tourism in cities, resorts, rural and coastal areas, hills and protected areas. According to South Australian Tourism Commission the sustainable tourism is a condition of tourism, not a type of tourism⁵¹.

One of the first definitions of sustainable tourism is that of the UN World Tourism Organization (WTO) in 1988: "Tourism activities are sustainable when they grow so as to maintain a living in a tourist area for an unlimited time, do not alter the environment (natural, social and artistic) and shall not restrict or inhibit the growth of other social and economic activities".

Other definitions of sustainable tourism: "Sustainable tourism development meets the needs of present tourists and host regions while protecting and enhancing opportunities for the future.

It must integrate the management of all resources in such a way that economic, social and aesthetic needs can be fulfilled while maintaining cultural integrity, essential ecological processes, biological diversity and life support systems." "Sustainable tourism is tourism and associated infrastructure, now and in the future, work within the natural capacity for regeneration and future productivity of natural resources; recognizes the contribution of tourism to the experience of populations, communities, customs and lifestyles; agree that people should have equitable distribution of economic benefits of tourism; is guided by the aspirations of local people and communities of the host" (World Travel & Tourism Council World Tourism Organization - Earth Council, 1996) "A tourism that can stand the test of time while maintaining its values and quantitative.

That is likely to coincide in the short and long term, the expectations of residents and tourists without reducing the quality of the tourist experience and without damaging the environmental values of the area affected by the phenomenon "(W.W.F.)⁵²

Sustainable tourism is an industry committed to make a low impact on the local culture, and environment, while helping to provide and generate future job

⁵¹ Australian tourism commission. *Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development*.2007

⁵² The World Wildlife Fund W.W.F. Is an international non-governmental organization founded on April 29, 1961, and is working on issues regarding the conservation, research and restoration of the environment.

opportunities for local people. It ensures that development is a positive experience for local people; tourism companies; and tourists themselves⁵³.

*Figure 3: Facets of sustainable tourism*⁵⁴

2.3.1 Kinds of Sustainable Tourism

Several institutions and commentators have implicit that sustainable tourism is a particular type of tourism appealing to a market niche that is sensitive to social and environmental impacts, serviced by particular types of products and operators, and usually implying small in scale.

This is a dangerous misunderstanding. The term ‘sustainable tourism’ must be clear that refers to a major objective: to make all tourism more sustainable. The term should be used to mention to a condition of tourism, not a type of tourism. Well-managed high-volume tourism can, and should be, just as sustainably as small-scale, dispersed special interest tourism⁵⁵.

Furthermore, sustainable tourism shouldn't be taken to imply a limited state of tourism. In fact, it is often argued that tourism may never be totally sustainable. Some countries by using the term ‘ecotourism’ as meaning the same as ‘sustainable tourism’ caused confusion compounded over the meaning of sustainable tourism. Ecotourism does indeed embrace the principles of sustainability, but it refers explicitly to a

⁵³ *khoshnevis Yazdi, Soheila. Sustainable Tourism .American International Journal of Social Science. 2012*

⁵⁴ *Source: Sustainable Tourism 2012*

⁵⁵ *Australian tourism commission. Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development.2007*

product niche. It is about tourism in natural areas, normally involving some form of interpretative experience of natural and cultural heritage, positively supporting conservation and indigenous communities, and usually organized for small groups. As was expounded in the Quebec Declaration on Ecotourism, 2002 the development of ecotourism can give a useful tool within wider strategies on the way to more sustainable tourism.

Figure 4: The relationship between Sustainable Tourism, Nature Tourism and Ecotourism⁵⁶

2.4 Goals of Sustainable Tourism

A suitable balance must be established between three dimensions of tourism development (environmental, economic and socio-cultural) to ensure its long-term sustainability. Thus, sustainable tourism should:

- A. Make best use of environmental resources which play a key element in tourism development, essential, maintaining, ecological processes and assisting to conserve natural biodiversity and heritage.
- B. Guarantee long-term, viable, economic operations, providing to all stakeholders socio-economic benefits that are fairly distributed, and contributing to poverty alleviation.
- C. Conserve living and built cultural heritage and traditional values of host communities, Respect their socio-cultural authenticity, and conserve their built

⁵⁶ Sustainable Tourism Definition URL:

<http://tourismdestinationpicture.blogspot.com/2015/02/sustainable-tourism-definition.html>

and living cultural heritage and traditional values, and contribute to tolerance and inter-cultural consideration.

The UNWTO grouped around the three goals of sustainability in the sustainable development of tourism: environmental preservation, social equity and cohesion and economic prosperity⁵⁷.

2.4.1 Environmental Preservation

Sustainable tourism recognized that future of tourism sector depends on protecting life in all its diversity. It integrates economic and ecological concerns by conserving natural areas which, in turn, generate increased revenues from tourism for future conservation.

2.4.2 Social Equity and Cohesion

Respect for, and understanding of, cultural diversity between nations and peoples. As a sector built on human interaction, tourism plays a key role in fostering greater respect and tolerance between cultures. It is a considerable force for the conservation of historic and cultural heritage and, by providing a source of income based around local culture, can encourage communities to value their cultural heritage more highly.

2.4.3 Economic Prosperity

Tourism is a driver of economic growth, accounting for 5% of global GDP and hundreds of millions of jobs worldwide. Sustainable tourism's contribution to poverty reduction and development is increasingly recognized. Its geographical expansion and labor intensive nature support the spread of employment and can be particularly relevant in remote and rural areas where many of the world's poorest live⁵⁷.

2.5 Principles of Sustainable Tourism

According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) the following 12 principles consider economic, social and environmental issues for more sustainable tourism; the order in which they are listed doesn't indicate any order of importance:

- A. Local prosperity: By strengthening business to business linkages and reducing leakages.
- B. Economic viability: Including various points such as understanding the market, maintaining and projecting an attractive destination, maintaining good trading conditions, and delivering business support and visitor satisfaction.
- C. Local control: Making effective local decision by improving the conditions, Guaranteeing empowerment and appropriate engagement of local

⁵⁷ World Tourism Organization. *Tourism and Sustainability*. 2011

communities, and addressing the specific position of indigenous and traditional communities with admiration to local control.

- D. Social equity: Voluntary sponsorship and giving by tourism enterprises or by tourists, including help in kind, utilization of compulsory or taxation levies made on tourism enterprises or tourists for social programs, supporting social programs by utilizing income, and rise income earning opportunities for underprivileged people.
- E. Visitor Fulfillment: Improving access for all, making sure to provision of meaningful information to tourists, providing holiday opportunities for the economically and socially deprived, maintaining a responsibility of care to visitors, monitoring the quality of experience and tourist services and monitoring visitor satisfaction.
- F. Employment Quality: Being worried about the well-being of employees who lose their jobs, enforcing and ensuring related labor regulations, rising the proportion and employment opportunities of all the year round, as a full time jobs, and finally, encouraging enterprises to afford career advancement and skills training programs.
- G. Community wellbeing: Decreasing congestion, getting the right balance in timing, location and the volume of visits, promoting mutual use of services and facilities by tourists and residents, careful management and planning of tourism infrastructure and enterprises, and affecting the behavior of tourists towards local communities.
- H. Physical integrity: Reducing the physical impact of the construction and the operation of tourism facilities, making sure that the new tourism development is suitable to local environmental conditions, and preserving high quality urban and rural landscapes as a tourism resource.
- I. Cultural Richness: To work with communities on the promotion and sensitive presentation of traditions and culture, upgrading the maintenance of the broader built environment, guaranteeing effective conservation and management of historic and cultural heritage sites.
- J. Resource Efficiency: Taking account of resource supply in the planning of tourism development, and vice versa. Minimizing water consumption and consumption of energy from non-renewable resources, emphasis on the efficient use of raw and land materials in tourism development, and supporting a “reduce, reuse, recycle” mentality.
- K. Environmental Purity: Influencing the development, minimizing the use of environmentally harmful chemicals, encouraging the use of more sustainable transport, refusing the discharge of sewage to river and marine environments and reducing and disposing waste with care.

- L. Biological Diversity: Promoting the development and management of ecotourism, working with protected areas and national parks, including private parks. Encourage landholders by using tourism to practice sustainable land management, rising support for conservation from enterprises and visitors, and reducing damage to natural heritage from the tourism⁵⁸.

2.6 Sustainable Tourism Development

The Brundtland report of the World Commission on Environment and Development - Our Common Future (1987) - gave the most frequently used definition of sustainable development which it means: "Development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs."⁵⁹

Since the 1987 the concept of sustainability has evolved definition to encirclement three pillars of sustainable development:

- A. Economic sustainability: has a focus on generating prosperity at different social hierarchies and making sure that the viability of enterprises and activities is maintained in the long-term.
- B. Social sustainability: has a focus on providing equal opportunities in society and respecting human rights. There is an assurance on local communities, recognizing and respecting different cultures and avoiding exploitation.
- C. Environmental sustainability: has a focus on conserving and managing resources, especially those that are not renewable, requiring action to minimize pollution of air, land and water and conserving biological diversity and natural heritage.

Tourism is in a unique position because of the contribution it can make to sustainable development and the challenges this presents. If developed without concern for sustainability, tourism can harm the natural, cultural or social environment. Conversely a sustainable approach to tourism has the capacity to benefit local communities, economically and socially, and to raise awareness and support for conservation of the environment. The CSIRO⁶⁰ in its report *Balancing Act: A triple bottom line analysis of the 135 sectors of the Australian economy, 2005* says the tourism industry has the ability to be a sustainability leader.

The definition of sustainable development which made in the Brundtland Report (United Nations, 1987), that attention to future generations becomes an obligatory policy for planning the economic development.

⁵⁸ UNWTO/UNEP Sustainable Tourism URL:
<http://www.grida.no/tourism/about.aspx?id=4794>

⁵⁹ *The Brundtland report of the World Commission on Environment and Development - Our Common Future 1987*

⁶⁰ *CSIRO is Australia's national science agency. We use science to solve real issues and our research makes a difference to industry, people, and the planet.*

From the concept of sustainable development derives the one of sustainable tourism understood as a tourism that combines the needs of present tourists and regions host protecting and enhancing opportunities for the future. Tourism development with its position in the global economy has a moral responsibility to take the lead in the transition towards sustainable development.

The product that the tourism industry and prepares sells is intimately linked with the clean beaches, untouched mountain slopes, water not polluted, the streets free from waste, buildings and archaeological sites well preserved and with different cultural traditions" (WTO, 1997) The environment is the basis of natural and cultural resources that attract tourists and that environmental protection is essential for long-term success of tourism. Planning must be carefully considering the carrying capacity of the area, reported that maximum use can be made of a site without causing adverse effects to its resources, decreasing the level of satisfaction of tourists and generating economic and social problems for the local community.

The general idea of sustainable development has been described as complex, vague and difficult to operationalize in practice, and these elements have followed many of the later definitions of the World Commission on Environment and Development's (WCED) original formulation. While the concept involves analytical weaknesses, it has also provided a common platform on which different stakeholders in development can interact, negotiate and reflect on the consequences and limits of their actions for the social, economic and ecological environment⁶¹.

2.7 Conclusion

Tourism can create great pressure on local resources such as energy, land, and water that may already be in short supply. The direct local impacts of tourism on people and the environment at destinations are strongly affected by concentration in space and time (seasonality). They result from:

- The intensive use of water by tourism and leisure facilities.
- The delivery and use of energy.
- Increasing the number of private vehicle trips. Most carbon monoxide of all Transportation modes is produced by far by Automobiles.
- Changes in the landscape coming from the construction of infrastructure, buildings and facilities.
- The intensive use of land which cause compaction and sealing of soils (damage and destruction of vegetation).
- The disturbance of fauna and local people.

⁶¹ *Drexhage, John. Murphy, Deborah. International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD). Sustainable Development. 2010*

- Solid Waste and littering.

A Sustainable Tourism Strategy is based on the information collected. It defines the priority issues, the stakeholder community, the potential objectives and a set of methodologies to reach these objectives. These include:

- Conservation of specific landscapes or habitats that make the area attractive or are protected under nature conservation legislation.
- Development of regionally specific sectors of the economy that can be interlinked with the tourism sector.
- Maximizing local revenues from tourism investments.
- Enabling self-determined cultural development in the region.

There are major challenges in sustainable tourism as a concept and development tool in practice. Instead of going beyond sustainability in tourism, there may be a real need to take serious steps back towards the original ideas of sustainable development. Therefore, the re-framing of sustainable tourism as a less tourism-centric activity operating in a local-global nexus is vital.

Sustainability is a crucial element for the future of tourism and this re-framing would make it a critical tool and dimension for the evaluations of the limits to growth in tourism with strong references to evolving discussions on ethical components in tourism. The ethical element in sustainable tourism development is built upon both theory and practice. This means that the industry would need to change and reconsider its position in development discourse if it really is aiming to promote sustainable development in tourism.

Chapter Three

Managing Environmental Impacts of Tourism in Coastal Zones

3.1 Tourism Development in Coastal Areas

Coastal tourism is a key component of coastal and marine economies. Coastal tourism is, in many countries, the fastest growing area of contemporary tourism, which has placed increased pressure on the coast, i.e. an area in which uses may already be highly concentrated in the form of agriculture, human settlements, fishing, industry, etc. (IOC/UNESCO, 2006).

The origins of tourism in coastal areas go back to Roman times, when the first villas were constructed in the Southern part of the Apennine peninsula. In the centuries that followed, especially from the mid-18th century onwards, coastal tourism was generally related to the therapeutic properties of sea and sun. Sun, sea and sand have continued to provide the main ingredients for coastal tourism until today⁶².

Coastal tourism is based on a unique resource combination at the interface of land and sea offering amenities such as water, beaches, scenic beauty, rich terrestrial and marine biodiversity, diversified cultural and historic heritage, healthy food and good infrastructure. It includes a diversity of activities that take place in both coastal zone and coastal waters, which involve the development of tourism capacities (hotels, resorts, second homes, restaurants, etc.) and support infrastructure (ports, marinas, fishing and diving shops, and other facilities). Coastal recreation activities, which have been increasing both in volume and in number, occupy a unique place in coastal tourism. They take in two main types of recreational uses of coastal zones: consumptive and non-consumptive ones. Activities such as fishing, shell fishing and shell collection, etc. belong in the first category while activities in the second include swimming, diving, boating, surfing, wind-surfing, jet skiing, bird watching, snorkeling, etc. Coastal tourism is strongly dependent upon natural (climate, landscape, ecosystems) and cultural (historic and cultural heritage, arts and crafts, traditions, etc.) resources. It encompasses activities that can only be carried out in particular areas and in specific conditions⁶³.

⁶² *Priority Actions Programme. UNEP. Sustainable Coastal Tourism an integrated planning and management approach. 2009*

⁶³ *schroeder, brandon. Johnson, laura. sustainable Coastal Tourism Development in Northeast Michiga. 2012*

Therefore, certain areas are considered to be particularly suited to specific types of tourism activities, for which they became known on a global scale. Besides physical conditions, the development of tourism in coastal areas is related to socio-economic features of the receiving environment such as local community interests, health and security conditions, political factors including unpredictable crises, exchange rate fluctuations, and traditional models of tourism exploitation or, simply, a successful or less effective marketing-led depiction of a destination. Environmental conditions such as unpredictable climate conditions, algae blooms, winds and the associated risk of forest fires, tsunamis, storms and floods, as well as many other constant features or unexpected events, affect tourism development in coastal areas⁶⁴.

Tourism development in coastal areas -including Resorts, hotels, airports and road construction- is often a matter for increasing concern worldwide as it can lead to sand mining, beach erosion and other forms of land degradation. Freshwater availability for competing agricultural, industrial, household and other uses is rapidly becoming one of the most critical natural resource issues in many countries and regions. Rapid expansion of the tourism industry, which tends to be extremely water-intensive, can exacerbate this problem by placing considerable pressure on scarce water supply in many destinations⁶⁵.

Water scarcity can pose a serious limitation to future tourism development in many low-lying coastal areas and small islands that have limited supplies of surface water, and whose groundwater may be contaminated by saltwater intrusion. Over-consumption by many tourist facilities -notably large hotel resorts and golf courses- can limit current supplies available to farmers and local populations in water-scarce regions and thus lead to serious shortages and price rises. In addition, pollution of available freshwater sources, some of which may be associated with tourism, related activities can also expansion of coastal and ocean tourism activities, such as snorkeling, scuba diving and sport fishing, can threaten fisheries and other marine resources. Disturbance to marine aquatic life can also be caused by the intensive use of thrill craft, such as jet skis, frequent boat tours and boat anchors⁶⁶.

Anchor damage is now regarded as one of the most serious threats to coral reefs in the Caribbean Sea, in view of the growing number of both small boats and large cruise ships sailing in the region. Severe damage to coral reefs and other marine resources may, in turn, not only discourage further tourism and threaten the future of local tourist industries, but also damage local fisheries. Exacerbate local shortages.

Integrated coastal zone management was defined at an international coastal zone workshop in 1989 as “a dynamic process in which a coordinated strategy is developed

⁶⁴ *schroeder, brandon. Johnson, laura. sustainable Coastal Tourism Development in Northeast Michiga. 2012*

⁶⁵ *Priority Actions Programme. UNEP. Sustainable Coastal Tourism an integrated planning and management approach. 2009*

⁶⁶ *Lal Mukherjee, Abir. Impact of tourism in coastal areas: Need of sustainable tourism strategy. 2013*

and implemented for the allocation of environmental, socio – cultural and sustainable multiple uses of the coastal zone” (CAMPNET, 1989).

Basic concept and principles of coastal zone management and the associated planning processes, as well as the various mechanisms that need to be developed were elaborated. The ICZM is designed to address key issues arising from conflicting uses of the space, the environment and the resources.

Key issues commonly referred to include the loss of habitats, resources, pollution of environment, coastal erosion, deforestation and changes in physical conditions that produce harmful results⁶⁷.

The central point in the whole approach towards ICZM is to develop an inter-sectoral and harmonized approach to resolve those key issues without detracting the users of coastal zone from their mandatory functions and responsibilities.

Key elements of integrated coastal zone management planning process such as integration of national efforts vertically at all levels in the government and horizontally across various sectors and agencies, and the need for inter-sectoral coordination were described, citing example case studies. The implications of physical environmental change for coastal zone management were highlighted⁶⁸.

Awareness and understanding of the nature and scale of the physical changes were considered as prerequisites for environmental-policy making and management. Only then the economic implications of the change can be properly assessed and the risks spelled out in time scale and terms of the economic consequences.

It is clear that coastal tourism depends on the quality and diversity of the coastal environment. Increases in tourist numbers have been shown to threaten areas of high ecological and resource value in the coastal environment. Finally, the integrated management approach should not only be applied for general coastal zone management but also for special sectors such as coastal tourism (IOC/UNESCO, 2006).

3.2 Essential Step in Managing the Impacts of Development

In order to manage the impacts of a development a well understood is needed. The impact of development must be considered beyond the scale of a building or a site. They must be considered at a range of scales, from specific building locations to site, site catchment and more global systems.

The best way to begin to understand how to manage the impacts of a development is to start by gathering some basic information (knowledge) that can then be used during the

⁶⁷ Nurhidayah, Laely . *Toward Integrated Coastal Zone Management in Indonesia: Framework Assessment and comparative analysis*. 2010

⁶⁸ Kir, Gee. Kannen, Andreas. Glaeser, Bernhard. Sterr, Horst. *National ICZM Strategies in Germany: A Patial Planing Approach*. 2004

design process. The first essential steps in the process are climate, location and site analysis.

These steps can assist with establishing some basic design concepts based on broad environmental constraints, then refining these considering local issues and tailoring them to a specific site. As design is a cyclical process, it may be necessary to work through the various issues a number of times before a final design evolve.

3.2.1 Climate Analysis

The basic information that needs to be gathered to design for climate includes:

- A. The path (vertical and horizontal angle) of the sun during the year
- B. The temperature range
- C. The annual rainfall amount and annual distribution
- D. The wind intensity, direction and occurrence
- E. The most likely direction of storms, cold or strong winds
- F. The most common directions of good breezes.

Climate analysis is taking on greater importance as society begins to understand the long-term implications of climate change. Climate change will present significant challenges but also provide opportunities for innovation⁶⁹.

3.2.2 Location Analysis

A locality can be seen as the catchment of a site. It might also be considered as an extension of the site. Potential impacts of the development should be considered at this broader scale. Locality analysis should be carried out to consider issues such as:

- A. Identifying an appropriate site and the scale or type of development that might suit
- B. Access to local resources and services such as food, building materials, fuel, labor, water sources and infrastructure
- C. Access to quality environmental values such as natural ecosystems, local culture and history
- D. The tourism appeal of the area

It is necessary to gain a broad picture of the locality before making detailed decisions about the suitability, type, design or management of the development. This is a key input into feasibility analysis, especially in its early stages⁷⁰.

⁶⁹ *Climate Data Analysis Tools and Methods: URL: <https://climatedataguide.ucar.edu/climate-data-tools-and-analysis>*

⁷⁰ *Australian tourism commission. Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development.2007*

Figure 5 is an example of a locality analysis. Locality and site analysis is fundamental to sustainable design and should be prepared early in the design process.

Figure 5: Example of a location analysis⁷¹

3.2.3 Site Analysis

The site is the likely or specific location for built development. In some projects the site is a given, while in others it becomes apparent through locality analysis. Site analysis needs to be undertaken to enable correct decisions to be made about the design and layout of the overall development and the exact location of built elements.

There are some general principles to be followed when deciding upon the specific site for a structure:

- A. Build on the least sensitive areas, or areas that have already been subject to human disturbance
- B. Site the development in an area with natural values that can be used to interpret the environment in a wider context
- C. Consider the type of tenure and rights of access and use
- D. Optimize the best available views without building on prominent points or ridgelines.

The type and detail of information as part of the site analysis will depend upon factors such as type, scale and intensity of the development and the nature of site conditions⁷².

⁷¹ Australian tourism commission. *Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development*.2007

One way to evaluate the potential of the site to sustain a tourism use is to evaluate the carrying capacity of the site. Carrying capacity is a measure of the amount of human activity a site can sustain without significant change to the ecology. An assessment of carrying capacity might include factors such as the:

- Fragility or resilience of the site
- Availability of water and power resources
- Type of development
- Maximum number of visitors
- Connections to different parts of the site like bushwalking trail or swimming at a nearby beach.

A Site Analysis Plan should be prepared to depict graphically the various factors that will influence the development. This Plan will also be useful for the planning authority to understand why certain design responses have been chosen⁷³.

Figure 6: Example of a broad site analysis plan⁷⁴

⁷² *Environmental Sciences*: URL: <http://www.ukessays.com/essays/environmental-sciences/principles-to-be-followed-while-designing-environmental-sciences-essay.php>

⁷³ *Environmental Sciences*: URL: <http://www.ukessays.com/essays/environmental-sciences/principles-to-be-followed-while-designing-environmental-sciences-essay.php>

3.3 Basic Elements in the Environmental Design

Sustainable tourism development always needs to respect the environment and refer to accepted principles of sustainability. It must be planned to make balanced use of the resources of any site, thus avoiding negative effects, reducing visitor satisfaction, or adversely impacting the local society, economy and culture.

Sometimes it may be difficult to quantify limits, but they are essential for sustainable tourism. Thus, if it is to maintain the main elements on which it is based, the tourism sector needs to invest in the maintenance of the natural environment. If properly planned, tourism can become a positive force for conservation and environmental protection, and economic development⁷⁵.

These elements are most relevant for developments that occur in close proximity to sensitive natural environments.

3.3.1 Energy

Energy efficiency is one of the easiest and most cost effective ways to combat climate change clean the air we breathe, improve the competitiveness of our businesses and reduce energy costs for consumer⁷⁶.

Lower energy use can reduce operational costs and reduces Greenhouse Gas emissions (like nitrous oxide, carbon dioxide, and methane). Environmental impacts can be reduced by using energy from a renewable source such as wind, solar and water.

3.3.2 Water

There is a variety of purposes in tourism developments that use the water such as washing, bathing and waste disposal. The main water sources in remote areas normally include surface water, rainwater and groundwater. In some areas controls should be exist on the taking of surface water and groundwater.

Rainfall also could provide a sustainable water supply and is used as the most important water source in remote tourism development with taking precautions to maintain water quality for guests. Regardless of the water source, a sustainable tourism development should aim to use water efficiently at all times and take measures to conserve water⁷⁷.

⁷⁴ Australian tourism commission. *Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development*. 2007

⁷⁵ Ministry for the Environment and Territory. *Environmental Action Strategy For Sustainable Development In Italy*

⁷⁶ Energy Efficiency: URL: <http://energy.gov/science-innovation/energy-efficiency>

⁷⁷ Sustainability and Water: URL: <http://www.overpopulation.org/water.html>

3.3.3 Land

Land is made up of a number of elements and systems that interact to form natural landscapes. It is possible to place a building in a natural landscape and have minimal impact on these elements and systems.

A common expression used in sustainable development is to ‘touch the earth lightly’. While some change to the environment is inevitable through human activity, a sustainable tourism development should ensure that the environment continues to function as an intact ecosystem⁷⁸.

3.3.4 Materials

Products environmental impact is directly influenced by the environmental properties of the materials used, such as energy costs, emissions involved in production. Therefore materials that comprise the built environment should be viewed from a life-cycle viewpoint. This involves considering source, material availability, consumption, reusability, durability, embodied energy, recycling, and contamination issues⁷⁹.

3.3.5 Waste

Responsible management of waste is an essential aspect of sustainable building. In this context, managing waste means eliminating waste where possible; minimizing waste where feasible; and reusing materials which might otherwise become waste.

Solid waste management practices have identified the reduction, recycling, and reuse of wastes as essential for sustainable management of resources. Construction phase and using the building produce waste which is not only visual pollution of the site but it also has the potential to cause contamination of the water, air and soil with fumes, chemical residues and nutrients⁸⁰.

3.3.6 Transport

Land-based transport includes a wide range of options that are used by visitors when travelling to a destination including self-drive (car, caravan or RV⁸¹), bikeways, coach, walkways, and public transport on rail and bus networks. Planning and development of required road infrastructure for drive tourism needs to be matched with an understanding of visitor characteristics and preferences⁷⁹.

⁷⁸ *Green Building Basics* :URL: <http://www.calrecycle.ca.gov/greenbuilding/basics.htm>

⁷⁹ *The design and construction of environmentally sustainable new buildings*: URL: <http://www.environment.admin.cam.ac.uk/resource-bank/guidance-documents/design-and-construction-environmentally-sustainable-new-buildings>

⁸⁰ *Construction Waste Management*: URL: <http://www.wbdg.org/resources/cwmgmt.php>

⁸¹ *RV: Recreational vehicle*

Figure 7: Basic elements in environmental design

3.4 International Examples

This part investigates tourism development through advanced international examples that present elements of sustainable design, construction and operation. These examples focus on accommodation and provide selected examples from South Australia and United State.

This part will also conduct a comparative analysis of the three buildings that conclude the most common environmental strategies that can be achieved to reduce the Impacts of development

3.4.1 Criteria of Selection

3.4.1.1 The criteria

- 1- These international examples offer an insight into the unique approach that each development has taken.
2. Each of these cases is awarded various certificates from leading sustainable tourism development associations.
 - The first example is The Bay of Fire Lodge. This building is award-winning architectural design and eco-lodge.

- The second building is Aquila Eco Lodges. The edifice was awarded Eco Certification and AAA Green Rating. Aquila Eco Lodges was also successful in achieving Ecotourism Australia Certification.
- Finally, Shore Hotel was awarded LEED Gold certificate and it offers eco-friendly accommodations with views of the Pacific Ocean. These examples also focus and provide the opportunity to learn from existing developments and, hopefully, improve upon them.

3.4.1.2 The Study Points

- 1- Site and Location Features
- 2- Architectural Features
- 3- Environmental Design Actions in the field of:
 - Energy
 - Water Use
 - Impact on the Land
 - Material
 - Waste
 - Transportation

Methods of studying these examples will be based on two aspects, firstly, investigating the aspects of the sustainable tourism development, and secondly, studying success strategies in managing environmental and sustainable tourism development actions.

3.4.2 The Bay of Fires Lodge

The Bay of Fires Lodge is located at Mount William National Park⁸² at the East Coast TAS⁸³ of Australia. This simple accommodation Set on a hilltop, 40 meters above the pounding of the sea and surrounded by National Park and it's the only building on 20km of coastal wilderness.

The Bay of Fires Lodge is an ecologically-aware building consists of two long timber and glass pavilions which allow maximum connection to the landscape with minimum impact on the environment.

Bay of Fires Lodge was established and designed by acclaimed Tasmanian architect Ken Latona to provide a unique, educational and environmentally sustainable way of experiencing the dramatic landscape of Mount William National Park.

⁸² *Mount William is a national park in Tasmania, Australia. Mt William National Park is located 234 km northeast of Hobart and it was established in 1973 as an 8,640 hectares large national park.*

⁸³ *Tasmania TAS is an island state that is part of the Commonwealth of Australia.*

Satellite Image 1: The Bay of Fires Lodge, Date: 2015

3.4.2.1 Site Features

As mentioned before the Bay of Fires Lodge located on a hilltop, 40 meters above the sea level. And it set on 35 hectares of private property, which contains a dramatic and diverse wilderness landscape of white sandy coastline and woodland scenery. The site is loaded with extraordinary wildlife including Eastern Grey Kangaroos, echidnas, wallabies and Tasmanian Devils as well as over 100 species of birdlife.

Figure 8: Aerial view of the Bay of Fires Lodge

3.4.2.2 Architectural Features

The Bay of Fires Lodge consists of two linear pavilions constructed principally of timber and glass joint by large timber decks. The Lodge provides lodging for 20 guests and six staff. There are common areas for dining both indoor and outdoor, a reading room and a lounge room and shared bathroom facilities. Meals are prepared in a communal kitchen. The Bay of Fires Lodge has a wood combustion stove in the living area and quality furniture, fittings and fixtures. Pedestrians can reach the lodge by foot from a private vehicle, road approximately 200 meters away, or from the beach as part of the guided walk. The building is not visible until almost upon it because of the dense vegetation, successfully achieving a dramatic sense of arrival. It is also accessible by helicopter for delivery and removal of large material⁸⁴.

Figure 9: The Bay of Fires Lodge balconies and interior spaces

⁸⁴ *Architectural Record*: URL:
<http://archrecord.construction.com/projects/portfolio/archives/0107ecolodge.asp>

3.4.2.3 Environmental Design Actions

A. Energy

The site is not connected with the main power supply. Therefore, The Bay of Fires Lodge uses solar energy as the main source of energy. However, a back-up generator is used in case of emergency.

On the other hand, passive solar design features was achieved to reduce energy consumption and this include extensive use of glass louvers to provide sunlight penetration and cross-ventilation, the louvers are shielded from the direct summer sun by 1200mm leaves on the skillion roof⁸⁵, the long north facade and skillion roof, and thus to the fact that the building is only opened during summer the architect used of a lightweight structure where no thermal mass⁸⁶ is required to retain heat.

The architect had also used interior design strategies to ensure energy conservation and this practice included the use of Instantaneous gas hot water systems, WC fan vents powered by solar energy, low energy lighting, and finally, Fridges, cooktop and barbecue are powered by LPG⁸⁷. Cylinders are brought in and removed every six months by helicopter.

B. Water

There is no mains water on the site so the water source for the Lodge is supplied by rainwater collected from the roofs into five, 22,000-litre tanks. This water is used for drinking, showers, kitchen use, and bushfire protection.

AAA rated water flow restrictors have been installed on fittings to minimize water consumption. And solar power pump have been installed to supply water to the kitchen, and finally and on the contrary water for showers and basins is hand-pumped from the water tanks by visitors to a header tank on the roof.

This hands-on approach to water use, and visibility of tanks were used to give guests a greater appreciation of their water usage and encourage conservation⁸⁸.

⁸⁵ A mono-pitched roof is a single-sloping roof surface, often not attached to another roof surface. Mono-pitched roofs are sometimes called a shed roof, lean-to roof, or skillion roof in Australia.

⁸⁶ In building design, thermal mass is a property of the mass of a building which enables it to store heat.

⁸⁷ Liquefied petroleum gas or liquid petroleum gas (LPG or LP gas), also referred to as simply propane or butane, is a flammable mixture of hydrocarbon gases used as fuel in heating appliances, cooking equipment, and vehicles.

⁸⁸ Tasmanian Expeditions Pty Limited. bay of fires lodge walk Experience the very best of the Bay of Fires wilderness. 2012

C. Land

The architect insured that the removal of trees and vegetation will be minimized. Only three trees were removed during the building process. All efforts were made to minimize damage to surrounding vegetation during construction and use.

D. Materials

The Designer selected lightweight building materials, where these materials were either brought by helicopter or walked in. And to minimize the amount of wastage, limited types of materials were used. These materials included Tasmanian hardwood and plantation pine structure, cladding and flooring, corrugated steel roof sheeting and glass. Walls are of single skin construction reducing the amount of material required⁸⁹.

E. Waste

As mentioned before, there is no mains power, mains water or sewage connection to the site. All sewage and organic kitchen waste is treated on site in a Clivus Multrum Dry composting system⁹⁰.

Figure 10: Clivus Multrum Dry composting system⁹¹

⁸⁹ *Tasmanian Expeditions Pty Limited. bay of fires lodge walk Experience the very best of the Bay of Fires wilderness.2012.*

⁹⁰ *Clivus Multrum is a type of composting toilet and the name of a company that markets this brand name of composting toilets. "Clivus" is Latin for incline or slope; "multrum" is a Swedish composite word meaning "compost room," thus a "Clivus Multrum" is an inclining compost room.*

However, waste water is removed from the system and passed through a digester where it is further filtered through a fine weave material treated with bacteria and then passed into a transpiration trench where it evaporates.

Kitchen waste water is run through a grease trap and then into the digester. Basin waste water runs straight to the digester. During construction the waste were centralized and the site was kept tidy to minimize the impact on the surrounding bush.

F. Transport

The nearest vehicle access to The Bay of Fires Lodge is 200 meter. The architect requested that the local tip, which is six kilometers away, should be used as a base for trucks delivering materials.

These materials were then divided into loads of a maximum 500kg and flown into site by helicopter.

3.4.3 Aquila Eco Lodges

To promote the philosophy and ease of sustainable living Aquila Eco Lodges was established by Barb Bjerking and Madeleine Claus as a family business, this modern and luxury eco accommodation is set on 100 acres of eucalyptus forest, sharing borders with the Grampians National Park and the delightful Dunkeld⁹² Golf Course.

Aquila Eco Lodges has achieved sustainable living, along with the ability to conserve and preserve the natural environment, its flora and fauna.

And therefore, it has granted Eco Certification and AAA⁹³ Green Rating. Aquila Eco Lodges was also successful in achieving Ecotourism Australia Certification.⁹⁴

3.4.3.1 Site Features

According to "South Australian Tourism Commission"⁹⁵ Aquila Eco Lodges are set in 100 acres of freehold land that is covered by a covenant enforced by Trust for Nature.

⁹¹ <http://www.clivusne.com/science-and-technology.php>

⁹² Dunkeld is a town in Victoria, Australia at the southern end of the Grampians National Park, in the Shire of Southern Grampians. It is approx 283 km west of Melbourne on the Glenelg Highway.

⁹³ AAA: The highest possible rating assigned to the bonds of an issuer by credit rating agencies. An issuer that is rated AAA has an exceptional degree of creditworthiness and can easily meet its financial commitments.

⁹⁴ The ECO Certification logo means that you are guaranteed to experience a genuine and authentic attraction or accommodation that looks after the environment. The ECO certification program assures you that certified products are backed by a commitment to sustainable practices and provides high quality nature-based tourism experiences.

⁹⁵ "Design Guide Lines For Sustainable Tourism Development"

Covenant conditions permitted building only in areas where there would be minimal disturbance to existing vegetation.

The National Park contains a very dramatic range of rugged Rocky Mountains projecting abruptly from the surrounding bush land. Vegetation in the area consists of brown stringy bark forest, and the wildlife is prolific.

Notable species include the Eastern Grey Kangaroo, Swamp Wallaby, Emu, Wedge-tailed Eagle and numerous parrots and other birdlife.

Satellite Image 2: Aquila Eco Lodges, Date: 2015

3.4.3.2 Architectural Feature

Aquila Eco Lodges include 4 architect designed lodges that are build a fair distance from each other to create a sense of privacy, each lodge is surrounded by bush garden and include a privet parking area.

There are two types of lodges on Aquila property, Treehouse and Lofthouse design. The Treehouse consists of three levels, the ground level hold the BBQ area is on. The living area, kitchen and bathroom are on the second level, and the bedroom on the third level.

The Loft house on the other hand is built to accommodate families and small groups of friends. It is a two level structure, the ground floor hold the living area, kitchen and one bedroom, and the second bedroom is on a mezzanine floor on the next level. The tiled,

roofed verandah extends from the lounge room area. BBQ with a sitting area and are located there and adjacent to it a private sandstone bathroom⁹⁶.

Figure 11: Aquila Eco Lodges⁹⁷

3.4.3.3 Environmental Design Actions

A. Energy

Similar to The Bay of Fires Lodge, The site is not connected with the main power supply. Therefore, Aquila Eco Lodges uses solar energy as the main source of energy. However, a back-up generator is used in case of emergency.

This generator is fueled by bio-diesel where vegetable oil waste is collected from a local restaurant and converted on-site into bio-diesel. Some designed methods were applied to insure the achievement of Passive thermal design principles, this includes: North facing glazing, Insulated walls and roof, Concrete slab on ground for thermal mass.

⁹⁶ *Aquila Eco Lodges - a Nature Retreat. URL:*
<http://www.stayz.com.au/accommodation/vic/the-grampians/dunkeld/112893>

⁹⁷ *Aquila Eco Lodges - a Nature Retreat. URL:*
<http://www.stayz.com.au/accommodation/vic/the-grampians/dunkeld/112893>

The architects had also used interior design strategies to ensure energy conservation and this practice included the use of Instantaneous gas hot water systems to minimize water wastage, and Low energy lighting and appliances⁹⁸.

B. Water

There is no mains water on the site so the water source for the Lodge is supplied by rainwater collected from the roofs, rainfall to the area is approximately 600mm to 700mm annually, and is augmented with water collected from the creek during seasonal flow, and this is currently providing an adequate water supply.

AAA rated water flow restrictors have been installed on all fittings to minimize water consumption. Finally a separate 40,000 liter rainwater tank has been installed for firefighting purposes. The installation maintained specifically for roof-mounted fire sprinklers and fire hoses located between each lodge. This water supply will last for 30 minutes.

C. Land

Disturbance to vegetation and preventing soil erosion during the construction process was minimized. Additional indigenous trees have been planted between units to enhance visual privacy.

D. Materials

All building materials have been selected for passive thermal performance, cost effectiveness, durability, low embodied energy and minimal toxic waste. These materials include local timber and local stone, fiber cement sheeting with timber battens to join to interior and exterior walls, a concrete slab floor and timber framed structure, and waterbased paint systems. No PVC pipes were used in this structure.

E. Waste

Inorganic household waste is separated and it is taken to recycling bins in Dunkeld by the management, however, organic kitchen waste and sewage is treated on site in a Downus Worm Farm sewage treatment system, filtered nutrient rich waste water is removed from the system and released into the soil via a soakage trench⁹⁹.

⁹⁸ Australian tourism commission. *Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development*.2007

⁹⁹ Soakage trenches are shallow lined trenches backfilled with sand and coarse stone. The trench surface can be covered with grating, stone, sand, grass or similar vegetation. They accept storm water runoff from roofs, parking lots, and other impervious surfaces, and can be placed under any ground-level porous surface such as yards and landscaped areas.

Soakage trenches reduce runoff flow rate, volume, and temperature and recharge groundwater. With a sufficient amount of sand or soil for filtration, they may be used to meet pollution reduction requirements. Soakage Trenches. Environmental Services, City of Portland, P.01.

Michael Green wrote in his article "Home Owners in Unsewered Areas Can Choose Greener Systems than Septics" that this worm farm system requires minimal ongoing maintenance, no chemical additives, and uses little power⁹⁸.

Figure 12: Downmus worm farm sewage treatment system

Figure 13: Downmus worm farm sewage treatment system¹⁰⁰

¹⁰⁰ <http://www.nrc.govt.nz/Resource-Library-Summary/Publications/Waste/Septic-tanks-and-sewerage-systems/Septic-tanks/>

3.4.4 The Shore Hotel

Shore hotel is a private property owned by Farzam family. The hotel is located on Ocean Avenue in Santa Monica, USA. The Shore Hotel is a new addition to the coastline and LEED Gold certified property that offers eco-friendly accommodations with views of the Pacific Ocean.

3.4.4.1 Architecture Features

Shore hotel include 164 rooms, each of which enjoys a private beach facing balcony. The main building is U-shaped and surrounds a heated pool which is solar thermal and is also clad in pale sandstone to reflect sunlight.

A steel-trussed roof outfitted with electric blue lighting serves as the gateway and entrance to the hip beach spot.

The building also include two dining establishments, meeting and special event spaces, a fitness center, a four-story underground parking lot with 300 public parking spaces, as well as the city's beaches¹⁰¹

Figure 14: Shore Hotel main elevation, California¹⁰²

¹⁰¹ Gensler Architecture to Envision New Eco-friendly Shore Hotel: URL: <http://www.hotelmanagement.net/gensler-architecture-to-envision-new-eco-friendly-shore-hotel-10694>

¹⁰² Source: http://www.tripadvisor.com/LocationPhotoDirectLink-g33052-d2257239-i79215410-Shore_Hotel-Santa_Monica_California.html

3.4.4.2 Environmental Design Actions

A. Energy

In order to save energy, Shore hotel used energy-efficient systems such as energy heat recover, automatic sensors and high efficient elevator.

In California, The hotel was the first to Implement "Savings by Design program" which allowed it to participate in California Edison's Auto Demand Response, and this enabled Shore hotel to earn incentives for reducing the use of energy during peak hours.

The design also provided naturally-day lit and ventilated rooms to reduce energy consumption.

B. Water

Shore Hotel collects and treats storm water through a storm water management plan and facilities, in addition, low-flow water fixtures had been used to reduce water consumption inside the rooms, such as a high efficiency toilets and low flow showerheads. Finally, the hotel used native plants in the vegetation of the landscape.

C. Materials

The current owners, the Farzam family, used to have two motels at the same location, the Pacific Sands and Travelodge, they decided to demolish these structures and recycle more than 50 percent of the construction waste to use in the new hotel.

Furthermore, 10% of the new building materials were chosen from within a 500 mile radius. And Low VOC (Volatile Organic Compounds) materials were also used.

In the interior spaces, the lobby chairs were upholstered with 100% from pre-consumer recycled polyester. Guest room carpet was also manufactured with Eco Solution Q Nylon, which contains a minimum of 25% recycled content¹⁰³.

3.5 Comparative Analysis

The comparative analysis in this section involves the synthesis and analysis of the similarities and differences across these international cases, this cases examination is focusing on the most successful way to achieve sustainability in tourism throughout managing the Impacts of Development on the environment.

¹⁰³ *Style by the shore: URL:*

<http://www.worldarchitecturenews.com/wanmobile/mobile/article/19713>

Table 002: Comparative Analysis

(Environmental design strategies comparative analysis between The Bay of Fires Lodge, Aquila Eco-Lodges and the Shore Hotel)

N.	Criteria	N.	Sub- criteria	The Bay Lodge	Aquila Lodges	Shore Hotel
I	Energy Conservation	A	The Implementation of Passive Solar Design	Yes	Yes	Yes
		B	The Use of Renewable Energy Resources	Yes	Yes	Yes
		C	The Use of Low Embodied Energy Building Materials	No	Yes	No
		D	The Utilize of Energy Efficient Mechanical Equipment and Appliance	Yes	Yes	Yes
II	Systemization of Water Use	A	The Treatment and Re-use of Waste Water	Yes	Yes	Yes
		B	The Possibility of Waterless Toilet Systems Use	Yes	Yes	No
		C	The Utilize of Accredited Water Efficient Devices and Equipment	Yes	Yes	Yes
III	The Impacts of the Building's Element on the Land	A	Minimize Negative Impacts on Site Vegetation	Yes	Yes	No
		B	Minimize any Impacts on Topsoil	Yes	Yes	No
		C	Minimize Changes to the Hydrology in Terms of Quality, Volume and Distribution	Yes	Yes	No
		D	Minimize any Impacts on Topography	Yes	Yes	No
		E	Minimize Site Impacts on Fauna	Yes	Yes	No
		F	Minimize the Risk of Bushfires and Grass Fires	Yes	Yes	No
IV	Materials	A	The Use of Recycled Materials	No	No	Yes
		B	The Use of Local Building Materials	Yes	Yes	Yes
V	Waste Management	A	Managing Organic Materials	Yes	Yes	Yes
		B	Managing Non-Organic Materials	Yes	Yes	Yes
VI	Transport	A	The Use of Bicycle Linkages with Nearby Attractions	Yes	Yes	Yes

N.	Criteria	N.	Sub- criteria	The Bay Lodge	Aquila Lodges	Shore Hotel
		B	Decrease the Area of Car Parking	Yes	No	No
		C	Providing Environmental Transportation Systems within the Site Parameters	Yes	Yes	No

3.6 Conclusion

Through the previous examples of tourist infrastructure, we found successful strategies used that significantly minimized the negative impacts on the environment during the development process. These environmental strategies are:

Energy conservation

The three examples have the same aim which is saving energy and to achieve that different actions are used:

- Implement of passive solar design,
- Using renewable energy resources,
- The utilize of energy efficient mechanical equipment and appliance
- using low embodied energy building materials

Water Systemization

The actions that used to achieve this purpose are:

- The treatment and re-use of waste water
- The possibility of waterless toilet systems use
- The utilize of accredited water efficient devices and water efficient equipment

Reduce the Impacts of the Building's Element on the Land

The actions that used to achieve this purpose are:

- Minimize negative impacts on site vegetation
- Minimize any impacts on topsoil
- Minimize changes to the hydrology in terms of quality, volume and distribution
- Minimize any impacts on topography
- Minimize site impacts on fauna
- Minimize the risk of bushfires and grass fires

Choice of Materials

The actions that used to achieve this purpose are:

- The use of local building materials
- The use of recycled materials

Waste Management

The actions that used to achieve this purpose are:

- Managing organic materials
- Managing non-organic materials

Transportation

The actions that used to achieve this purpose are:

- The use of bicycle linkages with nearby attractions
- Decrease the area of car parking
- Providing environmental transportation systems within the site parameters

All these environmental strategies along others can be helpful to decrease the negative impact of tourism activities and insure sustainable development. These case studies are good example of effective tourism planning, instead of indiscriminate development based solely on economics, planners first determined the needs of the local people, and then designed the area accordingly.

The following chapter will state possible environmental actions to ensure that the development process has low impact on the environment.

Chapter Four

Environmental Design Guidelines for Coastal Sustainable Tourism Development

Everyone is looking to be more environmentally conscious. There is a concern about the carbon footprint left behind, and it's become imperative to conserve energy. Tourism projects in particular, have a great potential for energy conservation. With just a few changes, its administration can ensure that they are doing their best to protect the environment while still providing an excellent experience for their customers.

In the coastal zone beaches, harbor, national parks, green mountain and climate are intrinsic part of the area's charm, consequently there are much more that should be done to promote all the coastal natural attractions, also it should be developed in ways that are sustainable and which conserve the very qualities that visitors are seeking. In the context of tourism development process this is possible through a systematic approach to make the environmental requirements as factors of innovation for a successful and sustainable tourism¹⁰⁴.

This can be achieved in accordance to the project Lifecycle, which takes into consideration all phases of project from concept development to construction phase, and finally, the operation period.

The development process is in a sensitive area; therefore, it is a must to closely consider all issues. In reality not all issues will be relevant or a priority for all developments. The key issues will include land, energy, materials, water and waste treatment. However, factors such as quality, production feasibility, requirements of use, servicing will also be considered as sub-environmental aspects.

The concept of ICZM is a highly accepted paradigm having had a huge support from the 1992 Earth summit and its Agenda 21, particularly chapter 17 on "protection of the oceans and coastal area" and the 1993 world coast conference held in Noordwijk, the Netherlands integrated coastal zone management involves the management of coastal waters and related land resources in an integrated manner¹⁰⁵. The concept of such management includes three main tasks:

- Planning which involves analysis and design

¹⁰⁴ CSIL Centre for Industrial Studies. *The Impact Of Tourism On Coastal Areas: Regional Development Aspects*. 2008

¹⁰⁵ United Nation. *Conference On Environment And Development* : URL:
http://www.un.org/depts/los/consultative_process/documents/A21-Ch17.htm

- Implementation, which involves execution, installation phase
- Operation and feedback evaluation (Ehler et al. 1995).

4.1 Methods to Ensure Sustainable Development of tourism projects during Projects Life Cycle

According to the United Nations Environment Programme, World Tourism Organization, South Australian Tourism Commission, New South Wales Department of Environment and Conservation and the examples that have been discussed before, Design guidelines consider the wide range of complex and interrelated issues that affect the level of human activity a particular environment can sustain¹⁰⁶. The Design Guidelines have a consistent format that includes:

- Brief description of each development issue.
- Basic information that needs to be gathered to commence analysis of the issues.
- Describes a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes. These environmental actions are divided into those that are relevant for:
 - A. Design phase.
 - B. Construction Phase
 - C. Project operation phase

4.1.1 in the Field of Energy Conservation

Important issues that contribute to reducing energy consumption include:

- Passive solar design
- Renewable energy
- Embodied energy
- Mechanical appliances and equipment

4.1.1.1 Passive Solar Design

Passive solar design is design that reduces the need for mechanical cooling and heating. Buildings that are passively designed exploit natural energy flows to preserve thermal comfort, and determine the types of materials that used in the building¹⁰⁷.

Passive solar design aims to (Design for Climate) Use Passive Solar Design to reduce the energy used for cooling and heating, and preserve thermal comfort. First there are initial information should be clear such as (What is the site orientation? Does the site

¹⁰⁶ World Tourism Organisation. *Tourism Investing in energy and resource efficiency. United Nations Environment Programme, 2011*

¹⁰⁷ *Energy Efficiency: URL: <http://energy.gov/science-innovation/energy-efficiency>*

have good solar access? What are the prevailing winds (direction, likely speed, likely occurrence and duration?)¹⁰⁸.

HOT-DRY INLAND CLIMATE MODEL

TEMPERATE CLIMATE MODEL: COASTAL

Figure 15: Illustrate building design solutions in response to the broad climate regions.

There is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

-In planning:

- A. Orient buildings so that solar access can be easily controlled by simple fixed shading systems (awnings and roof). Buildings should have walls generally

¹⁰⁸ *Fundamental Principles of Green Building and Sustainable Site Design: URL: http://www.epa.gov/statelocalclimate/documents/pdf/12_8_what_is_green_GGGC.pdf*

simple in the plan unless other dictated by site or functional requirements. Orientation cooperates with:

- Functional and social relationships within the building for example living areas and sleeping areas.
- Privacy between neighbors.
- Views.

- B. Optimize solar access suitable to the climatic region by design shading. The main strategy aims to keep the hot summer sun out and to let the sun in during winter

Figure 16: Solar paths during the year¹⁰⁹

- C. Shading could be achieved by building devices (roof overhangs, awnings) or/and by organized landscape planting. Shading cooperates with:
- Views
 - Orientation
 - Landscape design and surrounding vegetation
 - Ventilation
 - Privacy between neighbors
- D. Insulated Ceiling and walls to stop heat loss or gain between interior and exterior. In addition the regions where ground temperatures are very low, concrete floor slab edges should be insulated to stop heat loss.
- E. Design buildings which are open to breezes in the summer or whenever desired air is available. Appropriate ventilation must occur during the year to ensure a healthier and suitable indoor air quality.

¹⁰⁹ Source: *Solar Power Production on the Gold Coast*, URL: <http://gold-coast-solar-power-solutions.com.au/posts/solar-power-production-on-the-gold-coast/>

- F. Natural light goes hand in hand with heat. In careful design of shading the optimal balance between heat and light could be achieved for example the size and the placement of windows are considered in the passive solar design. Also skylight could be used to control and optimized natural light permeation into internal areas¹¹⁰.

4.1.1.2 Renewable Energy

Renewable energy can be obtained from natural sources such as the sun, wind and water flows. The initial information that should be known first is (the number of staff, visitors and guests- the usage pattern- What natural energy sources are suitable to the climatic region?)¹¹¹.

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

-In planning:

- A. Conduct an energy review during the design process to quantify the energy use during typical and highest occupancy periods. This can result in reduced energy infrastructure sizes and capital costs and identify ways by which energy or devices use can be minimized or evaded.
- B. Study use of renewable energy sources suitable to the climatic region like wind or photovoltaic.

4.1.1.3 Embodied Energy

Embodied energy is the total energy required for the extraction, processing, manufacture and delivery of building materials to the building site. In general the energy that is used in the running of a building is generally larger than savings in embodied energy by material selection.

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

-In planning:

- A. Selecting materials that are manufactured using renewable energy sources:
- Embodied energy comparisons should be balanced against:
 1. Material durability
 2. Local availability
 3. Longer term operational considerations
 4. The requirements of appropriate climatic design

¹¹⁰ *Fundamental Principles of Green Building and Sustainable Site Design: URL: http://www.epa.gov/statelocalclimate/documents/pdf/12_8_what_is_green_GGGC.pdf*

¹¹¹ *Renewable Energy: URL: <http://www.nrcan.gc.ca/energy/renewable-electricity/7295>*

- Reduce using highly processed materials because of the higher its embodied energy.
- Specifying standard sizes of materials.
- Avoiding waste¹¹².

4.1.1.4 Mechanical Appliances and Equipment

Energy efficient mechanical equipment and appliance should be selected which is very important where a development generates its own energy.

Heating water accounts for a major quantity of energy use, therefore this should be a priority area for decrease in energy use¹¹³.

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

-In planning:

- A. Reduce the energy consumed by cooling through:
 - Using air extraction ventilation systems where cool air is available. Depending on the climatic region ceiling fans or evaporative cooling could be used.
- B. Reduce the energy consumed in lighting through:
 - Good use of natural light alongside with using the least number of light fixtures possible.
 - Using solar powered lighting.
 - Using low wattage lamps.
 - Using reflective internal surfaces and light colors which rise efficient use of available lighting.
 - Using computer controlled lighting management systems that respond to room use and reduce artificial lighting to suit natural light levels.
- C. Reduce the energy consumed in heating water:
 - Isolate hot water pipes to minimize heat loss between equipment and heating system.
 - Using instantaneous gas or solar hot water systems
- D. Reduce the energy consumed by heating through using slow combustion wood burning stoves if the timber is plentiful or gas heaters. Making sure that timber is provided from a sustainable, renewable and reliable source.
- E. Reduce the energy consumed by white goods through using the most energy efficient white goods and devices possible for the number of occupiers¹¹⁴.

¹¹² Gillian, Menzies. *Embodied energy considerations for existing buildings*. 2011

¹¹³ *Saving Electricity*: URL: <http://energy.gov/public-services/homes/saving-electricity>

- In operation:

- A. Make sure that televisions, sound systems, computers and other equipment are not left in standby mode, because ‘Standby’ consumes almost as much energy as when the item is being used.

4.1.2 Systematization of Water Use

The objective here is to make sure that development is an efficient in the use of the water and has a sustainable water supply. The most preferable options are to reduce the use of water or to avoid the use of water if waterless options exist. When this cannot be achieved, study recycling of treated waste water. The least preferable option is to dispose of untreated waste water. The initial information that should be known first is (what water sources are available? Are there any hazards? What are the policy or legislative requirements? Is the taking of water prescribed in this area?)¹¹⁵

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

-In planning:

- A. Study the potential for re-use and treatment of waste water, which is greatly increasing energy requirements. The design solution need to take consider specific factors such as climate, soils, natural hydrology, vegetation and topography.
- B. Choose indigenous plant types during design landscaping procedure that are well adapted to local climatic conditions, so no need for irrigation will required.
- C. Investigate the suitability of waterless toilet systems (composting). Where their use is not practicable install water efficient dual flush systems¹¹⁶.

-In operation:

- A. Use accredited water efficient devices and water efficient equipment.
- B. Encourage staff and guests to decrease their consumption by providing educational information about the water efficient features¹¹⁷.

¹¹⁴ Australian tourism commission. *Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development*.2007

¹¹⁵ *Waterless Urinals and Flush Urinal*: URL: <http://www.sswm.info/content/waterless-urinals-and-flush-urinals>

¹¹⁶ North Carolina Department of Environment and Natural Resource. *Water Management Option*.2005

¹¹⁷ Zinderman,Carly. *Protect and Conserve Water Resources*. 2015

4.1.3 Diminish the Impacts of the Building's Element on the Land

The following elements and systems are needed to be understood and considered, when designing a tourism development in a natural landscape:

- Vegetation
- Soils
- Hydrology
- Topography
- Fauna and Bushfire management.

Figure 17: Elements in natural landscape (by the researcher)

4.1.3.1 Vegetation

Minimize negative impacts on site vegetation on parts of sites that built on and re-vegetation with local indigenous types (any plant species found growing at the site) on parts that disturbance has occurred.

The initial information that should be known first is (Is there any rare or endangered vegetation across the site? What are the types and species of vegetation across the site? Are there any weeds, introduced species or diseases?)

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes¹¹⁸:

-In planning:

¹¹⁸ Massachusetts Nonpoint Source Pollution Management. Preserving Natural Vegetation.2003

- A. Categorize and protect any areas of important vegetation or rare types.
- B. Design defined pathways to stop walking on and damaging the surrounding vegetation. The benefit of elevated boardwalks is that allowing light and moisture to pass through which encourages growth.
- C. Buildings should be designed and located to minimize the removal of mature trees.
- D. Aim to minimize or avoid fire breaks around buildings through using perimeter ground based, roof mounted sprinkler systems and suitable building construction details. In addition to found plantings near buildings that contribute to reducing fire
- E. When the design required a limited clearance of vegetation it should be a vegetation conservation initiative like replanting with locally indigenous types which ensure that overall result is a net biodiversity gain.
- F. Localize driveways or access points on cleared land to avoid unnecessary clearance¹¹⁹.

-In construction:

- A. Minimize the weed infestations:
 - Do not import organic /soil materials
 - Make sure that vehicles and tires are removed contaminants in a controlled area.
- B. A construction envelope can be defined to avoid accidental damage to vegetation outside.

-In operation:

- A. Consider sustainable low-impact productive plantings like permaculture. Preferably this should take place on degraded places and needs to be locally correct.
- B. The infestations of weed should be recognized and quickly managed.
- C. Re-vegetation should be undertaken where possible site, using seeds collected from the site and spread for this purpose¹²⁰.

¹¹⁹ *Massachusetts Nonpoint Source Pollution Management.Preserving Natural Vegetation.2003*

¹²⁰ *Australian tourism commission. Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development.2007*

4.1.3.2 Soils

Soils are connected to the original and underlying geology and geological processes. It is either of sedimentary or volcanic origin. It can be measured by their patterns, form, permeability to water, nutrient regime and layers. Development objective is to minimize impacts on topsoil as this can exhaust a landscape of its nutrients.

The initial information that should be known first is (What are the soil types and their distribution? Is there any existing soil contamination? What is the soil/substrata structure? Are there any broader locality issues)¹²¹

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

-In planning:

- A. Avoid or minimize the bulk excavations through responsible and suitable design
- B. Study elevating intensively used pathways
- C. Use permeable surfaces for paths and driveways

-In construction:

- A. Using local indigenous species to replant area that damaged by construction and excavation. To ensure that replanting is successful all areas replanted should be carefully monitored and managed.
- B. If erosion is required, make sure that any mechanical erosion control systems do not import nonindigenous or weed plant types.
- C. Minimize erosion problems by controlling site excavations or/and preventing the clearance of vegetation.
- D. All leaf litter and topsoil layers should be stockpiled carefully and reused in subsequent regeneration or landscaping works. Soil from lower layers should not be placed permanently over upper layers. Take care to fill in the opposite order to excavation¹²².

4.1.3.3 Hydrology

The study of water and its properties is called Hydrology, including both its movement through the land areas and its distribution in the land areas. All sites are located within a catchment and will have an altered or natural hydrology that includes storm water flows, groundwater and surface water. The hydrology of a site should be understood, because this will affect the design of a development. The development process should

¹²¹ Klara Brandl. *Environment Agency Austria. Sustainable Tourism & Nature Conservation. SURF-nature project. 2011*

¹²² Rogers, Chris, Dinesen. *Ways to Conserve Soil. 2015*

minimize changes to the hydrology in terms of quality, volume and distribution. The initial information that should be known first is (What are the policy requirements? What is the average rainfall? How sensitive is the site to changes in hydrology? Is there a risk of flooding? What are the surface and ground water flows?).

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

-In Planning:

- A. Install rainwater storage or tanks devices to control runoff from intensified flows from hard surface areas and from the roofs.
- B. Provide ways of remediating flows downstream, where natural flows will be interrupted, of any structure like storage systems or agricultural piping.
- C. Where buildings will be located near or in areas prone to flooding, elevated structures is required¹²³.

-In operation:

- A. Minimize or avoid nutrient input into the natural hydrology. Sources of nutrients include soil disturbance, waste systems and fertilizers.
- B. Reuse as much as possible the water captured on the site.
- C. Minimize or avoid the chemical contamination of the natural hydrology, which is including waste systems, cleaning products, vehicles and fertilizers.
- D. Petroleum products should be limited to sealed, contained areas¹²⁴.

4.1.3.4 Topography

Translated literally from its Greek roots of "topos" (place) and "graphein" (to write), topography means "the writing of place." As J. Hillis Miller notes (1995, p. 3), the term has come to refer to both the practice of accurate, scientific representation of particular places on the earth's surface and the actual configuration of those places.

This thesis considers the impact of the development on the natural landform; however, the visual impact of the development on the natural landform is not addressed as it represents a separate issue that might be studied in aesthetics. Any changes to topography will have an impact on vegetation, soils and hydrology because of the strong relation between these and the topography of an area, thus the development process must minimize changes to landform that caused by building on sensitive or

¹²³ Australian tourism commission. *Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development*.2007

¹²⁴ *Hydrologic and hydraulic design*: URL: <http://www.melbournewater.com.au/Planning-and-building/Standards-and-specifications/Design-general/Pages/Hydrologic-and-hydraulic-design.aspx>

steep areas¹²⁵. The initial information that should be known first is (How difficult is it to build there? Gain an understanding of the topography, a topographical study will identify the slope of the land and assist to locate valleys and ridges.). Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

-In planning:

- A. Building design options including:
- Part suspended mass option
 - Lightweight option
 - Lightweight around mass walls option.
- B. Design buildings to take a seat above sloping ground and minimize or avoid impacts on the natural landform by reducing the amount of cut and fill.

Figure 18: Building models for steep or sensitive sites

¹²⁵ *Environmental Impact Analysis: URL:*

http://www.lic.wisc.edu/shapingdane/facilitation/all_resources/impacts/analysis_environmental.htm

4.1.3.5 Fauna

Fauna include all the animal life normally present in a given habitat at a given time. Developing process aims to minimize site impacts on fauna and support the long-term recovery of any threatened species. However, interactions between guests and fauna need to be carefully managed.

The initial information that should be known first is (What are the policy requirements? What are the movement or corridors patterns of fauna across the site? What are the dominant species? Are there any endangered, rare or vulnerable types? Are there any potential or existing fauna hazards?)¹²⁶

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

-In planning:

- A. Consider re-establishing fauna habitat so endemic fauna in degraded areas could initiate repopulation.
- B. Make sure that the development does not happen in areas that may threaten, endanger, important nesting, breeding areas, and migration / movement patterns of fauna.
- C. Recognize and protect significant fauna habitat and threatened types.
- D. Use elevated path ways where possible to let small fauna types move without disturbed. If it is not possible the path ways should be designed to not boundary fauna movement.

In construction:

- A. Waste should be removed from site daily to prevent contamination of habitats.
- B. Specialist should relocate any threatened fauna that found in the building envelope.
- C. Control all areas for storage, parking, and movement of construction vehicles, material storage, and site sheds¹²⁷.

In operation:

- A. Carefully managed the interactions between visitor and fauna to prevent dependency on humans and minimize disruption.

¹²⁶ protect biodiversity and save endangered species: URL:
<http://www.endangeredspeciesinternational.org/overview4.html>

¹²⁷ Australian tourism commission. Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development.2007

- B. Provide opportunities for guests to actively participate in onsite programs.
- C. Eliminate or check for and manage any pest animal types.

4.1.3.6 Bushfire Protection

Identifying and managing the risks to property and life from bushfires and grass fires during building planning and development process. The impact of fire protection measures should be balanced and assessed against the potential impacts and level of risk on the environment as well as visitor experience.

From a tourism viewpoint, bushfire requirements (like clearance of vegetation around buildings) can be at odds with design responses aimed to minimizing impacts on vegetation and providing visitor experience. So the development procedure aims to protect the building and the occupiers from the danger of bushfire.

The initial information that should be known first is (What are the policy requirements? What is the bushfire risk classification of the site? How does the bush fire risk classification affect the design, construction and protection of the development?)¹²⁸.

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

In Planning:

- A. Study a variety of active fire protection actions. These actions can include:
 - Use the bushfire water tanks, fire hoses and a fuel driven pump for occupants' usage.
 - Putting perimeter ground-based and roof-mounted sprinkler systems with adequate water storage capacity
 - Install metal bushfire shutters over exterior wall glass areas.
- B. Study a variety of passive fire protection design and management processes like:
 - Design procedures to minimize embers and spark attack and build-up of litter in gutters that is against/around the buildings.
 - Fuel reduction.
 - Landscaping for fire protection.
 - Use high fire resistance materials in the building¹²⁹.
- C. Develop a suitable fire protection strategy for occupants based on the principles of leave early or stay and defend.

¹²⁸ *Building in a bush fire area: URL: <http://www.rfs.nsw.gov.au/resources/publications/building-in-a-bush-fire-area>*

¹²⁹ *How to Use Planning for Bush Fire Protection: URL: <http://www.rfs.nsw.gov.au/plan-and-prepare/building-in-a-bush-fire-area/planning-for-bush-fire-protection/how-to-use-planning-for-bush-fire-protection>*

- D. Designing should consider the accessible for fire vehicles and the accessible to available on-site water for firefighting.
- E. Design to comply with requirements of Building Code of countries.

A cooperative approach during the design process will generally assist resolving any conflicts. That means talking to the relevant authorities early in the design process and studying a variety of possible development responses to meet statutory requirements¹³⁰.

In operation:

- A. Assume a regular monitoring or/and maintenance program of fire protection procedures including:
 - Checking the sprinkler systems if they are operating
 - Recognizing possible risks and fuel hazards around the buildings and in close contiguous vegetation
 - Reducing vegetation canopy, before the start of the bushfire season flammable undergrowth should be slashed or mowed¹³¹.

4.1.4 Choice of Materials

Choosing Materials is a product of the design responses to the energy and land aspects. In addition the financial feasibility or cost analysis. Also choosing materials is affected by the long term payback period approach to material selection. Development process aims to minimize the environmental impacts of material consumption, processing or manufacture.

The initial information that should be known first is what local building materials are available?

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

In planning:

- A. Optimal use of each piece of material. Every piece of material has structural value it can provide shelter from rain, sun and wind in addition to the surfaces which can be combined into the finishes (color, textures, and pattern) of the buildings.
- B. Minimize the quantity of material through designing process. Design a close fit spaces to the number of people using them and their use¹³².

¹³⁰ *How to Use Planning for Bush Fire Protection: URL: <http://www.rfs.nsw.gov.au/plan-and-prepare/building-in-a-bush-fire-area/planning-for-bush-fire-protection/how-to-use-planning-for-bush-fire-protection>*

¹³¹ *Hon. Anthony Bernard KELLY. Planning for Bush Fire Protection. 2006*

¹³² *Australian tourism commission. Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development.2007*

- C. Use the standard building material size to design building that has simple geometrical grid which is allows off site prefabrication/ fabrication of building elements, reducing on-site construction time and minimizing site waste.
- D. Where available and suitable, re-use any existing building materials in good state.
- E. Use existing buildings on the site that are currently not in use where possible. This may need some extension, renovation and adaptation of the existing building.
- F. Use the natural and local materials in the site. This also contributes to the authenticity/sense of place¹³³.

-In construction:

- A. Design buildings for durability with low maintenance. Use dry techniques (membranes, metal flashings and good construction methods) instead of sealants to the greatest possible extent which is need thoughtful detailing of the building construction.
- B. Recycle, re-use or removed for replacement the material in the building by using certain construction systems. Lightweight structures could be able to be removed for re-use anywhere else. Consider bolted main fixings instead of nailed, glued or welded¹³⁴.

4.1.5 Waste management

Waste management should be considered in harmony with the waste management hierarchy. There are two main types of waste: organic and non-organic¹³⁵.

4.1.5.1 Organic Waste

Organic wastes include the scraps of sewage and food that are Susceptible to decay and other biological activity. Organic waste is often high in nutrients which are very difficult to remove in the course of treatment but can be easily recycled.

The development process aims to minimize organic waste impacts during construction and operation. The initial information that should be known first is (What are the policy requirements? What local waste management infrastructure exists?)

¹³³ Ashby, Michael. *Materials and the Environment: Eco-informed Material Choice*. 2012

¹³⁴ *Choosing Green Materials and Products: URL:*
<http://www.epa.gov/greenhomes/SmarterMaterialChoices.htm>

¹³⁵ Lettieri, Baeyens. *Waste Management: Recycling and recovery routes of plastic solid waste (PSW)*. 2009

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

In planning:

- A. Choose a sort of sewage treatment technologies like:
- Dry composting systems, which use very little water and produce a dry compost waste.
 - Very low flush composting system called hybrid.
 - A biological systems or mechanical system (digestion tanks, pumps and valves) that treats waste and produce a liquid waste that can be dried to a very small volume using evaporation.
- B. All organic waste products should be carefully dealt with in a manner that is in accordance with the fragility of the natural environment:
- Put the separated wastes from (kitchen, food scraps, and other composed material) into the organic waste cycle.
 - Wastewater may be distributed in areas of plantings that will use nutrients to avoid pollution of the ground water and soil with surplus nutrients. Alternatively it may need to remain isolated from the environment and removed, if possible to a food production area¹³⁶.
- C. Study alternative on-site wastewater systems like:
- Nutrient removal systems.
 - Composting toilets or other sewage treatment technology systems.
 - Grey water systems (laundry, bath, wastewater, shower, and kitchen).
 - Other wastewater systems using environmentally sound technologies.
 - Reed bed systems¹³⁷.

-In construction:

- A. All sewage waste should be stored and removed from site during construction.

-In operation:

- A. Give information of organic waste management system and clarify the environmental benefits to the guests on the operations.
- B. Minimize or avoid chemical pollutants (mineral oils, cleaning chemicals and pesticides) that enter the organic waste management system¹³⁵.

¹³⁶ Guerreroa, Lilliana. Maasa, Ger. Hoglandb, William . *Solid waste management challenges for cities in developing countries*. 2013

¹³⁷ Alexis, M. Troschinetz. James, R. Mihelcic. *Sustainable recycling of municipal solid waste in developing countries*. 2009

4.1.5.2 Non-organic Waste

Non-organic wastes are made up of a number of materials that vary greatly in their ability to be re-used or recycled. They should also be considered, as far as possible, as resources and parts of material cycles. The development process aims to minimize non-organic waste impacts during construction and operation. The initial information that should be known first is (What are the policy requirements? Work through the waste management hierarchy. What local waste management infrastructure exists?)¹³⁸.

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

In planning:

- A. Minimize building waste during construction:
 - A. Designing each piece of structure to have multiple uses.
 - B. Off-site prefabrication to minimize on site waste.
 - C. Re-use and recycling of building materials.
- B. Designing areas for storage and separation of non-organic waste (plastic, metal and glass)¹³⁹.

-In construction:

- A. Create a waste management system during construction as part of the Environmental Management Plan, that based on sorting of waste for other uses or for recycling. Removal of waste should be fixed to a strict schedule.

In operation:

- A. Maximize the use of recycled products.
- B. Non-organic wastes should be removed regularly after sorted into components for recycling.
- C. Select products that minimize the use of packaging.
- D. Awareness the guests about the waste management system and clarify the environmental benefits¹⁴⁰.

¹³⁸ Guerreroa, Lilliana. Maasa, Ger. Hoglandb, William . *Solid waste management challenges for cities in developing countries. 2013*

¹³⁹ Australian tourism commission. *Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development.2007*

¹⁴⁰ Alexis, M. Troschinetz. James, R. Mihelcic. *Sustainable recycling of municipal solid waste in developing countries. 2009*

4.1.6 Reduce the Impact of Transportation on the Environment

The development process aims to minimize the requirement for and impact of private vehicles on the environment. This can occur by reducing the number of private vehicle trips and reducing vehicle impacts on the site. The initial information that should be known first is (Is there a safe unobtrusive site where cars can be parked? Does the site have access to public transport? What are the likely transport needs of the target market?)¹⁴¹.

Here is a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes:

In planning:

- A. Decrease the area of car parking by using natural barriers such as vegetation to define or separate them.
- B. Design private vehicle parking in one location (if it is possible near the reception area) and provide alternative transport around the site, such as golf buggy, bicycle or pedestrian. This will minimize the requirement for wide paved vehicle access ways.
- C. Consider bicycle linkages with nearby attractions¹⁴².

In operation:

- A. Offer transport alternatives for guests not travelling by private or hire car, like shuttle service to nearest public transport facilities¹⁴⁰.

4.2 Guidelines for Achieving Sustainable Development of tourism projects.

The main objective of these guidelines is to build up the information that this thesis mentioned before and prepare it as a way to identify and manage the environmental actions for achieving the sustainable tourism development. The Design Guidelines are not intended to form a checklist, but rather to indicate appropriate ways a sustainable tourism development might respond to all developments.

4.2.1 Using the Guidelines

The Design Guidelines have been prepared on the assumption that the development is in a sensitive area and must, therefore, closely consider all issues. In reality not all issues will be relevant or a priority for all developments. The Design Guidelines have a consistent format that includes:

- Environmental Strategies

¹⁴¹ *Ways to Stop Pollution*: URL: <http://greenliving.lovetoknow.com/>

¹⁴² *Protecting the Environment*: URL: <http://www.epa.gov/epahome/trans.htm>

- Environmental Actions.
- Sub-fields: a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes.
- The optimum way to achieve the strategies

4.2.2 Proposed Guidelines for Managing Environmental Strategies of tourism projects

Table 2: Optimum actions for achieving environmental design strategies

(in the field of sustainable tourists' projects development)

Strategies		Actions		Sub-fields		Optimum	
I.	Energy Conservation	A	The Implementation of Passive Solar Design	1	Proper Orientation	-	Controlled the access of solar by simple fixed shading system.
						-	Orientation should interact with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Views. ▪ Privacy between neighbors. ▪ Functional and social relationships within the building.
				2	Optimize Solar Access to Be Suitable to the Climatic Region	-	The main strategy is to allow the sun in during winter and to keep the hot summer sun out.
				3	Utilize Shading Devices	-	Shading may be achieved through building devices (awnings, roof overhangs) and/or through controlled landscape planting.
				-	Shading interacts with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation. • Views. • Privacy between neighbors. • Landscape design and surrounding vegetation. • Ventilation. 		
				4	Control Heat Loss	-	Insulated Ceiling and walls to prevent heat gain or loss between interior and exterior.
						-	In regions where ground temperatures are very low, insulate the concrete floor slab edges to prevent heat loss.

				5	Appropriate Ventilation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design buildings to be opened to breezes in summer or whenever cool air is available and desired. - Sufficient ventilation must occur throughout the year to ensure suitable indoor air quality and a healthier and more comfortable building. - In regions where summer temperatures become very high, install ceiling fans or evaporative cooling to augment natural ventilation. (Evaporative cooling consumes substantial amounts of water).
				6	Utilize Natural Light	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The size and placement of windows for natural lighting must be integrated into the passive solar design. - Skylights can be used to optimize and control natural light penetration into internal areas. - Analysis can be done to determine an optimal balance between light and heat gain using careful design of shading.
		B	The Use of Renewable Energy Resources	1	Utilize Suitable Renewable Energy Sources According to Climatic Region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investigate use of renewable energy sources appropriate to the climatic region such as photovoltaic or wind
				2	Reduced Energy Infrastructure Sizes and Capital Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct an energy audit during the design process to quantify the energy use during typical and peak occupancy periods. This can identify ways by which energy or appliance use can be minimized or avoided and result in reduced energy infrastructure sizes and capital costs.

C	The Use of Low Embodied Energy Building Materials	1	The Use of Materials Manufactured by Using Renewable Energy Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Undertake embodied energy comparisons of building materials and balance these comparisons against: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material durability. • Local availability. • Longer term operational considerations. • The requirements of appropriate climatic design. This last item is notable because the energy used in the running of a building is generally larger than savings in embodied energy through material selection. - The Use of Specified standard sizes of materials. - Reduce using highly processed materials because of the higher its embodied energy. - Avoiding waste
	D	The Utilize of Energy Efficient Mechanical Equipment and Appliance	1	Reduce the energy consumed in cooling
2			Reduce the energy consumed in lighting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using the least number of light fixtures possible in conjunction with good use of natural light. - Using low wattage compact fluorescent lamps. - Using computer controlled lighting management systems that reduce artificial lighting to suit natural light levels and respond to room use. - Using reflective internal surfaces and/or light colors that increase efficient use of available lighting.

II.	Systemization of Water Use	A	The treatment and re use of waste water		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using solar powered lighting externally. 	
				3	Reduce the energy consumed in heating water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using solar or instantaneous gas hot water systems. For larger installations, consider a recirculating, instantaneous gas system as these can be very energy efficient and economical. - Insulating hot water pipes to minimize heat loss between heating system and fittings.
				4	Reduce the energy consumed by heating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using slow combustion wood burning stoves where timber is plentiful, or gas heaters (Ensure timber is provided from a reliable, renewable and sustainable source). - Design building that is well planned for the climate will require little heating.
				5	Reduce the energy consumed by white goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using the smallest, most energy efficient white goods and appliances possible for the number of occupants.
				6	Make sure that electrical devices are not in stand-by mode	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure that computers, sound systems, televisions and other appliances and equipment are not left in standby mode. 'Standby' consumes nearly as much energy as when the item is being used.
				1	Re-use waste water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investigate the potential for treatment and re-use of waste water. The design solution will need to take into account specific factors such as soils, topography, natural hydrology, climate and vegetation. (While it is feasible to treat and re-use waste water, this greatly increases energy requirements. It is better to avoid a problem rather than to have to find a technical solution).
				2	Choose indigenous plant types during landscape design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design landscaping and select indigenous plant species that are well adapted to local climatic conditions, thus removing the need for irrigation.

III. The Impacts of the Building's Element on the Land	B	Reduce the consumption of water	1	Use waterless toilet systems if suitable	- Investigate the suitability of waterless toilet systems (composting). Where their use is not practicable install water efficient dual flush systems.
			2	Use accredited water efficient devices and water efficient equipment	- Use water efficient fittings and accredited water efficient appliances. - Provide a sustainable water supply of sufficient quantity and quality. Where possible, harvest water from the site eg. Rainwater.
			C	Educate the importance	1
	A	Minimize Negative Impacts on Site Vegetation	1	Categorize and protect any areas of important vegetation	- Identify and protect any areas of significant vegetation or endangered species.
			2	Design defined pathways	- Create defined pathways to prevent guests from walking on and damaging the surrounding vegetation eg. Compacted gravel or boardwalks. - Elevated boardwalks that the guests can allow light and moisture to pass through which encourages growth.
			3	Minimize the removal of mature trees	- Buildings should be located and designed to minimize the removal of mature trees and interference with tree canopies.
4			Minimize or avoid fire breaks around buildings	- Using perimeter ground based and roof mounted sprinkler (water spray) systems and appropriate building construction. It is possible, after detailed analysis, to establish plantings near buildings that contribute to reducing fire spread.	
5			Apply vegetation conservation initiative to insure net biodiversity gain	- If limited clearance of vegetation is required, this should be offset by vegetation conservation initiatives, such as replanting with locally indigenous species, to ensure the overall result is a net biodiversity gain.	

					- Consider the purchase of carbon credits to contribute to revegetation in other regions.
			6	Localize driveways or access points on cleared land	- Locate driveways or access points on cleared land or along property boundaries to avoid unnecessary clearance.
			7	Minimize the weed infestations	- Weed infestations can be minimized or avoided by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • not importing soil/organic materials • Ensuring vehicles and types are decontaminated in a sealed, controlled area.
			8	Define construction envelope to avoid accidental damage to vegetation outside	- A construction envelope can be defined and physically sectioned off to prevent accidental damage to vegetation outside the envelope. Preferably this envelope should be in an already degraded part of the site
			9	Consider sustainable low-impact productive plantings	- Investigate sustainable low-impact productive plantings such as permaculture. Ideally this should occur on degraded places and needs to be locally appropriate.
			10	Recognize the infestations of weed	- Weed infestations should be identified and quickly managed.
			11	Re-vegetation should be undertaken where possible	- Where possible site revegetation should be undertaken using seeds collected from the site and propagated for this purpose.
		B		Minimize any Impacts on Topsoil	
			1	Avoid or minimize the bulk excavations	- By appropriate design responses.
			2	Study elevating intensively used pathways	- Using pathways, e.g. boardwalks.
			3	Use permeable surfaces for paths and driveways	- By using compacted gravel, stones, permeable paving.

				4	Replant area that had been damaged by construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Areas damaged by excavation and construction should be replanted using local indigenous species as soon as possible. - All areas replanted should be carefully managed and monitored to ensure replanting is successful. 		
				5	Mechanical erosion control systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where erosion control is required, ensure that any mechanical or pre-used erosion control systems do not import weed or nonindigenous plant species. 		
				6	Minimize erosion problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By limiting the clearance of vegetation and/or site excavations. 		
				7	Reuse leaf litter and topsoil layers in subsequent regeneration or landscaping works	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All leaf litter and topsoil layers should be stockpiled carefully and reused in subsequent regeneration or landscaping works. - Soil from lower layers should not be placed permanently over upper layers. - Take care to fill in the opposite order to excavation. 		
				C	Minimize Changes to the Hydrology in Terms of Quality, Volume and Distribution	1	Using rainwater storage or tanks devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Install rainwater tanks or other storage devices to control run-off from intensified flows from roofs and hard surface areas.
						2	Provide ways of remediating flows downstream	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where natural flows will be interrupted, provide ways of remediating flows downstream of any structure such as agricultural piping, soakage or storage systems
						3	Suitable structure design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Elevate structures where buildings will be located in or near areas prone to flooding.
						4	Control nutrient input into the natural hydrology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient input into the natural hydrology should be avoided or minimized. Sources of nutrients include fertilizers, soil disturbance and waste systems.

				5	Control the water captured on the site	- By Re-use as much of the water captured on the site as possible.
				6	Control the chemical contamination of the natural hydrology	- Chemical contamination of the natural hydrology should be avoided or minimized. Sources of chemical contamination include cleaning products, waste systems, vehicles and fertilizers.
				7	Control Petroleum products	- Petroleum products should be limited to sealed, contained areas.
		D	Minimize any Impacts on Topography	1	Use building design options	- Explore building design options including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lightweight option • Part suspended mass option • Lightweight around mass walls option.
				2	Design buildings to take a suitable seat	- Design buildings to sit above sloping ground and avoid or minimize impacts on the natural landform, eg by minimizing the extent of cut and fill.
		E	Minimize Site Impacts on Fauna	1	Consider fauna habitat	- In degraded areas consider re-establishing fauna habitat or movement corridors to initiate repopulation by endemic fauna.
				2	Choosing development areas	- Ensure development does not occur in areas that may endanger or threaten important nesting or breeding areas or movement/migration patterns of fauna.
				3	Recognize fauna habitat	- Identify and protect important fauna habitat and threatened species
				4	Use suitable path ways	- Where possible, pathways should be elevated to allow small fauna species to move undisturbed. Where this is not possible, pathways should be designed so that they do not limit fauna movement.
				5	Consider the waste in the site	- Removed the waste from site daily to prevent contamination of habitats.

			6	Consider threatened fauna	- Any threatened fauna found within the building envelope should be relocated by a specialist.		
			7	Consider all construction areas	- Design and controlled Areas for the movement/storage/parking of construction vehicles, site sheds and materials storage.		
			8	Consider the interactions between visitor and fauna	- Visitor interactions with fauna need to be carefully managed to minimize disturbance and prevent dependency on humans.		
			9	Provide opportunities for guests to actively participate in onsite programs	- By participating in biodiversity surveys, monitoring programs and habitat restoration.		
			10	Consider pest animal types	- Check for and manage or eliminate any pest animal species.		
		F		Minimize the Risk of Bushfires and Grass Fires	1	Use a variety of active fire protection actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Installation of perimeter ground-based and roof-mounted sprinkler (water spray) systems with adequate water storage capacity. - Installation of metal bushfire shutters over external wall glass areas. - Installation of bushfire water tanks, fire hoses and a fuel driven pump for occupants' use.
					2	Apply a variety of passive fire protection design and management processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design measures to minimize spark and embers attack and buildup of litter in gutters and against/around buildings. - Fuel reduction, eg thinning and/or removal of flammable undergrowth. - Landscaping for fire protection, eg selected plant species and mulches are less flammable than others. <p>This should only be carried out after detailed analysis of the local environment.</p>

IV.	Choice of Materials	A	Optimal Use of building Material		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of building materials with high fire. - Resistance, e.g. masonry. 	
				3	Develop a suitable fire protection strategy for occupants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Based on the principles of stay and defend or leave early.
				4	Study the location of the building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sitting and design should consider access for fire vehicles and access to available on-site water for firefighting.
				5	Consider the Code of countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design to comply with requirements of Building Code of countries.
				6	Assume a regular monitoring or/and maintenance program of fire protection procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Checking sprinkler systems are operating - Identifying possible risks and fuel hazards around the buildings and in surrounding contiguous vegetation - Thinning (reducing vegetation canopy), mowing or slashing flammable undergrowth before the start of the bushfire season.
				1	Optimal use of each piece of material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make the most use out of each piece of material. Every piece of material has structural value - It can provide shelter from sun, wind and rain and has surfaces that can be incorporated into the finishes (colour, pattern, textures) of the buildings. <p>For example, sheet materials for cladding can also provide structural bracing.</p>

			2	Minimize the quantity of material through designing process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design buildings on a simple geometrical grid based on standard building material sizes. <p>This approach allows off-site fabrication/ prefabrication of building components, minimizing site waste and reducing on-site construction time</p>
			3	Use the standard building material size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design buildings on a simple geometrical grid based on standard building material sizes. This approach allows off-site fabrication/ prefabrication of building components, minimizing site waste and reducing on-site
	B	Use of Recycled Materials	1	existing building materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where available and appropriate, re-use any existing building materials in good condition, e.g. aluminium and timber-framed windows, structural timber and steel components and corrugated steel sheeting.
			2	existing buildings on the site that	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where possible make use of existing buildings on the site that are currently not in use. This may require some adaptation, renovation and extension of the existing building.
	C	Use of Local Building Material	1	local materials in the site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use materials sourced locally to the site and where possible natural (stone, timber and rammed earth). This also contributes to the authenticity/sense of place.
			2	Design buildings for durability with low maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use 'dry' methods (metal flashings, membranes and good construction methods) in lieu of sealants to the greatest possible extent. This requires thoughtful detailing of the construction of buildings.
			3	Use certain construction systems for replacement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lightweight structures may be able to be removed for re-use elsewhere. - Consider bolted main fixings instead of nailed, glued or welded.

V.	Waste Management	A	Managing Organic Materials	1	Use sewage treatment technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dry composting systems, which use very little water and produce a dry compost waste that is effectively inert. - Flushing systems that biologically digest/ treat waste using either a mechanical system (pumps, valves, digestion tanks) or biological systems. These produce a liquid waste that can be dried to a very small volume using evaporation. - A 'hybrid' very low flush composting system.
				2	Organic waste products are treated in a manner that is in accordance with the fragility of the natural environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wastewater may be distributed in areas of plantings that will use nutrients to avoid contamination of the soil and ground water with excess nutrients. Alternatively it may need to remain isolated from the environment and removed, preferably to a food production area. - Separate kitchen wastes, food scraps and other compost materials from solid waste and put them into the organic waste cycle.
				3	Use on-site wastewater systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Composting toilets or other sewage treatment technology systems. - Grey water /sullage systems, e.g. laundry, bath, wastewater, shower, kitchen. - Reed bed systems. - Nutrient removal systems. - Other wastewater systems using environmentally sound technologies.
				4	Consider the waste in the site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During construction all sewage waste should be stored and removed from site.
				5	Give information of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Educate guests on the operations of the organic waste management

				organic waste management to the guests	system and explain the environmental benefits.
			6	Consider chemical pollutants	- Avoid or minimize chemical contaminants (such as cleaning chemicals, pesticides and mineral oils) that enter the organic waste management system.
		B Managing Non-Organic Materials	1	Minimize building waste during construction	- Off-site prefabrication (to minimize on site waste). - Minimize the number of different materials by designing each piece of material and structure to have multiple uses. - Design to suit material sizes (minimize off-cuts). - Re-use and recycling of building materials.
			2	Separating non-organic waste	- Designate areas for storage and separation of non-organic waste, e.g. plastic, metal and glass.
			3	Create a waste management system during construction	- This should be based on sorting/separation of waste for recycling or for other uses and should also allow for regular removal.
			4	Recycled products	- Maximize the use of recycled products that can be recycled, e.g. recycled paper, glass containers.
			5	Remove non-organic wastes	- Non-organic wastes should be sorted into components for recycling, e.g. plastic, metal and glass. - Designate areas for storage and remove waste regularly.
			6	minimize the use of packaging	- By selecting products that minimize the use of packaging.
			7	Awareness the guests about the waste management systems	- Educate guests on the operations of the waste management system and explain the environmental benefits.

VI.	Transportation	A	Decrease the Area of car Parking	1	Decrease the area of car parking	- By using natural barriers such as vegetation to define or segregate them.		
				2	parking location and alternative transport	- Provide private vehicle parking in one location (preferably near the reception area) and provide alternative transport around the site, e.g. pedestrian, bicycle or golf buggy. This will minimize the requirement for wide paved vehicle access ways.		
				B	Providing Environmental Transportation	1	Investigate bicycle linkages	- With nearby attractions. bicycle linkages
						2	transport alternatives	- Provide transport alternatives for guests not travelling by private or hire car, e.g. shuttle service to nearest public transport facilities.

Chapter Five

Tourism Sites Management in the Syrian Coastal Zone

5.1 The Syrian Coastline

The coastal zone of Syria is critical importance to country and a strategic access to the world. This importance includes national security, leisure use by national Arab and foreign tourists an increasing percentage of economic activities, and as main passageway for Syrian trade. The coastal zone therefore provides important economic, transport, residential and recreation all functions, all of which depend on its physical characteristics; appealing landscape, cultural heritage, natural resources and rich marine and terrestrial biodiversity. This resource base is thus the foundation for the well-being and economic viability of present and future generations of its residents¹⁴³.

Most Syrians, even including those in landlocked regions, relay on the resources of the coast either as a source of food and raw materials, or as a vital link for transport and trade, as well as the passageway for some neighboring countries that have no direct access to the Mediterranean.

The coastal zone in Syria considered as one of the scarce natural resources of the country, providing a narrow window to the sea for such a relatively large country. With 83 Kilometers of coast, Syria has the lowest ratios of coast to land area and coast to population of any Mediterranean state. However, this statistic disguises the importance of the coast to Syria in terms of economy and tourism and as a part of national heritage¹⁴⁴.

In addition, powerful economic pressures exist in the coastal region, and particularly in the narrow coastal zone. Among these economic pressure are Syria's tow commercial seaports, its tow oil terminals, its largest oil refinery, power plant and cement factory, the third largest airport, the first region for citrus, greenhouse vegetables and tobacco framing and processing, and the second region for olive farming and olive production, the heaviest concentration of steel bars and beverages production, and naturally, the major source of fresh marine food. These examples clearly underscore how central is coastal zone to economy of the country¹⁴⁵.

¹⁴³ *Mediterranean Environmental Technical Assistance Program. Integrated Coastal Zone Management — ICZM Syria.*

¹⁴⁴ *European Commision Study. Country Report: Syria. 2011*

¹⁴⁵ *UNEP/MAP-METAP SMAP III Project. Syria's Coastal Zone and its Desired Integrated Management, Proposed Vision and Policy. 2009*

Syria's coast hosts many archaeological sites and ancient ruins. Some are still poorly excavated, documented and protected. Among the most importance sites are the ruins and old cities of Latakia, Tartous, Ugarit (north of Latakia) and Amrit (south Tartous).

The coastal region, consisting of the 2 coastal governorates Latakia and Tartous, represents less than 2.5% of state area, but is home to 11% of the Syrians; the population density is the highest among all governorates except of Damascus. According to the State Planning Commission the population density reached in the governorate of Latakia 405 and Tartous 370 inhabitants/km², while in the narrow coastal plain the population density is almost 20 times greater than the national average, and 6 times greater than the rest of the coastal region, the hinterland. This population density, combined with its strategic and economic importance, places disproportionate pressures on the coastal zone. The current population in the 2 coastal administrative regions of Syria, Latakia and Tartous Governorates, is about 2 million, more than 4 times that of half a century ago. This rapid population growth, in an area mostly shaped by steep slopes, mountains and limited arable land, has led to high rates of rural- to urban migration and extensive urban sprawl over the coastal strip¹⁴⁶.

The combination of the attractive landscape, the favorable climate and transport infrastructure has led to the development of a number of summer resorts primarily used by Syria's inland urban population and other Arab visitors. In addition, archaeological sites attract European tourist groups. Increasing population, both resident and transient especially during the conflict in Syria, is leading to increased conflict between the competing uses in the coastal zone. Low impact uses are frequently being replaced by intensive uses that are more profitable in the short term but undermine the long term potential of the coast by reducing its resilience. Unfortunately, there is no sign that inappropriate uses of the coastal zone are becoming less frequent. In fact, with increasing population, visitors and economic activities, the pressures are increasing¹⁴⁷.

Satellite Image 3: Syrian Coastal cities

¹⁴⁶ UNEP/MAP-METAP SMAP III Project. *Syria's Coastal Zone and its Desired Integrated Management, Proposed Vision and Policy*. 2009

¹⁴⁷ European Commission Study. *Country Report: Syria*. 2011

5.2 Case Study

The practical studies in this chapter will examine the stated design guidelines for achieving sustainable tourism development throughout two case studies in the Syrian coastal zone. These case studies are Rotana Afamia Resort in Latakia and Porto Tartous Resort in Tartous. After examining both cases a comparative analysis and conclusion will be stated. This examination and assessment plan will be based on the guidelines that were conducted in the previous chapter.

5.2.1 Criteria of Selection

5.2.1.1 The criteria

1. Each of these projects is located in the major city of the Syrian coastal zone so that could help to represent the tourism projects in this city.
2. The location of these projects: on rocky shore -biologically rich environments- which featured in special kinds of fauna and flora.
3. Both of these resorts had built parts into the sea water.
4. The two projects are facing intensive use throughout the year especially after the Syrian conflict.
5. The developer of both resorts Rotana Afamia in Latakia and Porto Tartous in Tartous had announced that the projects are environmentally friendly and sustainable development.

5.2.1.2 Study Points

- 1- Site and Location Features
- 2- Architectural Features
- 3- Examining Environmental Design Strategies
 - Strategies in the field of energy conservation.
 - The Implementation of Passive Solar Design
 - The Use of Renewable Energy Resources
 - The Use of Low Embodied Energy Building Materials
 - The Utilize of Energy Efficient Mechanical Equipment and Appliance
 - Strategies in the field of water use systemization.
 - The Treatment and Re-use of Waste Water
 - Reduce the consumption of water
 - Educate the importance of saving water

- Strategies in the field of preserving the land.
 - Minimize Negative Impacts on Site Vegetation
 - Minimize any Impacts on Topsoil
 - Minimize Changes to the Hydrology in Terms of Quality, Volume and Distribution
 - Minimize any Impacts on Topography
 - Minimize Site Impacts on Fauna
 - Minimize the Risk of Bushfires and Grass Fires
- Strategies in the field of materials efficiency.
 - Optimal Use of building Material
 - Use of Recycled Materials
 - Use of Local Building Material
- Strategies in the field of waste management.
 - Managing Organic Materials
 - Managing Non-Organic Materials
- Strategies in the field of green transportation.
 - Decrease the Area of car Parking
 - Providing Environmental Transportation

This research examines raw data using many interpretations in order to find linkages between the research objective and the outcomes. Throughout the evaluation and analysis process using field notes and databases to categorize and reference data so that it is readily available for subsequent reinterpretation.

5.2.2 Rotana Afamia Resort

Rotana Afamia Resort is 5 km from the Latakia city center. This accommodation is located at the crossroad of the Near East, within easy distance of Syria's historical sites including Ugarit Canaanite, seaport, Crusaders forts and castles and ancient Roman vestiges.

The resort has view of the Mediterranean and it is established on fifty acres, including reclamation along with 15000 square meters of green zones. The Owners of the project are Afamia company (Urban Development Corporation) and the Council of the city of Latakia, which has 20% of the project¹⁴⁸. Rotana Afamia Resort was designed by Sameer Attaya architect in cooperation with Bin Laden Group¹⁴⁹. The duration of construction was extended over eight years started in 2002 CE and finished in 2009. The cost of the project is amounted 60 million Syrian pounds¹⁵⁰.

¹⁴⁸ Latakia, Syria: URL: <https://www.rotana.com/syria/latakia/39>

¹⁴⁹ Saudi Binladin Group is a multinational construction conglomerate and is headquartered in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

¹⁵⁰ Rotana Afamia: <http://www.wehda.alwehda.gov.sy/>

Satellite Image 4: Rotana Afamia Resort

Satellite Image 5: Rotana Afamia Resort

5.2.2.1 Architectural Features

The main building is curved shaped facing the sea shore. It is constructed principally of concrete and glass. The shore was reformed by grinding the rocks from the location into fine sediments.

Rotana Resort includes 245 rooms (double and single rooms), each of these rooms has private veranda with a sea view, and it also include villas (Three Bedrooms, Two Bedrooms and one bed room villas). The resort also includes on-site activities such as:

- Beach with 500 m length
- Health Club
- Health Spa/Massage
- Pool (Children's Pool, Outdoor Pool)
- Tennis (Outdoor Tennis)
- Gift Shops
- Baby sitting area
- Wedding hall (two wedding halls)
- Restaurants (five restaurants)
- Aquarius
- Yacht club

Figure 19: Rotana Resort Sea View Elevation

Figure 20: Terraforming and land reclamation during the construction of Rotana Resort

5.2.2.2 Examining Environmental Design Strategies

The aim of this part is to collect data regarding the proposed design guidelines. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the environmental actions that have been done in this resort the strategies that have considered in the study are:

- Strategies in the field of energy conservation.
- Strategies in the field of water use systemization.
- Strategies in the field of preserving the land.
- Strategies in the field of materials efficiency.
- Strategies in the field of waste management.
- Strategies in the field of green transportation.

A- In the field of Energy conservation

Table 3: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Rotana in the field of Energy Conservation

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Rotana Resort	Notes	
Energy Conservation	A	The Implementation of Passive Solar Design	1	Proper Orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Controlled the access of solar by simple fixed shading system. - Orientation should interact with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Views. • Privacy between neighbors. • Functional and social relationships 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The orientation of the building take into considers the relationship between the blocks to ensure that each room has the view and the privacy. <i>Figure21</i>
			2	Optimize Solar Access to Be Suitable to the Climatic Region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The main strategy is to allow the sun in during winter and to keep the hot summer sun out. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The building located, oriented and designed to maximize window area facing West-North which is access to sea view and cooling breezes. <i>Figure 22</i>
			3	Utilize Shading Devises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shading may be achieved through building devices (awnings, roof overhangs) and/or through controlled landscape planting. - Shading interacts with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation. • Views. • Privacy between neighbors. • Landscape design and surrounding vegetation. • Ventilation. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All rooms had been subjoined with a private veranda. <i>Figure 25</i> - These roofed platforms are protecting the interior space from direct sun waves in the summer. <i>Figure 25</i> - These verandas enhance the privacy between rooms and provide a social private area for entertainment and relaxation with a sea view <i>Figure 26</i> - All the verandas were placed behind a vegetation barrier to enhance the shading interacts - Rotana Afamia enclose a 500 square meter court which also natural ventilation, it also provide shaded interior spaces which are used for various social activities <i>Figure 23</i> - The design provides a broad porch

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Rotana Resort	Notes
						which shades both the entrance and the interior lobby from direct sun. . <i>Figure 25</i>
			4 Control Heat Loss	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Insulated Ceiling and walls - Insulate the concrete floor slab edges to prevent heat loss. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No isolation materials were used during construction
			5 Appropriate Ventilation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design buildings to be opened whenever cool air is available and desired. - Sufficient ventilation must occur throughout the year - In regions where summer temperatures become very high, install fans or evaporative cooling to augment natural ventilation. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The inside court provide a natural ventilation for the interior spaces especially during summer times. The 500 square meters court is also completely planted with local fauna which provide healthier air quality. <i>Figure 25</i> - Ceiling and standing fans along with evaporative cooling systems are also used during summer.
			6 Utilize Natural Light	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The size and placement of windows for natural lighting must be integrated into the passive solar design. - Skylights can be used to optimize and control natural light penetration into internal areas. - Analysis can be done to determine an optimal balance. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The interior court provides natural lighting for the lobby and other social area. - The roofed verandas allowed the designer to provide a board glass façade to each room which enhance the amount of natural lighting. <i>Figure 26</i>

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Rotana Resort	Notes	
	B	The Use of Renewable Energy Resources	1	Utilize Suitable Renewable Energy Sources According to Climatic Region	- Investigate use of renewable energy sources appropriate to the climatic region such as photovoltaic or wind	No	- According to climate analysis, both photovoltaic and wind power could be generated at the site. However, presently the building is not using any renewable energy source.
			2	Reduced Energy Infrastructure Sizes and Capital Costs	- Conduct an energy audit during the design process to quantify the energy use during typical and peak occupancy periods	No	- Energy auditing was not completed at any stage.
	C	The Use of Low Embodied Materials	1	The Use of Materials Manufactured by Using Renewable Energy Sources	- Undertake embodied energy comparisons of building materials - The requirements of appropriate climatic design. - Reduce using highly processed materials because of the higher its embodied energy.	No	- No embodied building materials were used
			D	The Utilize of Energy Efficient Mechanical Equipment and Appliance	1	Reduce the energy consumed in cooling	- Using ceiling fans or evaporative cooling depending on the climatic region. - In desert regions, air extraction ventilation systems may be used where cool air is available, eg night purging.
	2	Reduce the energy consumed in lighting	- Using the least number of light fixtures - Using low wattage lamps.		Partly	- Minimum light fixtures had been used in respond to the use of natural lighting.	

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Rotana Resort	Notes
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using reflective internal surfaces - Using solar powered lighting externally. 		
			3	<p>Reduce the energy consumed in heating water</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using solar or instantaneous gas hot water systems. For larger installations, consider a recirculating, instantaneous gas system as these can be very energy efficient and economical. - Insulating hot water pipes to minimize heat loss between heating system and fittings. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Even though the climate analysis indicates the possibility if using solar energy to heat water, this technology is not applied. - No gas hot water system is applied at the facility. - Electrical hot water system is used.
			4	<p>Reduce the energy consumed by heating</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using slow combustion wood burning stoves where timber is plentiful, or gas heaters (Ensure timber is provided from a reliable, renewable and sustainable source). - Design building that is well planned for the climate will require little heating. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The proper orientation of the building according to micro-climate studies had minimized the need for heating during winter season. <i>Figure 21</i>
			5	<p>Reduce the energy consumed by white goods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using the smallest, most energy efficient white goods and appliances possible for the number of occupants. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Domestic appliances had been chosen after careful consideration of energy consumption.
			6	<p>Make sure that electrical devices are not in stand-by mode</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure that computers, sound systems, televisions and other appliances and equipment are not left in standby mode. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All domestic appliances (except the mini-refrigerator) will automatically shut down after leaving the room.

Figure 21: The Orientation of Rotana Resort

Figure 22: Sea View, Rotana Resort

Figure 23: Interior Court, Rotana Resort

Figure 24: Roofed Platform, Rotana Resort

Figure 25: Abroad Shaded Porch

Figure 26: Natural Interior Lighting

B- Systemization of Water Use

Table 4: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Rotana Resort in the field of systemization the water use

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Rotana Resort	Notes	
Systemization of Water Use	A	The treatment and re use of waste water	1	Re-use waste water	- Investigate the potential for treatment and re-use of waste water. The design solution will need to take into account specific factors such as soils, topography, natural hydrology, climate and vegetation.	No	- No system was implemented to re-use waste water
			2	Choose indigenous plant types during landscape design	- Design landscaping and select indigenous plant species that are well adapted to local climatic conditions, thus removing the need for irrigation.	Applied	- All planted fauna are well adapted to local climate <i>Figure 27</i>
	B	Reduce the consumption of water	1	Use waterless toilet systems if suitable	- Investigate the suitability of waterless toilet systems (composting). Where their use is not practicable install water efficient dual flush systems.	No	- Composting toilet were not used
			2	Use accredited water efficient devices and water efficient equipment	- Use water efficient fittings and accredited water efficient appliances. - Provide a sustainable water supply of sufficient quantity and quality. Where possible, harvest water from the site e.g. Rainwater.	Partly	- Water efficient fittings were applied at all rooms <i>Figure 28</i>

	C Educate the importance of saving water	1 Encourage staff and guests to decrease their consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide educational information about water efficient features and encourage staff and guests to reduce their consumption. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Educational flyers about energy consumption are distributed regularly - Guidelines for saving energy are offered to the hotel guests.
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Figure 27: Plant Species

Figure 28: Water Efficient Fittings

C - The Impacts of the Building's Elements on the Land

Table 5: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Rotana Resort in the field minimizing the negative impacts on the land

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Rotana Resort	Notes	
The Impacts of the Building's Elements on the Land	A	Minimize Negative Impacts on Site Vegetation	1	Categorize and protect any areas of important vegetation	- Identify and protect any areas of significant vegetation or endangered species.	No	- No protection for any significant vegetation or endangered species.
			2	Design defined pathways	- Create defined pathways to prevent guests from walking on and damaging the surrounding vegetation - Elevated boardwalks that the guests can allow light and moisture to pass through which encourages growth.	Partly	- All pathways had been carefully design to prevent guests from walking on and damaging the surrounding vegetation <i>Figure 30</i>
			3	Minimize the removal of mature trees	- Buildings should be located and designed to minimize the removal of mature trees and interference with tree canopies.	Partly	- Palm tree had been re-located <i>Figure 30</i>
			4	Minimize or avoid fire breaks around buildings	- Using perimeter ground based and roof mounted sprinkler (water spray) systems and appropriate building construction. It is possible, after detailed analysis, to establish plantings near buildings that contribute to reducing fire spread.	Partly	- Specific kind of planting was founded around the building so it interrupts the spread of fire. <i>Figure 29</i>
			5	Apply vegetation conservation initiative to insure	- If limited clearance of vegetation is required, this should be offset by vegetation conservation initiatives, such as replanting		- During the construction phase there was clearance to twenty palm trees, these trees was removed carefully to

		net biodiversity gain	<p>with locally indigenous species, to ensure the overall result is a net biodiversity gain.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consider the purchase of carbon credits to contribute to re-vegetation in other regions. 	Applied	replanting them in different place as the design required. <i>Figure 30</i>
	6	Localize driveways or access points on cleared land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Locate driveways or access points on cleared land or along property boundaries to avoid unnecessary clearance. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Driveways were designed to avoid unnecessary clearance.
	7	Minimize the weed infestations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weed infestations can be minimized or avoided by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • not importing soil/organic materials • Ensuring vehicles and types are decontaminated in a sealed, controlled area. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weed infestation was not considered
	8	Define construction envelope to avoid accidental damage to vegetation outside	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A construction envelope can be defined and physically sectioned off to prevent accidental damage to vegetation outside the envelope. Preferably this envelope should be in an already degraded part of the site 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Construction envelope had been partly set during construction to avoid accidental damage
	9	Consider sustainable low-impact productive plantings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investigate sustainable low-impact productive plantings such as permaculture. Ideally this should occur on degraded places and needs to be locally appropriate. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sustainable low-impact productive plantings was not considered
	10	Recognize the infestations of weed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weed infestations should be identified and quickly managed. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When occur weed infestations was identified and quickly managed

		1	Re-vegetation should be undertaken where possible	- Where possible site re-vegetation should be undertaken using seeds collected from the site and propagated for this purpose.	Applied	- Site re-vegetation was partly done using seeds collected from the site <i>Figure 31</i>
B	Minimize any Impacts on Topsoil	1	Avoid or minimize the bulk excavations	- By appropriate design responses.	Partly	- Almost no excavations were done at the site
		2	Study elevating intensively used pathways	- Using pathways, e.g. boardwalks.	No	- All pathway are not elevated
		3	Use permeable surfaces for paths and driveways	- By using compacted gravel, stones, permeable paving.	Applied	- Permeable surfaces were used for paths and driveways
		4	Replant area that had been damaged by construction	- Areas damaged by excavation and construction should be replanted using local indigenous species as soon as possible. - All areas replanted should be carefully managed and monitored to ensure replanting is successful.	Applied	- All replanted area had been monitored <i>Figure 31</i>
		5	Mechanical erosion control systems	- Where erosion control is required, ensure that any mechanical or pre-used erosion control systems do not import weed or non-indigenous plant species.	No	- Imported weeds were not monitored
		6	Minimize erosion problems	- By limiting the clearance of vegetation and/or site excavations.	Partly	- Excavations were minimized

		7	Reuse leaf litter and topsoil layers in subsequent regeneration or landscaping works	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All leaf litter and topsoil layers should be stockpiled carefully and reused - Soil from lower layers should not be placed permanently over upper layers. - Take care to fill in the opposite order to excavation. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - topsoil layers were professionally maintained <i>Figure 29</i>
	Minimize Changes to the Hydrology	1	Using rainwater storage or tanks devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Install rainwater tanks or other storage devices to control run-off from intensified flows from roofs and hard surface areas. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No waste water system was implemented
		2	Provide ways of remediating flows downstream	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where natural flows will be interrupted, provide ways of remediating flows downstream of any structure such as agricultural piping, soakage or storage systems 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New pipes were installed to provide ways of remediating flows
		3	Suitable structure design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Elevate structures where buildings will be located in or near areas prone to flooding. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The structure was not elevated.
		4	Control nutrient input into the natural hydrology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient input into the natural hydrology should be avoided or minimized. Sources of nutrients include fertilizers, soil disturbance and waste systems. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The natural hydrology was vastly modified
		5	Control the water captured on the site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By Re-use as much of the water captured on the site as possible. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No waste water system was implemented
		6	Control the chemical contamination of the natural hydrology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chemical contamination of the natural hydrology should be avoided or minimized. Sources of chemical contamination include cleaning products, waste systems, vehicles and fertilizers. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The natural hydrology was vastly modified

	D	Minimize any Impacts on Topography	7	Control Petroleum products	- Petroleum products should be limited to sealed, contained areas.	Partly	- Petroleum products are sealed in certain locations on-site
			1	Use building design options	- Explore building design options including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lightweight option • Part suspended mass option • Lightweight around mass walls option. 	No	- No lightweight or suspended structures were used <i>Figure 32</i>
			2	Design buildings to take a suitable seat	- Design buildings to sit above sloping ground and avoid or minimize impacts on the natural landform, e.g. by minimizing the extent of cut and fill.	Partly	- The building is partly elevated 10cm above rocky stones
	E	Minimize Site Impacts on Fauna	1	Consider fauna habitat	- In degraded areas consider re-establishing fauna habitat or movement corridors to initiate repopulation by endemic fauna.	No	- No consideration to the fauna habitat.
			2	Choosing development areas	- Ensure development does not occur in areas that may endanger or threaten important nesting or breeding areas or movement/migration patterns of fauna.	No	- The development area was chosen depend on the design requirement without avoiding areas that may be in danger.
			3	Recognize fauna habitat	- Identify and protect important fauna habitat and threatened species	No	- There was not study for fauna habitat or the possibility of founding any threatened spices in this area.
			4	Use suitable path ways	- Where possible, intensively used pathways should be elevated to allow small fauna species to move undisturbed. Where this is not possible, pathways should be designed so that they do not significantly limit fauna movement.	No	- No elevated pathways were used. And there was not study for designing pathways that limit fauna movement.
			5	Consider the waste in the site	- Removed the waste from site daily to prevent contamination of habitats.	Applied	- The waste is collected every day and removed it from the site.

		6	Consider threatened fauna	- Any threatened fauna found within the building envelope should be relocated by a specialist.	No	- No consideration about any threatened fauna to study the possibility of relocated it.
		7	Consider all construction areas	- Design and controlled Areas for the movement/storage/parking of construction vehicles, site sheds and materials storage.	No	- There was no thinking about designing controlled areas in the site.
		8	Consider the interactions between visitor and fauna	- Visitor interactions with fauna need to be carefully managed to minimize disturbance and prevent dependency on humans.	No	- There is no Fauna that the tourists can interact with so there wasn't managing for this point.
		9	Provide opportunities for guests to actively participate in onsite programs	- By participating in biodiversity surveys, monitoring programs and habitat restoration.	No	- There wasn't any program that allows the guests to participate.
		10	Consider pest animal types	- Check for and manage or eliminate any pest animal species.	No	- There is no rules for pets animal .
F	Minimize the Risk of Bushfires and Grass Fires	1	Use a variety of active fire protection actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Installation of perimeter ground-based and roof-mounted sprinkler (water spray) systems with adequate water storage capacity. - Installation of metal bushfire shutters over external wall glass areas. - Installation of bushfire water tanks, fire hoses and a fuel driven pump. 	Partly	- The firefighting that used in the resort is the fire hoses and a fuel driven pump.
		2	Apply a variety of passive fire	- Design measures to minimize spark and embers attack and build-up of litter in		- The building used high fire protection materials. <i>Figure 34</i>

		protection design and management processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gutters and against/around buildings. - Fuel reduction, eg thinning and/or removal of flammable undergrowth. - Landscaping for fire protection, eg selected plant species and mulches are less flammable than others. This should only be carried out after detailed analysis of the local environment. - Use of building materials with high fire. - Resistance, eg masonry. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The planting was chosen to be at least flammable. <i>Figure 29</i> - The flammable undergrowth mowing regularly. - There was consideration in the resort to minimize the spark by using cigarette ashtrays that include sand, removing the waste every day from the building, and save the fuel in insulated tank. <i>Figure 33</i>
	3	Develop a suitable fire protection strategy for occupants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Based on the principles of stay and defend or leave early. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A suitable Evacuate the building plan for the staff and the guests was founded.
	4	Study the location of the building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Siting and design should consider access for fire vehicles and access to available on-site water for firefighting. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a private street for the fire vehicles so it can access easily to the site for firefighting.
	5	Consider the Code of countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design to comply with requirements of Building Code of countries. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All Syrian codes were considered during the design
	6	Assume a regular monitoring or/and maintenance program of fire protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Checking sprinkler systems - Identifying possible risks and fuel hazards around the 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a contract with a maintenance company which is comes monthly to the resort to check out if there is any damage to the equipment.

			procedures	- Thinning mowing or slashing flammable undergrowth before the start of the bushfire season.		- There is regularly mowing and slashing to the vegetation in the site.
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Figure 29: Vegetation Surrounding the Structure

Figure 30: The Re-locating of Palm Trees

Figure 31: Site Re-vegetation

Figure 32: Heavy Structure

Figure 33: Fire Protection Devices

Figure 34: Interior Materials, Rotana Resort

D - Choice of Materials

Table 6: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Rotana Resort in the field of choosing materials

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Rotana Resort	Notes	
Choice of Materials	A	Optimal Use of building Material	1	Optimal use of each piece of material	- Make the most use out of each piece of material. Every piece of material has structural value – it can provide shelter from sun, wind and rain and has surfaces that can be incorporated into the finishes (color, pattern, textures) of the buildings. For example, sheet materials for cladding can also provide structural bracing.	No	- Materials were not considered for optimal use
			2	Minimize the quantity of material through designing process	- Design buildings to minimize the amount of materials. Spaces should be a ‘close-fit’ to their use and the number of people using them.	No	- No consideration for minimizing the quantity of materials through the design process
			3	Use the standard building material size	- Design buildings on a simple geometrical grid based on standard building material sizes. This approach allows off-site fabrication/ prefabrication of building components, minimizing site waste and reducing on-site	Applied	- The building was designed based on simple geometrical grid <i>Figure 37</i>

		4	Use certain construction systems for replacement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lightweight structures may be able to be removed for re-use elsewhere. - Consider bolted main fixings instead of nailed, glued or welded. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No replacement systems were considered 		
	B		Use of Recycled Materials	1	existing building materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where available and appropriate, re-use any existing building materials in good condition, e.g. aluminum and timber-framed windows, structural timber and steel components and corrugated steel sheeting. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No re-use of any existing building materials was approved
				2	existing buildings on the site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where possible make use of existing buildings on the site that are currently not in use. This may require some adaptation, renovation and extension of the existing building. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No existing buildings are located on-site
	C		Use of Local Building Material	1	local materials in the site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use materials sourced locally to the site and where possible natural (stone, timber and rammed earth). This also contributes to the authenticity/sense of place. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local materials were used - Natural materials were also used when applicable <i>Figure 35</i>

		2	<p>Design buildings for durability with low maintenance</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use 'dry' methods (metal flashings, membranes and good construction methods) in lieu of sealants to the greatest possible extent. This requires thoughtful detailing of the construction of buildings. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Many materials were chosen based on their durability and maintenance plan <i>Figure 36</i>
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Figure 35: Natural Materials, Rotana Resort

Figure 36: Durability Materials

Figure 37: Geometrical Building Shape

E - Waste Management

Table 7: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Rotana Resort in the field of waste management

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Rotana Resort	Notes	
Waste Management	A	Managing Organic Materials	1	Use sewage treatment technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dry composting systems, which use very little water and produce a dry compost waste that is effectively inert. - Flushing systems that biologically digest/treat waste using either a mechanical system (pumps, valves, digestion tanks) or biological systems. These produce a liquid waste that can be dried to a very small volume using evaporation. - A 'hybrid' very low flushes composting system. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No sewage treatment technologies are used
			2	Organic waste products are treated in a manner that is in accordance with the fragility of the natural environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wastewater may be distributed in areas of plantings that will use nutrients to avoid contamination of the soil and ground water with excess nutrients. Alternatively it may need to remain isolated from the environment and removed, preferably to a food production area. - Separate kitchen wastes, food scraps and other compost materials from solid waste and put them into the organic waste cycle. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No wastewater systems are implemented - Organic wastes are not separated

		3	Use on-site wastewater systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Composting toilets or other sewage treatment technology systems. - Grey water /sullage systems - Reed bed systems. - Nutrient removal systems. - Other wastewater systems using 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No wastewater systems are implemented
		4	Consider the waste in the site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During construction all sewage waste should be stored and removed from site. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During construction all sewage waste was stored and removed regularly from site.
		5	Give information of organic waste management to the guests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Educate guests on the operations of the organic waste management system and explain the environmental benefits. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No flyers about organic waste management are distributed
		6	Consider chemical pollutants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avoid or minimize chemical contaminants (such as cleaning chemicals, pesticides and mineral oils) that enter the organic waste management system. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chemical contaminants are used
	B	Managing Non-Organic Materials	1	Minimize building waste during construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Off-site prefabrication (to minimize on site waste). - Minimize the number of different materials by designing each piece of material and structure to have multiple uses. - Design to suit material sizes (minimize off- 	Partly

			cuts).		
			- Re-use and recycling of building materials.		
		2	Separating non-organic waste	- Designate areas for storage and separation of non-organic waste, e.g. plastic, metal and glass.	No - No waste separation system is implemented
		3	Create a waste management system during construction	- This should be based on sorting/separation of waste for recycling or for other uses and should also allow for regular removal.	Partly - Non organic waste and organic waste are regularly removed from the site
		4	Recycled products	- Maximize the use of recycled products that can be recycled, e.g. recycled paper, glass containers.	No - Recycled materials were not considered
		5	Remove non-organic wastes	- Non-organic wastes should be sorted into components for recycling, e.g. plastic, metal and glass. - Designate areas for storage and remove waste regularly.	Partly - Non-organic waste was managed only during constructing
		6	minimize the use of packaging	- By selecting products that minimize the use of packaging.	No - No packaging preferences were considered
		7	Awareness the guests about the waste management systems	- Educate guests on the operations of the waste management system and explain the environmental benefits.	No - No flyers about waste management are distributed

E - Transportation

Table 8: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Rotana Resort in the field of green transportation

Transportation	A	Decrease the Area of car Parking	1	Decrease the area of car parking	- By using natural barriers such as vegetation to define or segregate them.	Applied	- Green materials and natural barriers are used in the parking construction <i>Figure 38</i>
			2	parking location and alternative transport	- Provide private vehicle parking in one location (preferably near the reception area) and provide alternative transport around the site, eg pedestrian, bicycle or golf buggy. This will minimize the requirement for wide paved vehicle access ways.	Partly	- Private vehicle parking is provided <i>Figure 40</i> - The parking is located near the entrance <i>Figure 38</i>
	B	Environmental Transporta	1	transport alternatives	- Provide transport alternatives for guests not travelling by private or hire car, e.g. shuttle service to nearest public transport facilities.	No	- No such transport alternatives were provided
			2	bicycle linkages	- Investigate bicycle linkages with nearby attractions.	No	- No bicycle system is used <i>Figure 39</i>

Figure 38: Parking Location

Figure 39: Car Linkage

Figure 40: Parking Area

5.2.3 Porto Tartous

Porto Tartous is located in the heart of the coastal town of Tartous where it spans over one and a half kilometers along its Mediterranean shoreline. The hotel is located near the center of country and an hour from the city of Latakia.

The majority of the site is land reclaimed from the Mediterranean Sea and work has been continued for many months in raising the level of the site to that required for protection from the sea. A sea defense wall is also constructed¹⁵¹.

The project was designed by JUNADA¹⁵². On the other hand, Wahoud Group, a company owned by Mohammad Ali Wahoud, a Syrian businessman, and a consortium of other companies signed in 2004 an agreement with the Municipality of Tartous to develop project off the coast of the city, which is estimated to cost up to USD 200 million.

Satellite Image 6: Porto Tartous Resort

5.2.3.1 Architectural Features

The project consists of architectural blocks constructed principally of concrete and glass. The northern section, which includes Porto Hotel and entertainment facilities, while the southern includes chalets in various grades in the midsection there, is a public park that is established in front of the waterfront.

¹⁵¹ *Porto Tartous: URL:*

<http://www.portoworldhotels.com/HotelInner.aspx?HID=13&HLID=170>

¹⁵² *Junada International is an Architectural and Project Management company who specialize in project development and project facilitation in UK and abroad, especially in the Middle East*

Porto Tartous Beach Resort & Spa offers 281 appointed rooms and suites including:

- 206 Standard Rooms
- 38 Patio Beach Rooms
- 31 Suites
- 6 Royal Suites

Each of these rooms has private veranda with a sea view or lagoon view, in addition villas (Three Bedrooms, Two Bedrooms and one bed room villas). The resort also includes on-site activities such as:

- A yacht club will be constructed adjacent to the marina.
- International spa complex
- Cinema complex
- Water sports
- Promenade
- International restaurants and cafés
- Porto Tartous five star Hotel
- Private beach
- Swimming pools

Figure 41: Porto Tartous

Satellite Image 7: The construction process of Porto Tartous

5.2.3.2 Examining Environmental Design Strategies

The aim of this part is to collect data regarding the proposed design guidelines. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the environmental actions that have been done in this resort the strategies that have considered in the study are:

- Strategies in the field of energy conservation.
- Strategies in the field of water use systemization.
- Strategies in the field of preserving the land.
- Strategies in the field of materials efficiency.
- Strategies in the field of waste management.
- Strategies in the field of green transportation.

A- In the field of Energy conservation

Table 9: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Porto Tartous in the field of Energy Conservation

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Porto Tartous	Notes	
Energy Conservation	A	The Implementation of Passive Solar Design	1	Proper Orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Controlled the access of solar by simple fixed shading system. - Orientation should interact with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Views. • Privacy between neighbors. • Functional and social relationships within the building. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The building was oriented to obtain optimum sea view <i>Figure 42</i> - The building was oriented according the preferable wind direction - The building was oriented according to local climate analysis
			2	Optimize Solar Access to Be Suitable to the Climatic Region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The main strategy is to allow the sun in during winter and to keep the hot summer sun out. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The building was designed by maximizing glass facades in proper directions <i>Figure 45</i>
			3	Utilize Shading Devises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shading may be achieved through building devices (awnings, roof overhangs) and/or through controlled landscape planting. - Shading interacts with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation. • Views. • Privacy between neighbors. • Landscape design and surrounding vegetation. • Ventilation. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All rooms had been subjoined with a private veranda. <i>Figure 43</i> - These roofed platforms are protecting the interior space from direct sun waves in the summer. <i>Figure 43</i> - These verandas enhance the privacy between rooms and provide a social private area for entertainment and relaxation with a sea view <i>Figure 43</i> - Shading panels built from local materials had been added to many verandas <i>Figure 46</i>

		4	Control Heat Loss	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Insulated Ceiling and walls to prevent heat gain or loss between interior and exterior. - In regions where ground temperatures are very low, insulate the concrete floor slab edges to prevent heat loss. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - isolation materials were used during construction, for example double glass facades
		5	Appropriate Ventilation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design buildings to be opened to breezes in summer or whenever cool air is available and desired. - Sufficient ventilation must occur throughout the year to ensure suitable indoor air quality and a healthier and more comfortable building. - In regions where summer temperatures become very high, install fans or evaporative cooling to augment natural ventilation. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The building is located so it could be naturally ventilated based on the local wind directions. <i>Figure 42</i>
		6	Utilize Natural Light	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The size and placement of windows for natural lighting must be integrated into the passive solar design. - Skylights can be used to optimize and control natural light penetration into internal areas. - Analysis can be done to determine an 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The roofed verandas allowed the designer to provide a board glass façade to each room which enhance the amount of natural lighting. <i>Figure 43</i>

				optimal balance between light and heat gain using careful design of shading.		
B	The Use of Renewable Energy Resources	1	Utilize Suitable Renewable Energy Sources According to Climatic Region	- Investigate use of renewable energy sources appropriate to the climatic region such as photovoltaic or wind	No	- According to climate analysis, both photovoltaic and wind power could be generated at the site. However, presently the building is not using any renewable energy source.
		2	Reduced Energy Infrastructure Sizes and Capital Costs	- Conduct an energy audit during the design process to quantify the energy use during typical and peak occupancy periods. This can identify ways by which energy or appliance use can be minimized or avoided and result in reduced energy infrastructure sizes and capital costs.	No	- Energy auditing was not completed at any stage.

	C	The Use of Low Embodied Energy Building Materials	1	<p>The Use of Materials Manufactured by Using Renewable Energy Sources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Undertake embodied energy comparisons of building materials and balance these comparisons against: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material durability. • Local availability. • Longer term operational considerations. • The requirements of appropriate climatic design. This last item is notable because the energy used in the running of a building is generally larger than savings in embodied energy through material selection. - The Use of Specified standard sizes of materials. - Reduce using highly processed materials because of the higher its embodied energy. - Avoiding waste. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A standard size of doors, windows and glass façade were used to avoid waste. . <i>Figure 46</i> - All local materials had been considered and used when fit to the design requirements. - Materials with high durability were used intensively. . <i>Figure 46</i>
			D	<p>The Utilize of Energy Efficient Mechanical Equipment and Appliance</p>		<p>1</p> <p>Reduce the energy consumed in cooling</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using ceiling fans or evaporative cooling depending on the climatic region. - In desert regions, air extraction ventilation systems may be used where cool air is available.
	2	<p>Reduce the energy consumed in lighting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using the least number of light fixtures possible in conjunction with good use of natural light. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minimum light fixtures had been used in respond to the use of natural lighting. . <i>Figure 42</i> 		

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using low wattage compact fluorescent lamps. - Using computer controlled lighting management systems that reduce artificial lighting to suit natural light levels and respond to room use. - Using reflective internal surfaces and/or light colors that increase efficient use of available lighting. - Using solar powered lighting externally. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reflective internal surfaces were designed to increase efficient use of available lighting. <i>Figure 45</i> 	
		3	Reduce the energy consumed in heating water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using solar or instantaneous gas hot water systems. For larger installations, consider a re-circulating, instantaneous gas system as these can be very energy efficient and economical. - Insulating hot water pipes to minimize heat loss between heating system and fittings. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Even though the climate analysis indicates the possibility if using solar energy to heat water, this technology is not applied. - No gas hot water system is applied at the facility. - Electrical hot water system is used.
		4	Reduce the energy consumed by heating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using slow combustion wood burning stoves where timber is plentiful, or gas heaters (Ensure timber is provided from a reliable, renewable and sustainable source). - Design building that is well planned for the climate will require little heating. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The proper orientation of the building according to micro-climate studies had minimized the need for heating during winter season. . <i>Figure 42</i>

		5	Reduce the energy consumed by white goods	- Using the smallest, most energy efficient white goods and appliances possible for the number of occupants.	Partly	- Domestic appliances had been chosen after careful consideration of energy consumption.
		6	Make sure that electrical devices are not in stand-by mode	- Ensure that computers, sound systems, televisions and other appliances and equipment are not left in standby mode. 'Standby' consumes nearly as much energy as when the item is being used.	Applied	- All domestic appliances (except the mini-refrigerator) will automatically shut down after leaving the room

Figure 42: Building Orientation, Porto Tartous

Figure 43: Private Verandas

Figure 44: Cooling Device

Figure 45: Natural Light Access

Figure 46: Shading Devices

B- In the field of Systemization the water use*Table 10: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Porto Tartous in the field of Systemization the water use*

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Porto Tartous	Notes	
Systemization of Water Use	A	The treatment and re use of waste Water	1	Re-use waste water	- Investigate the potential for treatment and re-use of waste water.	No	- No system was implemented to re-use waste water
			2	Choose indigenous plant types during landscape design	- Design landscaping and select indigenous plant species that are well adapted to local climatic conditions, thus removing the need for irrigation.	Applied	- All planted fauna are well adapted to local climate <i>Figure 47</i>
	B	Reduce the consumption of water	1	Use waterless toilet systems if suitable	- Investigate the suitability of waterless toilet systems (composting). Where their use is not practicable install water efficient dual flush systems.	No	- Composting toilet were not used
			2	Use accredited water efficient devices and water efficient equipment	- Use water efficient fittings and accredited water efficient appliances. - Provide a sustainable water supply of sufficient quantity and quality. Where possible, harvest water from the site e.g. Rainwater.	No	- No accredited water efficient devices and water efficient equipment were used

	C Educate the importance of saving water	1 Encourage staff and guests to decrease their consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide educational information about water efficient features and encourage staff and guests to reduce their consumption. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Educational flyers about energy consumption are distributed regularly - Guidelines for saving energy are offered to the hotel guests.
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Figure 47: Landscape Plant Types

C- In the field diminish the impact on the land

Table 11: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Porto Tartous in the field of decrease the impact on the land

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Porto Tartous	Notes	
The Impacts of the Building's Element on the Land	A	Minimize Negative Impacts on Site Vegetation	1	Categorize and protect any areas of important vegetation	- Identify and protect any areas of significant vegetation or endangered species.	No	- No study for any areas of significant vegetation or endangered species.
			2	Design defined pathways	- Create defined pathways to prevent guests from walking on and damaging the surrounding vegetation - Elevated boardwalks that the guests can allow light and moisture to pass through which encourages growth.	Applied	- All pathways had been carefully design to prevent guests from walking on and damaging the surrounding vegetation <i>Figure 49</i> - Many pathways had been elevated to encourage vegetation growth
			3	Minimize the removal of mature trees	- Buildings should be located and designed to minimize the removal of mature trees and interference with tree canopies.	No	- No consideration for removal of mature trees
			4	Minimize or avoid fire breaks around buildings	- Using perimeter ground based and roof mounted sprinkler (water spray) systems and appropriate building construction. It is possible, after detailed analysis, to establish plantings near buildings that contribute to reducing fire spread.	Applied	- Walls for separation purposes and green buffer zone were designed to reduce fire spread. <i>Figure 50</i> - Water sprinklers system was implemented.
			5	Apply vegetation conservation initiative to insure net biodiversity gain	- If limited clearance of vegetation is required, this should be offset by vegetation conservation initiatives, such as replanting with locally indigenous species, to ensure the overall result is a net biodiversity gain.	Partly	- Partly the location is reclaimed and terra formed

			- Consider the purchase of carbon credits to contribute to re-vegetation in other regions.			
		6	Localize driveways or access points on cleared land	- Locate driveways or access points on cleared land or along property boundaries to avoid unnecessary clearance.	Partly	- Partly the location is reclaimed and terra formed
		7	Minimize the weed infestations	- Weed infestations can be minimized or avoided by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Not importing soil/organic materials ▪ Ensuring vehicles and types are decontaminated in a sealed, controlled area. 	No	- Weed infestation was not considered
		8	Define construction envelope to avoid accidental damage to vegetation outside	- A construction envelope can be defined and physically sectioned off to prevent accidental damage to vegetation outside the envelope. Preferably this envelope should be in an already degraded part of the site	Partly	- Construction envelope had been partly set during construction to avoid accidental damage
		9	Consider sustainable low-impact productive plantings	- Investigate sustainable low-impact productive plantings such as permaculture. Ideally this should occur on degraded places and needs to be locally appropriate.	No	- sustainable low-impact productive plantings was not considered
		10	Recognize the infestations of weed	- Weed infestations should be identified and quickly managed.	Applied	- When occur weed infestations was identified and quickly managed
		11	Re-vegetation should be undertaken where possible	- Where possible site re-vegetation should be undertaken using seeds collected from the site and propagated for this purpose.	Partly	- Site re-vegetation was partly done using seeds collected from local areas

B	Minimize any Impacts on Topsoil	1	Avoid or minimize the bulk excavations	- By appropriate design responses.	Applied	- Almost no excavations were done at the site, the building is elevated above the ground <i>Figure 50</i>
		2	Study elevating intensively used pathways	- Using pathways, e.g. boardwalks.	Partly	- Various pathways had been elevated <i>Figure 48</i> - Elevated pathways had been mostly structured from wood <i>Figure 48</i>
		3	Use permeable surfaces for paths and driveways	- By using compacted gravel, stones, permeable paving.	Applied	- Permeable surfaces were used for paths and driveways <i>Figure 49</i>
		4	Replant area that had been damaged by construction	- Areas damaged by excavation and construction should be replanted using local indigenous species as soon as possible. - All areas replanted should be carefully managed and monitored to ensure replanting is successful.	Applied	- All replanted area had been monitored <i>Figure 51</i>
		5	Mechanical erosion control systems	- Where erosion control is required, ensure that any mechanical or pre-used erosion control systems do not import weed or non-indigenous plant species.	No	- Imported weeds were not monitored
		6	Minimize erosion problems	- By limiting the clearance of vegetation and/or site excavations.	Applied	- Excavations were minimized
		7	Reuse leaf litter and topsoil layers in	- All leaf litter and topsoil layers should be stockpiled carefully and reused in		- Partly the location is reclaimed and terra formed with no former topsoil

			subsequent regeneration or landscaping works	<p>subsequent regeneration or landscaping works.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soil from lower layers should not be placed permanently over upper layers. - Take care to fill in the opposite order to excavation. 	No	layer
C	Minimize Changes to the Hydrology	1	Using rainwater storage or tanks devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Install rainwater tanks or other storage devices to control run-off from intensified flows from roofs and hard surface areas. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No waste water system was implemented
		2	Provide ways of remediating flows downstream	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where natural flows will be interrupted, provide ways of remediating flows downstream of any structure such as agricultural piping, soakage or storage systems 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New pipes were installed to provide ways of remediating flows
		3	Suitable structure design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Elevate structures where buildings will be located in or near areas prone to flooding. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The structure was elevated to encounter sea waves and storms <i>Figure 50</i>
		4	Control nutrient input into the natural hydrology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient input into the natural hydrology should be avoided or minimized. Sources of nutrients include fertilizers, soil disturbance and waste systems. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The natural hydrology was vastly modified
		5	Control the water captured on the site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By Re-use as much of the water captured on the site as possible. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No waste water system was implemented

		6	Control the chemical contamination of the natural hydrology	- Chemical contamination of the natural hydrology should be avoided or minimized. Sources of chemical contamination include cleaning products, waste systems, vehicles and fertilizers.	No	- Chemical contamination of the natural hydrology was occur
		7	Control Petroleum products	- Petroleum products should be limited to sealed, contained areas.	Partly	- Petroleum products are sealed in certain locations on-site
		D				
	Minimize any Impacts on Topography	1	Use building design options	- Explore building design options including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lightweight option • Part suspended mass option • Lightweight around mass walls option. 	No	- No lightweight or suspended structures were used
		2	Design buildings to take a suitable seat	- Design buildings to sit above sloping ground and avoid or minimize impacts on the natural landform, e.g. by minimizing the extent of cut and fill.	Partly	- The building is partly elevated 4m
	Minimize Site Impacts on Fauna	1	Consider fauna habitat	- In degraded areas consider re-establishing fauna habitat or movement corridors to initiate repopulation by endemic fauna.	No	- No consideration to the fauna habitat.
		2	Choosing development areas	- Ensure development does not occur in areas that may endanger or threaten important nesting or breeding areas or movement/migration patterns of fauna.	No	- The development area was chosen depend on the design requirement without avoiding areas that may be in danger.
		3	Recognize fauna habitat	- Identify and protect important fauna habitat and threatened species	No	- There was not study for fauna habitat or the possibility of founding any threatened spices in this area.

		4	Use suitable path ways	- Where possible, intensively used pathways should be elevated to allow small fauna species to move undisturbed. Where this is not possible, pathways should be designed so that they do not significantly limit fauna movement.	Partly	- Elevated pathways were used. <i>Figure 48</i>
		5	Consider the waste in the site	- Removed the waste from site daily to prevent contamination of habitats.	Applied	- The waste is collected every day and removed from the site.
		6	Consider threatened fauna	- Any threatened fauna found within the building envelope should be relocated by a specialist.	No	- No consideration about any threatened fauna to study the possibility of relocated it.
		7	Consider all construction areas	- Design and controlled Areas for the movement/storage/parking of construction vehicles, site sheds and materials storage.	Partly	- Storage areas are controlled and supervised
		8	Consider the interactions between visitor and fauna	- Visitor interactions with fauna need to be carefully managed to minimize disturbance and prevent dependency on humans.	No	- There is no Fauna that the tourists can interact with so there is no management plan
		9	Provide opportunities for guests to actively participate in onsite programs	- By participating in biodiversity surveys, monitoring programs and habitat restoration.	No	- There is no programme that allows the guests to participate.
		10	Consider pest animal types	- Check for and manage or eliminate any pest animal species.	No	- There are no rules for pet animals.

F	Minimize the Risk of Bushfires and Grass Fires	1	Use a variety of active fire protection actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Installation of perimeter ground-based and roof-mounted sprinkler (water spray) systems with adequate water storage capacity. - Installation of metal bushfire shutters over external wall glass areas. - Installation of bushfire water tanks, fire hoses and a fuel driven pump for occupants' use. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The firefighting system that is used in the resort is water sprinkles system. - Fire hoses and a fuel driven pump are also used.
		2	Apply a variety of passive fire protection design and management processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design measures to minimize spark and embers attack and build-up of litter in gutters and against/around buildings. - Fuel reduction. - Landscaping for fire protection, e.g. selected plant species and mulches are less flammable than others. - Use of building materials with high fire. - Resistance, e.g. masonry. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The building used high fire protection materials. <i>Figure 50</i> - The planting was chosen to be at least flammable. <i>Figure 49</i>
		3	Develop a suitable fire protection strategy for occupants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Based on the principles of stay and defend or leave early. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A suitable evacuation plan for both the staff and the guests is used.
		4	Study the location of the building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Site should consider access for fire vehicles and access to available on-site water for firefighting. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a pathway for the fire vehicles so they can access easily to the site for firefighting.
		5	Consider the Code of countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design to comply with requirements of Building Code of countries. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All Syrian codes were considered during the design

		6	Assume a regular monitoring or/and maintenance program of fire protection procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Checking sprinkler systems are operating - Identifying possible risks and fuel hazards around the buildings and in surrounding contiguous vegetation - Thinning (reducing vegetation canopy), mowing or slashing flammable undergrowth before the start of the bushfire season. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a contract with a maintenance company which comes monthly to the resort to check out if there is any damage to the equipment
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Figure 48: Elevated Pathway, Porto Tartous

Figure 49: Green Buffer Zone around the Building

Figure 50: Elevated Structure

Figure 51: Re-planted Site

D- In the field of choosing the materials

Table 12: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Porto Tartous in the field of choosing the material

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Porto Tartous	Notes	
Choice of Materials	A	Optimal Use of building Material	1	Optimal use of each piece of material	- Make the most use out of each piece of material. Every piece of material has structural value – it can provide shelter from sun, wind and rain and has surfaces that can be incorporated into the finishes (colour, pattern, textures) of the buildings. For example, sheet materials for cladding can also provide structural bracing.	No	- Materials were not considered for optimal use

		2	Minimize the quantity of material through designing process	- Design buildings on a simple geometrical grid based on standard building material sizes. This approach allows off-site fabrication/ prefabrication of building components, minimizing site waste and reducing on-site construction time.	Applied	- All materials were minimized through the design process
		3	Use the standard building material size	- Design buildings on a simple geometrical grid based on standard building material sizes. This approach allows off-site fabrication/ prefabrication of building components, minimizing site waste and reducing on-site	Applied	- The building was designed based on simple geometrical grid <i>Figure 52</i>
		4	Use certain construction systems for replacement	- Use 'dry' methods (metal flashings, membranes and good construction methods) in lieu of sealants to the greatest possible extent. This requires thoughtful detailing of the construction of buildings.	No	- No replacement systems were considered
	B Use of Recycled Materials	1	existing building materials	- Where available and appropriate, re-use any existing building materials in good condition, e.g. aluminum and timber-framed windows, structural timber and steel components and corrugated steel sheeting.	No	- No re-use of any existing building materials was approved
		2	existing buildings on the site	- Where possible make use of existing buildings on the site that are currently not in use. This may require some adaptation, renovation and extension of the existing building. -	No	- No use of former existing buildings was recorded

C	Use of Local Building Material	1	local materials in the site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use materials sourced locally to the site and where possible natural (stone, timber and rammed earth). This also contributes to the authenticity/sense of place. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local materials were used <i>Figure 53</i> - Natural materials were also used when applicable (for example the shading devices) <i>Figure 54</i>
		2	Design buildings for durability with low maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use ‘dry’ methods (metal flashings, membranes and good construction methods) in lieu of sealants to the greatest possible extent. This requires thoughtful detailing of the construction of buildings. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Many materials were chosen based on their durability and maintenance plan <i>Figure 52</i>

Figure 52: Geometrical Design Morphology

Figure 53: Local Materials Use

Figure 54: Shading Devices

D- In the field of Waste management

Table 13: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Porto Tartous in the field of Waste management

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Porto Tartous	Notes
Waste Management	A	Managing Organic Materials	1 Use sewage treatment technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dry composting systems, which use very little water and produce a dry compost waste that is effectively inert. - Flushing systems that biologically digest/ treat waste using either a mechanical system (pumps, valves, digestion tanks) or 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No sewage treatment technologies are used

			<p>biological systems. These produce a liquid waste that can be dried to a very small volume using evaporation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A 'hybrid' very low flush composting system. 		
		2	<p>Organic waste products are treated in a manner that is in accordance with the fragility of the natural environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wastewater may be distributed in areas of plantings that will use nutrients to avoid contamination of the soil and ground water with excess nutrients. Alternatively it may need to remain isolated from the environment and removed, preferably to a food production area. - Separate kitchen wastes, food scraps and other compost materials from solid waste and put them into the organic waste cycle. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No wastewater systems are implemented - Organic wastes are not separated
		3	<p>Use on-site wastewater systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Composting toilets or other sewage treatment technology systems. - Grey water /sullage systems, e.g. laundry, bath, wastewater, shower, kitchen. - Reed bed systems. - Nutrient removal systems. - Other wastewater systems using environmentally sound technologies. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No wastewater systems are implemented

		4	Consider the waste in the site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During construction all sewage waste should be stored and removed from site. 	Applied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During construction all sewage waste was stored and removed regularly from site.
		5	Give information of organic waste management to the guests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Educate guests on the operations of the organic waste management system and explain the environmental benefits. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No flyers about organic waste management are distributed
		6	Consider chemical pollutants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avoid or minimize chemical contaminants (such as cleaning chemicals, pesticides and mineral oils) that enter the organic waste management system. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chemical contaminants are used
	B Managing Non-Organic Materials	1	Minimize building waste during construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Off-site prefabrication (to minimize on site waste). - Minimize the number of different materials by designing each piece of material and structure to have multiple uses. - Design to suit material sizes (minimize off-cuts). - Re-use and recycling of building materials. 	Partly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The design was modified to suit material sizes. - Materials were minimized to avoid waste
		2	Separating non-organic waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designate areas for storage and separation of non-organic waste, e.g. plastic, metal and glass. 	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No waste separation system is implemented

		3	Create a waste management system during construction	- This should be based on sorting/separation of waste for recycling or for other uses and should also allow for regular removal.	Partly	- Non organic waste and organic waste are regularly removed from the site
		4	Recycled products	- Maximize the use of recycled products that can be recycled, eg recycled paper, glass containers.	No	- Recycled materials were not considered
		5	Remove non-organic wastes	- Non-organic wastes should be sorted into components for recycling - Designate areas for storage and remove waste regularly.	Partly	- Non-organic waste was managed only during constructing
		6	minimize the use of packaging	- By selecting products that minimize the use of packaging.	No	- No packaging preferences were considered
		7	Awareness the guests about the waste management systems	- Educate guests on the operations of the waste management system and explain the environmental benefits.	No	- No flyers about waste management are distributed

D- In the field of Transportation

Table 14: Evaluate environmental design strategies in Porto Tartous in the field of green transportation

Strategies	N	Actions	Sub-fields	Optimum	Porto Tartous	Notes	
Transportation	A	Decrease the Area of car Parking	1	Decrease the area of car parking	- By using natural barriers such as vegetation to define or segregate them.	No	- Parking was not design according to green standards <i>Figure</i>
			2	parking location	- Provide private vehicle parking in one location (preferably near the reception area) and provide alternative transport around the	Partly	- Private vehicle parking is provided (constructed from green materials)

				site, e.g. pedestrian, bicycle or golf buggy. This will minimize the requirement for wide paved vehicle access ways.			
	B	Environmental Transportation	1	transport alternatives	- Provide transport alternatives for guests not travelling by private or hire car, e.g. shuttle service to nearest public transport facilities.	Applied	- Electric-cars are provided for guests inside the resort <i>Figure 55</i>
			2	cycle linkages	- Investigate bicycle linkages with nearby attractions.	No	- No bicycle system is used

Figure 55: Alternative Transportation Vehicles

5.2.4 Comparatives Analysis

In the field of energy conservation both edifices had implanted passive solar design actions. This concept was achieved by proper orientation regarding various factors: minimizing direct solar waves during summer, proper ventilation by orienting the buildings towards preferable wind directions, utilizing shading devices and maximizing natural lighting. Rotana resort had promoted the passive solar design by adding 500 square meter court which had increased the amount of natural light and provide healthier air quality by planting all the court with local fauna. However, both buildings did not use any Insulated Ceiling or walls to prevent heat gain or loss between interior and exterior. Regarding the use of renewable energy use, both buildings did not use such technologies. However, it important the state that architects of Porto Tartous had designed a solar electric system, the idea was abandoned during the construction.

Regarding the materials both buildings had been designed with a standard size of doors, windows and glass façade were used to avoid waste. Local materials had been considered when fit to design requirements. And finally, materials with high durability were used intensively. Furthermore, both buildings were structured with no regards to materials manufactured by using renewable energy sources.

Regarding utilize of energy efficient mechanical equipment and appliance both building had utilized evaporative cooling systems and most energy efficient white goods, however, no solar or instantaneous gas hot water systems was applied in both buildings.

In the field of water-use systemization both buildings do not use any re-use waste water systems, in addition, both building do not use waterless toilet systems. However, in both resorts all planted fauna are well adapted to local climate, and water efficient fittings are applied at all rooms.

Regarding the impacts of the building's elements on the land both buildings had carefully designed pathways to prevent guests from walking on and damaging the surrounding vegetation. However, Porto Tartous had also implemented elevated pathways elevated to allow small fauna species to move undisturbed. Both building did not record any existence of significant vegetation prior to the construction. However, in Rotana Resort architects had decided to replant all the palm trees that had been removed though to construction activates.

In the field of materials use both building had been designed with geometrical morphology based on grid design system. Both buildings had partly used local materials. However, both buildings didn't consider the use of recycle materials and did not consider any replacement system for future maintenance

In the field of waste management, organic and non-organic materials are regularly removed from both sites. However, waste are not separated, treated or recycled in anyway. Flyers about waste management were never distributed.

In the field of green transportation systems, electric cars are offered for guests within the site of Porto Tartous. Parking lots are also offered for private cars. However the parking area was not decreased in both cases

-The aim of this part is to compare between these two examples in order to know which Resort is closer to the sustainable development of tourism projects depending on the previous proposed guideline that was concluded before.

The analysis has a consistent format that includes:

- First column: Environmental Strategies
- Second column: Environmental Actions.
- Third column: Sub-fields: a range of possible actions that will help to ensure sustainable outcomes.
- Fourth column: Will show if these actions had applied or not or partly applied in Rotana resort using red background for not applied, yellow background for partly applied and green background for applied.
- Fifth column: Will show if these actions had applied or not or partly applied in Porto Tartous using red background for not applied, yellow background for partly applied and green background for applied.

Key:

Applied

Partly Applied

Not Applied

Table 15: Comparative Analysis

Strategy	Actions		Sub-fields		Rotana	Porto
Energy Conservation	A	The Implementation of Passive Solar Design	1	Proper Orientation	Applied	Applied
			2	Optimize Solar Access	Applied	Applied
			3	Utilize Shading Devices	Applied	Applied
			4	Control Heat Loss	Not Applied	Partly Applied
			5	Appropriate Ventilation	Applied	Partly Applied
			6	Utilize Natural Light	Applied	Partly Applied
	B	The Use of Renewable	1	Utilize Suitable Renewable Energy	Not Applied	Not Applied

		Energy Resources	2	Reduced Energy		
	C	Low Embodied Energy Materials	1	The Use Materials Manufactured by Renewable Energy Sources		
	D	The Utilize of Energy Efficient Mechanical Equipment and Appliance	1	Reduce the energy consumed in cooling		
			2	Reduce the energy consumed in lighting		
			3	Reduce the energy consumed in heating water		
			4	Reduce the energy consumed by heating		
			5	Reduce the energy consumed by white goods		
6	Make sure that electrical devices are not in stand-by mode					
Systemization of Water Use	A	The treatment and re use of waste water	1	Re-use waste water		
			2	Choose indigenous plant types during landscape design		
	B	Reduce the consumption of water	1	Use waterless toilet systems if suitable		
			2	Use efficient equipment		
	C	Educate the importance of saving water	1	Encourage staff and guests to decrease their consumption		
	The Impacts of the Building's Element on the Land	A	Minimize Negative Impacts on Site Vegetation	1	Categorize and protect any areas of important vegetation	
2				Design defined pathways		
3				Minimize the removal of mature trees		
4				Minimize or avoid fire breaks around buildings		
5				Apply vegetation conservation initiative		

			6	Localize driveways or access points on cleared land		
			7	Minimize the weed infestations		
			8	Define construction envelope to avoid accidental damage		
			9	Consider sustainable low-impact productive plantings		
			10	Recognize the infestations of weed		
			11	Re-vegetation should be undertaken where possible		
	B	Minimize any Impacts on Topsoil	1	Avoid or minimize the bulk excavations		
			2	Study elevating intensively used pathways		
			3	Use permeable surfaces for paths and driveways		
			4	Replant area that had been damaged by construction		
			5	Mechanical erosion control systems		
			6	Minimize erosion problems		
			7	Reuse leaf litter and topsoil layers in subsequent		
	C	Minimize Changes to the Hydrology in Terms of Quality, Volume and Distribution	1	Using rainwater storage or tanks devices		
			2	Provide ways of remediating flows downstream		
			3	Suitable structure design		
			4	Control nutrient input into the natural hydrology		
			5	Control the water captured on the site		

		6	Control the chemical contamination		
		7	Control Petroleum products		
	D	Minimize any Impacts on Topography	1	Use building design options	
			2	Design buildings to take a suitable seat	
	E	Minimize Site Impacts on Fauna	1	Consider fauna habitat	
			2	Choosing development areas	
			3	Recognize fauna habitat	
			4	Use suitable path ways	
			5	Consider the waste in the site	
			6	Consider threatened fauna	
			7	Consider all construction areas	
			8	Consider the interactions between visitor and fauna	
			9	Provide opportunities for guests	
			10	Consider pest animal types	
	F	Minimize the Risk of Bushfires and Grass Fires	1	Use a variety of active fire protection actions	
			2	Apply a variety of passive fire	
			3	Develop a suitable fire protection strategy for occupants	
			4	Study the location of the building	

			5	Consider the Code of countries	Green	Green
			6	Assume a regular monitoring or/and maintenance program	Green	Green
Choice of Materials	A	Optimal Use of building Material	1	Optimal use of each piece of material	Red	Red
			2	Minimize the quantity of material through designing process	Green	Green
			3	Use the standard building material size	Green	Green
	B	Use of Recycled Materials	1	existing building materials	Red	Red
			2	existing buildings on the site that	Red	Red
	C	Use of Local Building Material	1	local materials in the site	Green	Green
			2	Design buildings for durability with low maintenance	Yellow	Yellow
			3	Use certain construction systems for replacement	Red	Red
	Waste Management	A	Managing Organic Materials	1	Use sewage treatment technologies	Red
2				Organic waste products are treated	Red	Red
3				Use on-site wastewater systems	Red	Red
4				Consider the waste in the site	Green	Green
5				Give information of organic waste management to the guests	Red	Red
6				Consider chemical pollutants	Red	Red
B		Managing Non-Organic Materials	1	Minimize building waste during construction	Yellow	Yellow
			2	Separating non-organic waste	Red	Red

			3	Create a waste management system during construction	Yellow	Yellow			
			4	Recycled products	Yellow	Yellow			
			5	Remove non-organic wastes	Yellow	Yellow			
			6	minimize the use of packaging	Red	Red			
			7	Awareness the guests about the waste management systems	Red	Red			
			Transportation	A	Decrease the Area of car Parking	1	Decrease the area of car parking	Green	Red
						2	parking location and alternative transport	Green	Red
B	Providing Environmental Transportation	1		Investigate bicycle linkages	Red	Green			
		2		transport alternatives	Red	Red			

5.2.5 Conclusion

Some of the results emerging from the previous cases clearly place the tourism projects in the coastal zone at a vantage position to drive the national plans for sustainable coastal tourism in Syria. If the coastal projects' investment sustained in the long run, it will result an improvement in ecosystems and biodiversity.

It is clear from these studies that there are some issues which weren't took in consideration during the development process such as:

- Minimizing consumption of energy from nonrenewable resources (Promoting a "reduce, reuse, recycle" mentality).
- Using low Embodied energy building materials
- Re- use waste water.
- Using Recycled materials.
- Separating organic and non-organic waste.
- Use on-site wastewater treatment systems
- Use sewage treatment technologies
- Using Bicycle linkages with nearby attractions.
- Minimizing the physical impact of the construction and operation of tourism facilities.
- Promoting the development and management of ecotourism.

There are some issues which partly took in consideration during the development process such as:

- Using utilize of energy efficient mechanical equipment and appliance.
- Reduce consumption of water.
- Minimize sit impact on fauna.
- Minimizing the negative impact of the building elements on topography.
- Minimizing changes to hydrology.
- Using local materials.
- Promoting the use of more sustainable transportation systems within the site parameters.

There are some issues which took in consideration during the development process such as:

- The implementation of passive solar design.
- Minimizing the negative impact of the building elements on vegetation.
- Design landscaping that is well adapted to the local climate.
- Minimizing the risk of bushfires and grass fires.

All decision makers who are encouraged to be actively involved in the development of an environmentally responsible tourism should ensure that the development process in the Syrian coastal zone will make an optimal use of environmental resources that constitute a key element in tourism development, maintaining essential ecological processes and helping to conserve natural heritage and biodiversity.

5.3 Questionnaire

This research conducted a questionnaire in order to study the preferences sub-actions that both designers and developers show towards each environmental element regarding to the proposed design guidelines.

This questionnaire obligates both designers and developers to order their preferences sub-actions from the most important in their own point of view towards the least important in each of the six basic elements in environmental design: energy, water, land, waste, materials and transport.

The questionnaire was distributed among two groups as the following:

- A. First group include 50 Syrian architects in which they obtain more than 5 years' experience in the field of architectural design
- B. Second group include 50 Syrian real estate developers and owners in which they are currently investing in tourism developing projects

The distributed questionnaire was a closed format questions, respondents were restricted to choose among any of the given multiple choices. And they were also required to rate these answers in each field as this was a Rating Scale Questions.

The questionnaire contained 6 questions. These questions were presented as the following:

1. In the field of energy conservation and in order to achieve sustainable tourism development, please rate the following four actions according to your preferences: (1 would be the most important)
 - the implementation of passive solar design
 - the use of renewable energy resources
 - the use of low embodied energy building materials
 - the utilize of energy efficient mechanical equipment and appliance
2. In the field of water use systemization and in order to achieve sustainable tourism development, please rate the following three actions according to your preferences: (1 would be the most important)
 - The Treatment and Re-use of Waste Water
 - Reduce the consumption of water
 - Educate the importance of saving water
3. In the field of preserving the land and in order to achieve sustainable tourism development, please rate the following six actions according to your preferences: (1 would be the most important)
 - minimize negative impacts on site vegetation
 - minimize any impacts on topsoil
 - minimize changes to the hydrology in terms of quality, volume and distribution
 - minimize any impacts on topography
 - minimize site impacts on fauna
 - minimize the risk of bushfires and grass fires
4. In the field of materials efficiency and in order to achieve sustainable tourism development, please rate the following actions according to your preferences: (1 would be the most important)
 - Optimal Use of building Material
 - Use of Recycled Materials
 - Use of Local Building Material
5. In the field of waste management and in order to achieve sustainable tourism development, please rate the following actions according to your preferences: (1 would be the most important)
 - managing organic waste materials
 - managing non-organic waste materials

6. In the field of green transportation and in order to achieve sustainable tourism development, please rate the following actions according to your preferences: (1 would be the most important)
- Decrease the Area of car Parking
 - Providing Environmental Transportation.

This questionnaire was distributed as one page A4 format, the questionnaire was sent by email as PDF format for all respondents. The following table demonstrates the questionnaire in the way in which it was sent.

Table 16: Questionnaire Form

Questionnaire				
Researcher: Khoulood Ali			Cairo University, 2015-2016	
<p><i>Thesis: Managing Environmental Design Strategies towards Sustainable Tourism Development in the Syrian Coastal Zone</i></p> <p><i>In each Category, please rate the following actions in the sub-field column regarding your preferences (1 would be the most important)</i></p>				
N.	Field	N.	Sub-Field	Order
I	Energy Conservation	A	The Implementation of Passive Solar Design	
		B	The Use of Renewable Energy Resources	
		C	The Use of Low Embodied Energy Building Materials	
		D	The Utilize of Energy Efficient Mechanical Equipment and Appliance	
II	Systemization of Water Use	A	The Treatment and Re-use of Waste Water	
		B	Reduce the consumption of water	
		C	Educate the importance of saving water	
III	The Impacts of the Building's Element on the Land	A	Minimize Negative Impacts on Site Vegetation	
		B	Minimize any Impacts on Topsoil	
		C	Minimize Changes to the Hydrology in Terms of Quality, Volume and Distribution	
		D	Minimize any Impacts on Topography	
		E	Minimize Site Impacts on Fauna	
		F	Minimize the Risk of Bushfires and Grass Fires	
IV	Materials	A	Optimal Use of building Material	
		B	Use of Recycled Materials	
		C	Use of Local Building Material	

V	Waste Management	A	Managing Organic Materials	
		B	Managing Non-Organic Materials	
VI	Transport	A	Decrease the Area of car Parking	
		B	Providing Environmental Transportation	

5.3.1 Analysis

out of 50, 27 architects considered the implementation of passive solar design is the most important action, 11 considered the use of low embodied energy building materials, 9 considered the use of renewable energy resources and only 3 considered the utilize of energy efficient mechanical equipment and appliance to be the most important action. However, 23 developers considered the implementation of passive solar design is the most important action, 15 considered the use of low embodied energy building materials, 10 considered the use of renewable energy resources and only 2 considered the utilize of energy efficient mechanical equipment and appliance to be the most important action.

Figure 56: Questionnaire's results analysis in the field of energy conservation

In the field of water use systemization, 23 architects considered the utilize of accredited water efficient devices and water efficient equipment is the most important action in this field, 22 considered the treatment and re-use of waste water, and only 5 considered the possibility of waterless toilet systems use to be the most important action.

However, 32 developers considered the utilize of accredited water efficient devices and water efficient equipment is the most important action in this field, 17 considered reducing the consumption of water, and only one considered educate the impotence of saving water

Figure 57: Questionnaire's results analysis in the field of water use systemization

In the field of land persevering and minimizing the impacts of the building's element on the land, 10 architects considered minimizing the impacts on topography is the most important action in this field, 9 considered minimizing negative impacts on site vegetation, 9 considered minimizing any impacts on topsoil, 8 considered minimizing changes to the hydrology in terms of quality, volume and distribution, and 7 considered minimizing the risk of bushfires and grass fires to be the most important action.

However, 14 developers considered minimizing the risk of bushfires and grass fires is the most important action in this field, 12 considered minimizing site impacts on fauna, 7 minimizing negative impacts on site vegetation, 6 considered minimizing any impacts on topsoil, 6 considered minimizing changes to the hydrology in terms of quality, volume and distribution, and only 5 considered minimizing any impacts on topsoil to be the most important action.

Figure 58: Questionnaire's results analysis in the field of the impacts of building's elements on the land

In the field of materials efficiency, 10 architects and 25 developers considered the use of local building materials. However 11 architects and 9 developers considered the use of recycled materials more important.

Figure 59: Questionnaire's results analysis in the field of materials preferences

In the field of waste management, 29 architects and 36 developers managing non organic materials is the most important action. However 21 architects and 14 developers considered managing organic materials more important.

Figure 60: Questionnaire's results analysis in the field of waste management

In the field of green transport, 41 architects considered providing environmental transportation systems within the site parameters is the most important action in this field and only 9 considered decreasing the area of car parking.

However, 33 developers considered providing environmental transportation systems within the site parameters is the most important action in this field and only 17 considered decreasing the area of car parking.

Figure 61: Questionnaire's results analysis in the field of green transportation

The full results can be illustrated in the following chart:

Figure 62: Questionnaire Full Results

5.3.2 Conclusion

There value of previously listed environmental strategies is varied between architects and developers. This divergence can be described as the following:

- In the field of energy conservation, results had shown that most of both architects and developers had considered the implementation of passive solar design is the most important action in this field.
- In the field of water systemization, results had shown that most of both architects and developers had considered that Reduce the consumption of water and water efficient equipment is the most important action then the treatment and reuse waste water and lastly educating the importance of saving water.
- In the field of land persevering and minimizing the impacts of the building's element on the land most developers had shown that minimize the risk of bushfire is the most important then minimize the impact on fauna, then vegetation then both topsoil and hydrology and lastly topography. While most architects considered that minimize the impact on topography is the most important then topsoil and vegetation then hydrology and lastly both fauna and bushfires.
- In the field of material efficiency results had shown that majority of developer had considered the use of local material is the most important action in this field then optimal use of building materials and lastly using recycled materials while most of architect considered that optimal use of building materials is the most important actions in this field then using local materials and lastly using the recycled materials.
- In the field of waste management efficiency results had shown that most of both architects and developers had considered that managing non-organic materials is the most important then managing the organic materials.
- In the field of green transportation results had shown that most of both architects and developers considered providing environmental transportation system within the site is the most important action in this field then decrease the area of car parking.

Chapter Six

Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

This research shows through discussion of all different previous chapters that Sound and efficient environmental management of tourism facilities (e.g. water and energy saving measures, waste minimization, and use of environmentally friendly material) can decrease the environmental impact of tourism. A planning helps to make choices between the conflicting interests of tourism Development and Sustainability in order to find ways to make them compatible. By planning sustainable tourism development strategy at an early stage prevents damages and expensive mistakes, thereby avoiding the gradual deterioration of the quality of environmental goods and services significant to tourism.

The theoretical study conclusion:

- Tourism is an important sector to any country for the development of the economy. But tourism industry is directly related to the environment. The quality of the environment, both natural and man-made, is essential to tourism. However, the relationship of tourism with the environment is complex. It involves many activities that can have adverse environmental effects. Many of these impacts are linked with the construction of general infrastructure such as roads and airports, and of tourism facilities, including resorts, hotels, restaurants, shops, golf courses and marinas. The negative impacts of tourism development can gradually destroy environmental resources on which it depends. On the other hand, tourism has the potential to create beneficial effects on the environment by contributing to environmental protection and conservation.
- Tourism can create great pressure on local resources such as energy, land, and water that may already be in short supply.
- Negative impacts from tourism occur when the level of visitor use is greater than the environment's ability to cope with this use within acceptable limits of change. Uncontrolled conventional tourism poses potential threats to many natural areas around the world. It can put enormous pressure on an area and lead to impacts such as soil erosion, increased pollution, discharges into the sea, natural habitat loss, increased pressure on endangered species and heightened vulnerability to forest fires. It often puts as train on water resources, and it can force local populations to compete for the use of critical resources.

- The adverse impact that tourism can have on the environment both undermines the basic resource for tourism in coastal areas and heavily affects other non-tourist economic activities. To avoid these impacts tourism needs to be planned, managed and undertaken in a way that is environmentally sustainable, socially beneficial and economically viable.
- Beaches in the last century have completely reversed their role: they have become the driving force behind the economic welfare instead of just being an inhospitable place. However, the demographic pressure and the overuse of the land related to those factors have caused a general decrease in the contribution of sediments to the beaches with a continental or a marine origin. It is hard to find a unique solution for all those problems. However, it should be absolutely essential to follow these points:
 - First, a sustainable development for tourism projects
 - Second, a better dissemination of the existing information should be achieved. For that purpose, a better coordination of the existing governmental bodies that deal with environmental strategies management is necessary.
 - Third, an improvement of the environmental education is essential for a sustainable development of the coast.
- If strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA), applied at the proper stage of tourism development planning and within a well-defined regulatory and legislative framework, it will be a good guarantee of the sustainability of tourism activity and its harmonious coexistence with other activities in a well-preserved environment.
- Energy is used in buildings for heating and cooling, hot water, lighting and services and equipment. Well-designed buildings can significantly reduce energy consumption. Environmental impacts can be further reduced by using energy from a renewable source such as solar or wind. Lower energy use reduces Greenhouse Gas emissions (such as carbon dioxide, methane and nitrous oxide) and reduces operational costs. Important issues that contribute to reducing energy consumption include: • Passive solar design • Mechanical appliances and equipment • Renewable energy • Embodied energy.
- When designing a tourism development in a natural landscape, the following elements and systems need to be understood and accounted for: • Hydrology • Soils • Vegetation • Fauna • Bushfire management; and • Topography.
- Water is used for a range of purposes in tourism developments, including drinking, bathing, washing and waste disposal. Principal water sources in remote areas typically include rainwater, groundwater and surface water. In some areas of South Australia, controls exist on the taking of groundwater and surface water. Rainfall can provide a sustainable water supply and is commonly used as the primary water source in remote tourism development. Precautions need to be taken to maintain water quality for guests.

- There are two main types of waste: organic and non-organic. The most preferable options are to avoid or reduce waste. Where these cannot be achieved, materials should be reused and recycled/recovered wherever possible. The least preferable options are the treatment and disposal of waste.
- This involves considering material availability, source, consumption, durability, reusability, recycling, contamination issues and embodied energy. Some complex design decisions are required to be made in this area. Examples include:
 - A more durable material may be more difficult to recycle
 - A building designed for easy re-use may consume slightly more materials
 - A structurally efficient, durable and recyclable material such as aluminium, causes contamination in its manufacture and has a very high embodied energy.
 Materials selection is very much a product of the design responses to the land and energy aspects. There is also the financial feasibility or cost analysis considerations. A longer-term, payback period approach to material selection may also affect the choice of materials
- There are successful tourism developments in natural areas that deliberately limit or exclude vehicle access around the site. This is not just good for the environment; it can also make a significant contribution to enhancing the visitor experience.

The Practical study conclusion:

- Appropriate environmental measures in the tourism projects will be required to compensate for the loss of natural features from unavoidable development.
- There are some environmental issues which weren't taken in consideration during the development process while other issues are partly considered.
- There value of previously listed environmental strategies is varied between architects and developers.
- The following measures combine the essential elements of a fully integrated approach to the sustainable Development of the Syrian coastal projects. In summary, these elements are:

Good governance, targeted environmental management and actions, effective Stakeholder participation, capacity building and scientific support.

All are equally key to achieving the vision; legal and financial measures are complimented by community and environmental action, supported by public awareness and training, and underpinned by research and training. A wide range of organisations and individuals, sectors of government and levels of administration will be responsible for translating them into action.

6.2 Recommendations

- Sustainable tourism development always needs to respect the environment and refer to accepted principles of sustainability. It must be planned to make balanced use of the resources of any site, thus avoiding negative effects, reducing visitor satisfaction, or adversely impacting the local society, economy and culture. Sometimes it may be difficult to quantify limits, but they are essential for sustainable tourism. Thus, if it is to maintain the main elements on which it is based, the tourism sector needs to invest in the maintenance of the natural environment. If properly planned, tourism can become a positive force for conservation and environmental protection, and economic development
- All tourist facilities (Hotels, Roads, Resorts, Airport.....) shall be subjected to strict environmental authorization and control so that their negative impact on coastal ecosystems, landscape and geomorphology is minimized.
- A high level of protection of the environment in the selection of location and the operation of tourism facilities (including wastewater treatment plants) shall be guaranteed to preserve coastal ecosystems and landscapes and prevent pollution of the sea, water, air and soil.
- Development shall not block access to the coast or restrict coastal views.
- The use of natural resources such as power, water, and land, by the various tourism facilities shall be rationalized and the needs of future generations shall take into account.
- Respect for integrated water resources management and environmentally sound waste management shall be ensured, including development of new approaches and regulations with regards to industrial wastewater treatment, recycle and discharge.
- The coastal zone forests and a forestation sites shall be clearly identified, monitored and sustainably managed. Measures including early alert systems and the upgraded capacity of local fire brigades will ensure the proper protection from fires. Forest areas will be protected from land-use change.
- Coastal and marine habitats and species of high conservation value shall be protected through legislation, planning and management within the context of regional and international cooperation for the implementation of common programmes on the protection of marine habitats.
- Sustainable coastal tourism, sporting and recreational activities that preserves coastal ecosystems, natural resources, landscape, cultural heritage, and respects the local traditions shall be encouraged, including the promotion of specific forms of coastal tourism such as cultural, rural and ecotourism, and regulating or, where necessary, prohibiting the practice of damaging sporting and recreational activities.

6.3 Further Studies

This research recommends further studying the following topics:

- Further investigate new environmental strategies, actions and new technologies that can further develop the sustainability of tourism projects urbanism
- Enhance the sustainable development of tourism projects urbanism by studying the other aspects of sustainability (economic and social aspects)
- Investigate practical methods that can be achieved to further develop these guidelines, and design a guiding framework for architects that can include obligatory points to preserve the environment and awarding points in sustainable tourism field.

References

List of References:

1. *Australian Government, Department of the Environment and Heritage. Steps To Sustainable Tourism. 2004.*
2. *Alexis, M. Troschinetz. James, R. Mihelcic. Sustainable recycling of municipal solid waste in developing countries. 2009*
3. *Andereck, Kathleen L.,. The Impacts of Tourism on Natural Resources. Parks and Recreation. 1993*
4. *Ashby,Michael.Materials and the Environment: Eco-informed Material Choice. 2012*
5. *Australian tourism commission. Design Guide lines for Sustainable Tourism Development.2007*
6. *Bacon, Peter R.Use of Wetlands for Tourism in the Insular Caribbean. Annals of Tourism Research. 1987*
7. *Bosselman, Fred P. In the Wake of the Tourist. Washington, DC: The Conservation Foundation. 1978*
8. *Bulbeck, C. Facing the Wild Ecotourism, Conservation and Animal Encounters. Earthscan London. 2005*
9. *Camarda. G.,. Environments and agriculture in the Mediterranean region. 2003*
10. *Cessford, G.R. and Dingwall, P.R. Impacts of Visitors on Natural and Historic Resources of Conservation Significance: Part 1 - Workshop proceedings. Science and Research Internal Report, No. 156Department of Conservation, Wellington. 1997*
11. *Cessford, G.R. Impacts of visitors on natural and historic resources of conservation significance: Part 2 Research and information needs. Science and Research Internal Report. Department of Conservation. 1997*
12. *Cessford,Gordon.Impacts of visitors on natural and historic resources of conservation significance.Department of Conservation.1997*
13. *CSIL Centre for Industrial Studies.The Impact Of Tourism On Coastal Areas: Regional Development Aspects. 2008*
14. *Dickinson, J. and Lumsdon, L. Slow Travel and Tourism. Earthscan. London. 2010*
15. *Drexhage, John. Murphy,Deborah.International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD). Sustainable Development. 2010*

16. Dwyer, Larry. Edwards, Deborah .*Understanding the Sustainable Development of Tourism*. Goodfellow Publishers Limited Woodeaton. Oxford. 2011
17. *European Commission Study. Country Report: Syria*. 2011
18. Ghimire, K.B. *The Native Tourist. Mass Tourism within Developing Countries*. Earthscan, London. 2001
19. Giaoutzi, Maria. Dionetis, Christos. *Cultural Tourism and Sustainable Local Development*. Ashgate Publishing. 2009
20. Gillian, Menzies. *Embodied energy considerations for existing buildings*. 2011
21. Graci, S. Dodds, R. *Sustainable Tourism in Island Destinations*, Earthscan, London. 2010
22. Groth, A. *Sustainable tourism and the environment*. 2000
23. Guerreroa, Lilliana. Maasa, Ger. Hoglandb, William . *Solid waste management challenges for cities in developing countries*. 2013
24. Gutierrez, Eileen. *Project Development For Sustainable Tourism A Step By Step Approach*. United States Agency for International Development to the Global Sustainable Tourism. (2014).
25. Hall, D. Richards, G. *Tourism and Sustainable Community Development*. Routledge, London. 2003
26. Hon. Anthony Bernard KELLY. *Planning for Bush Fire Protection*. 2006
27. IUCN the World Conservation Union. *Tourism, Ecotourism and Protected Areas*. 1996
28. Johnston, A.M. *Is the Sacred for Sale, Tourism and Indigenous Peoples*. Earthscan, London. 2005
29. khoshnevis Yazdi, Soheila. *Sustainable Tourism*. American International Journal of Social Science. 2012
30. Kir, Gee. Kannen, Andreas. Glaeser, Bernhard. Sterr, Horst. *National ICZM Strategies in Germany: A Patial Planing Approach*. 2004
31. Klara Brandl. *Environment Agency Austria. Sustainable Tourism & Nature Conservation. SURF-nature project*. 2011
32. Lal Mukherjee, Abir. *Impact of tourism in coastal areas: Need of sustainable tourism strategy*. 2013
33. Lawal Mohammed Marafa. *Integrating Sustainable Tourism Development in Coastal and Marine Zone Environment*. 2008

34. Leisanyane ,Mamahooana . Malabeja, Michael. Cheyo, Robert. *Impact of Tourism on Wildlife* www.environmental-auditing.org Conservation. INTOSAI Working Group on Environmental Auditing (WGEA). 2013
35. Lettieri. Baeyens. *Waste Management: Recycling and recovery routes of plastic solid waste (PSW)*. 2009
36. Mann, M. Brahim, Z. *The Good Alternative Travel Guide*. Earthscan. London. 2002
37. *Massachusetts Nonpoint Source Pollution Management.Preserving Natural Vegetation*.2003
38. Mastny, L. *Traveling Light: New Paths for International Tourism*. Worldwatch Institute. 2001
39. Md, GhulamRabbany. Sharmin Afrin. Airin Rahman. Faijul Islam. Fazlul Hoque. *ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS OF TOURISM*. American Journal of Environment. 2013
40. Md. Ghulam. Rabban, Sharmin. Airin, Rahman. Faijul, Islam. Fazlul, Hoque. *Environmental Effects of Tourism*. American Journal of Environment, Energy and Power Research. 2013
41. *Mediterranean Environmental Technical Assistance Program. Integrated Coastal Zone Management — ICZM Syria*.
42. *Ministry For The Environment And Territory. Environmental Action Strategy For Sustainable Development In Italy*
43. Mitchell, J. Ashley, C. *Tourism and Poverty Reduction, Pathways to Prosperity*. Earthscan. London. 2009
44. Mowforth, M. Munt, I. *Tourism and Sustainability: Development, Globalisation and New Tourism in the Third World (3rd Edition)*. Routledge. London. 2008
45. Munt,Ian. Mowforth,Martin. *New Tourism in the Third World*. 2003
46. Neto, Frederico. *A New Approach To Sustainable Tourism Development: Moving Beyond Environmental Protection*. A United Nations Sustainable Development Journal .Published Online 2003
47. *North Carolina Department of Environment and Natural Resource. Water Management Option*.2005
48. Nurhidayah, Laely . *Toward Integrated Coastal Zone Management in Indonesia: Framework Assessment and comparative analysis*. 2010
49. P.R. Dingwall and G.R. Cessford. *An approach to assessing the environmental impacts of tourism*. 1998

50. Pattullo, P. Minelli, O. Hourmant, P. Smith, P. Viesnik, L. Dall, A. *The Ethical Travel Guide (Second Edition)*. Earthscan. London. 2009
51. *Priority Actions Programme*. UNEP. *Sustainable Coastal Tourism An integrated planning and management approach*. 2009
52. Robinson, M. Picard, D. *Tourism Culture and Sustainable Development*. Division of Cultural Policies and Intercultural Dialogue. Culture Sector, UNESCO. 2006
53. Rogers, Chris, Dinesen. *Ways to Conserve Soil*. 2015
54. Schroeder, Brandon. Johnson, Laura. *Sustainable Coastal Tourism Development In Northeast Michiga*. 2012
55. Sharpley, R. *Tourism Development and the Environment: Beyond Sustainability*. Earthscan. London. 2009
56. Shaw ,Gareth. Allan, M, Williams. *Tourism and Tourism Spaces*. SAGE Publications Ltd . 2004
57. Smale, Robin. Krahe,Max. Johnson,Tim. *Aviation report market based mechanisms to curb greenhouse gas emissions from international aviation*. Gland, Switzerland: WWF International, 2012
58. Spenceley, A. *Responsible Tourism. Critical Issues for Conservation and Development*. Earthscan. London. 2008
59. Steckenreuter,Andre. *How does Australia's largest dolphin-watching industry affect the behaviour of a small and resident population of Indo-Pacific bottlenose dolphins*.2011
60. *Sustainable Tourism, Planning A Sustainable Future For Tourism, Heritage And The Environment*. 2004
61. *Tasmanian Expeditions Pty Limited*. *bay of fires lodge walk Experience the very best of the Bay of Fires wilderness*.2012
62. *The South Australian Tourism Commission. Design Guidelines for Sustainable Tourism Development*. Government of South Australia. 2007
63. *U.S. Ambassador's Youth Council. Strategies and challenges for pursuing sustainable tourism in Cambodia*. 2014
64. *UNEP/MAP-METAP SMAP III Project Promoting awareness and enabling a policy framework for environment and development integration in the Mediterranean with focus on Integrated Coastal Zone Management*. 2006
65. *UNEP/MAP-METAP SMAP III Project. Syria's Coastal Zone and its Desired Integrated Management, Proposed Vision and Policy*. 2009

66. *United Nation Development Program. Tourism and Poverty Reduction Strategies in the Integrated Framework for Least Developed Countries. 2011*
67. *United Nation. Achieving Sustainable Development and Promoting Development Cooperation.*
68. *United Nations Environment Program (UNEP). Environmental Impacts Of Tourism: Three main impact areas, natural resources, pollution, and physical impacts . 2012*
69. *United Nations Environment Program, World Tourism Organization. Making Tourism More Sustainable A Guide For Policy Makers. 2005*
70. *UNWTO. International tourists to hit 1.8 billion by 2030. World Tourism Organization. 2011*
71. *UNWTO. Tourism and Biodiversity: Achieving common goals towards sustainability. World Tourism Organization. Madrid. 2010*
72. *UNWTO. UNEP. Tourism in the Green Economy. World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP). 2012*
73. *UNWTO. UNWTO World Tourism Barometer. Geneva. World Tourism Organization. 2010*
74. *Victorian Government. Environmentally Sustainable Tourism Strategic Plan. Melbourne, Australia. 2009*
75. *World Tourism Organisation. Tourism Investing in energy and resource efficiency. United Nations Environment Program, 2011*
76. *World Tourism Organization (WTO) .A Practical Guide to the Development and Use of Indicators of Sustainable Tourism. 2005*
77. *World Tourism Organization (WTO) Guide for Local Planner Authorities in Developing Sustainable Tourism. 1998*
78. *World Travel & Tourism Council WTTC. The Economic Impact of Travel & Tourism. 2015*
79. *Zinderman, Carly. Protect and Conserve Water Resources. 2015*

List of Web References:

1. *Aquila Eco Lodges*. URL: <http://www.stayz.com.au/accommodation/vic/the-grampians/dunkeld/112893>
2. *Architectural Record*: URL: <http://archrecord.construction.com/projects/portfolio/archives/0107ecolodge.asp>
3. *Building in a bush fire area*: URL: <http://www.rfs.nsw.gov.au/resources/publications/building-in-a-bush-fire-area>
4. *Choosing Green Materials and Products*: URL: <http://www.epa.gov/greenhomes/SmarterMaterialChoices.htm>
5. *Consequences of biodiversity loss*: URL: <http://www.rainforestconservation.org/rainforest-primer/2-biodiversity/g-recent-losses-in-biodiversity/4-consequences-of-biodiversity-loss/>
6. *Construction Waste Management*: URL: <http://www.wbdg.org/resources/cwmgmt.php>
7. *Energy Efficiency*: URL: <http://energy.gov/science-innovation/energy-efficiency>
8. *Environmental Impact Analysis*: URL: http://www.lic.wisc.edu/shapingdane/facilitation/all_resources/impacts/analysis_environmental.htm
9. *Environmental Impacts of Tourism - Global Level*: URL: <http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Business/SectoralActivities/Tourism/FactsandFiguresaboutTourism/ImpactsOfTourism/EnvironmentalImpacts/EnvironmentalImpactsOfTourism-GlobalLevel/tabid/78777/Default.aspx>
10. *Environmental Sciences*: URL: <http://www.ukessays.com/essays/environmental-sciences/principles-to-be-followed-while-designing-environmental-sciences-essay.php>
Fundamental Principles of Green Building and Sustainable Site Design:
URL: http://www.epa.gov/statelocalclimate/documents/pdf/12_8_what_is_green_GGGC.pdf
11. *Gensler Architecture to Envision New Eco-friendly Shore Hotel*, URL: <http://www.hotelmanagement.net/gensler-architecture-to-envision-new-eco-friendly-shore-hotel-10694>

12. *Giving your waste the full treatment.* URL: <http://news.domain.com.au/domain/green/giving-your-waste-the-full-treatment-20110209-1am97.html>
13. *Glenn Research Reduces Harmful Aircraft Emissions:* URL: <http://www.nasa.gov/centers/glenn/about/fs10grc.html>
14. *Green Building Basics:*URL: <http://www.calrecycle.ca.gov/greenbuilding/basics.htm>
15. *Green Standard at Shore Hotel.* URL: <http://www.shorehotel.com/Stay/Amenities/Green-Standards>
16. *How to Use Planning for Bush Fire Protection:* URL: <http://www.rfs.nsw.gov.au/plan-and-prepare/building-in-a-bush-fire-area/planning-for-bush-fire-protection/how-to-use-planning-for-bush-fire-protection>
17. *Hydrologic and hydraulic design:* URL: <http://www.melbournewater.com.au/Planning-and-building/Standards-and-specifications/Design-general/Pages/Hydrologic-and-hydraulic-design.aspx>
18. *International Air Passengers' Numbers : Monterey Bay National Marine Sanctuary* URL: <http://montereybay.noaa.gov/intro/welcome.html>
19. *Latakia, Syria:* URL: <https://www.rotana.com/syria/latakia/39>
20. *Noise pollution : United Nation Environmental programme,* URL: <http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Home/Business/SectoralActivities/Tourism/tabid/78766/Default.aspx>
21. *Porto Tartous:* URL: <http://www.portoworldhotels.com/HotelInner.aspx?HID=13&HLID=170>
22. *protect biodiversity and save endangered species:* URL: <http://www.endangeredspeciesinternational.org/overview4.html>
23. *Protecting the Environment:* URL: <http://www.epa.gov/epahome/trans.htm>
24. *Renewable Energy:* URL: <http://www.nrcan.gc.ca/energy/renewable-electricity/7295>

25. *Saving Electricity*: URL: <http://energy.gov/public-services/homes/saving-electricity>
26. *Shore Hotel* : http://www.tripadvisor.com/LocationPhotoDirectLink-g33052-d2257239-i79215410-Shore_Hotel-Santa_Monica_California.html
27. *Shore Hotel is a LEED Gold Beach Retreat in Santa Monica*, URL: <http://inhabitat.com/genslers-shore-hotel-is-a-leed-gold-green-respite-on-the-beach-in-santa-monica/shore-hotel-gensler-5/?extend=1>
28. *Solar paths during the year: Solar Power Production on the Gold Coast*, URL: <http://gold-coast-solar-power-solutions.com.au/posts/solar-power-production-on-the-gold-coast/>
29. *Style by the shore*: URL: <http://www.worldarchitecturenews.com/wanmobile/mobile/article/19713>
30. *Sustainability and Water*: URL: <http://www.overpopulation.org/water.html>
31. *Sustainable Tourism Definition* URL: <http://tourismdestinationpicture.blogspot.com/2015/02/sustainable-tourism-definition.html>
32. *Sustainable Tourism* URL: <http://www.grida.no/tourism/about.aspx?id=4794>
33. *Sustainable Tourism*: URL: http://www.biodiversity.ru/coastlearn/tourism-eng/why_problems.html
34. *The design and construction of environmentally sustainable new buildings*: URL: <http://www.environment.admin.cam.ac.uk/resource-bank/guidance-documents/design-and-construction-environmentally-sustainable-new-buildings>
35. *The International Air Transport Association IATA* URL: <http://www.iata.org/pressroom/pr/pages/2012-12-06-01.aspx>
36. *Tourism's Three Main Impact Areas*: URL <http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Business/SectoralActivities/Tourism/FactsandFiguresaboutTourism/ImpactsOfTourism/EnvironmentalImpacts/TourismsThreeMainImpactAreas/tabid/78776/Default.aspx>
37. *Trampling: United Nation Environmental programme*, URL: <http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Home/Business/SectoralActivities/Tourism/tabid/78766/Default.aspx>

38. *Union of Concerned Scientists*, URL: http://www.ucsusa.org/clean_vehicles/why-clean-cars/air-pollution-and-health
39. *Waste removal : United Nation Environmental programme*, URL: <http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Home/Business/SectoralActivities/Tourism/tabid/78766/Default.aspx>
40. *Waterless Urinals and Flush Urinal*: URL: <http://www.sswm.info/content/waterless-urinals-and-flush-urinals>
41. *Ways to Stop Pullution*: URL: <http://greenliving.lovetoknow.com/>

Abbreviation 1 World Travel & Tourism Council
Abbreviation 2 Gross Domestic Product
Abbreviation 3 The United Nations World Tourism Organization
Abbreviation 4 Enhanced Integrated Framework
Abbreviation 5 Least Developed Countries
Abbreviation 6 Tourism Planning Research Group
Abbreviation 7 Master of Tourism Management
Abbreviation 8 General Agreement on Trade in Services
Abbreviation 9 Regional Trade Agreements
Abbreviation 10 The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
Abbreviation 11 Life Cycle Assessment
Abbreviation 12 The International Air Transport Association
Abbreviation 13 Monterey Bay National Marine Sanctuary
Abbreviation 14 Off-Road Vehicles
Abbreviation 15 Ozone Depleting Substances
Abbreviation 16 Chlorofluorocarbons
Abbreviation 17 The World Wildlife Fund
Abbreviation 18 Australia's National Science Agency
Abbreviation 19 World Commission on Environment and Development
Abbreviation 20 Integrated Coastal Zone Management
Abbreviation 21 Leadership in Energy & Environmental Design
Abbreviation 22 Polyvinyl Chloride
Abbreviation 23 Volatile Organic Compounds

المخلص

تعد السياحة نوعاً هاماً من أنواع الأنشطة التجارية والاستثمارية عالية الربحية، فقد أصبحت صناعة رئيسية على النطاق العالمي، ومن المتوقع أن تنمو نمواً متواصلاً، حيث زاد عدد السياح على المستوى الدولي ثلاثة أمثاله في العقدين الماضيين، وتعد السياحة ووالسفر أكبر مصدرين للعمالة في العالم. تعتبر السياحة من أكثر الصناعات نمواً وتطوراً في العالم. وفي الوقت ذاته اتفق على التنمية المستدامة من أجل تحقيق هذا التطور في السياحة.

قد حاولت العديد من الهيئات والمنظمات الدولية مثل منظمة السياحة العالمية ومجلس السفر (WWTC) والاتحاد الفيدرالي الدولي لشركات السياحة (IFTO) التركيز على القضايا السياحية ذات التوجه البيئي. حيث نشرت منظمة السياحة العالمية دليلاً إرشادياً للتنمية المستدامة للجهات المحلية المسؤولة عن التخطيط. كما أصدر البرنامج البيئي التابع للأمم المتحدة بالتعاون مع "مبادرة البيئة للفنادق الدولية" بعض الإرشادات من أجل تحسين الأداء البيئي للوحدات الفندقية مثل (الفندي الأخضر، الاعتناء بالأخضر فكرة جديدة بالاحترام، والإدارة البيئية للفنادق). أما اتفاقية التنوع الحيوي وأجندا ٢١ تدعم الحوافز الموجهة من أجل تحقيق تنمية السياحة المستدامة. كما نشرت المفوضية الأوروبية ورقة خضراء عن دور الاتحاد في مجال السياحة. كما أسست على مدار سنتي ١٩٩٥ و ١٩٩٦ ما يعرف باسم ECONETT، وهي شبكة معنية بالسياحة والبيئة. بالإضافة إلى تبنى المجلس الأوروبي العديد من المبادرات الهامة في السياحة المستدامة. وبسبب بعض الالتزامات التي تنص عليها المعاهدات يتعين أن يشمل تعاون القطاع السياحي بالاتحاد الأوروبي مع الحكومات أو الأعمال الخاصة على الأخذ في الاعتبار الآثار البيئية لكل عمل يتم التخطيط له. وفي هذا السياق تولى القطاع الخاص بدوره بعض المبادرات نحو الحد من آثار السياحة السلبية على البيئة.

يمتد الساحل السوري من محافظة طرطوس جنوباً حتى رأس البسيط شمالاً في محافظتين رئيسيتين هما: اللاذقية و طرطوس، بطول يمتد ب ١٨٠ كلم. و يساوي ٣٥ ميلاً بحرياً (٦٥ كلم) تقريباً من شاطئ البحر الأبيض المتوسط. ان تزايد عدد السكان في الساحل السوري وعدد الزوار والانشطة السياحية (وخاصة أثناء النزاعات السورية الحالية) ادى الى زيادة في الآثار السلبية للسياحة على الموارد البيئة الطبيعية هناك نتيجة لعدم الاستخدام الرشيد للاراضي والموارد الطبيعية من مياه و طاقة.

الهدف الرئيسي من هذه الرسالة هو التعريف بمجموعة من استراتيجيات التصميم البيئي خلال مراحل المشروع المختلفة (تصميم و تنفيذ و مرحلة الصيانة) لإدارة التنمية المستدامة في الساحل السوري، حيث تلعب هذه الاستراتيجيات دورا هاما أثناء عملية التنمية عند استخدامها من قبل السلطات والمطورين, فهي تمكن من فهم مشترك للقضايا الرئيسية التي تساهم في تصميم التنمية المستدامة للمشاريع السياحية.

استخدم في هذه الرسالة :

المنهج التحليلي: تحليل الدراسات النظرية لتحديد أثر السياحة على البيئة وتحديد مفهوم السياحة المستدامة ومفهوم التنمية السياحية المستدامة. وبالإضافة إلى ذلك مقارنة تحليلية بين العديد من المشاريع السياحية العالمية التي اقيمت على الساحل و التي اخذت في الاعتبار الحفاظ على البيئة وذلك لتحديد استراتيجيات بيئية في سياق دورة حياة المشاريع التي تهدف الى تحقيق التنمية السياحية المستدامة في المناطق الساحلية.

المنهج التطبيقي: ويتم من خلال محورين حيث سيتم استخدام هذه الاستراتيجيات التي خلصنا اليها في البحث لمراقبة حالة المشاريع السياحية في الساحل السوري وتقييمها في المحور الاول بينما سيتم في الحور الثاني اجراء استبيان لدراسة اختلاف وجهات النظر لكل من المصممين والمستثمرين لاهمية كل من هذه الاستراتيجيات على حدى.

وقد بين هذا البحث من خلال مناقشة جميع الفصول انه كفاءة الادارة البيئية للمرافق السياحية(كالمياه والطاقة واستخدام المواد الصديقة للبيئة) يقلل من الاثار السلبية للسياحة ويساعد على اتخاذ الخيارات المناسبة لتحقيق التنمية السياحية المستدامة وبالتالي صيانة الموارد الطبيعية لأجل ادامة استخدامها مستقبلا مع تمكين الأجيال الحاضرة من الاستفادة منه.

فالحرص على استمرار جودة البيئة بكافة جوانبها و تحسين الجودة في المواقع السياحية التي تحتاج لذلك فان السياح عادة ما يرغبون في زيارة مواقع تمتاز بالطبيعة الخلابة و البيئة النظيفة الغير ملوثة فجودة البيئة توفر متعة كبيرة لاهالي المنطقة و السياحة تزيد وعيهم لأهمية جودة البيئة و بالتالي دعمهم لخطط الحفاظ على هذه الجودة و تحسينها متى ما اقتضى الأمر ذلك.

خلود جميل علي

١٩٨٥ / ١ / ٥

سورية

مهندس:

تاريخ الميلاد:

الجنسية:

تاريخ التسجيل:

تاريخ المنح:

القسم:

الدرجة:

المشرفون:

الهندسة المعمارية

ماجستير العلوم في الهندسة المعمارية

أ.د. أحمد محمد أمين (المشرف الرئيسي)

أ.د. عماد الشرييني (مشرف)

المتحنون:

أ.د. شريف محمد صبري العطار، أستاذ العمارة، كلية الهندسة، جامعه

الفيوم (المتحن الخارجي)

أ.د. أيمن حسان أحمد (المتحن الداخلي)

أ.د. أحمد محمد أمين (المشرف الرئيسي)

أ.د. عماد الشرييني (مشرف)

عنوان الرسالة:

ادارة الاستراتيجيات العمرانية البيئية: نحو تنمية متواصلة لعمران المشروعات السياحية (دراسة حالة لنطاق الساحل السوري)

ملخص الرسالة:

تعد السياحة نوعاً هاماً من أنواع الأنشطة التجارية والاستثمارية عالية الربحية، فقد أصبحت صناعة رئيسية على النطاق العالمي، ومن المتوقع أن تنمو نمواً متواصلاً، حيث زاد عدد السياح على المستوى الدولي ثلاثة أمثاله في العقدين الماضيين، وتعد السياحة والسفر أكبر مصدرين للعمالة في العالم. تعتبر السياحة من أكثر الصناعات نمواً وتطوراً في العالم. وفي الوقت ذاته اتفق على التنمية المستدامة من أجل تحقيق هذا التطور في السياحة.

الهدف الرئيسي من هذه الرسالة هو التعريف بمجموعة من استراتيجيات التصميم البيئي خلال مراحل المشروع المختلفة (تصميم و تنفيذ و مرحلة الصيانة) لإدارة التنمية المستدامة في الساحل السوري، حيث تلعب هذه الاستراتيجيات دوراً هاماً أثناء عملية التنمية عند استخدامها من قبل السلطات والمطورين، فهي تمكن من فهم مشترك للقضايا الرئيسية التي تساهم في تصميم التنمية المستدامة للمشاريع السياحية.

ادارة الاستراتيجيات العمرانية البيئية: نحو تنمية متواصلة لعمران المشروعات
السياحية (دراسة حالة لنطاق الساحل السوري)

اعداد
خلود جميل علي

رسالة مقدمة إلى كلية الهندسة - جامعة القاهرة
كجزء من متطلبات الحصول على درجة ماجستير العلوم
في
الهندسة المعمارية

يعتمد من لجنة الممتحنين:

الممتحن الخارجي الاستاذ الدكتور: شريف العطار

الممتحن الداخلي الاستاذ الدكتور: أيمن حسان

المشرف الرئيسي الاستاذ الدكتور: أحمد أمين

المشرف الاستاذ الدكتور: عماد الشريبي

كلية الهندسة - جامعة القاهرة
الجيزة - جمهورية مصر العربية

2015

ادارة الاستراتيجيات العمرانية البيئية: نحو تنمية متواصلة لعمران المشروعات
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اعداد
خلود جميل علي

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كجزء من متطلبات الحصول على درجة ماجستير العلوم
في
الهندسة المعمارية

تحت اشراف

اسم المشرف
الاستاذ الدكتور: عماد الشربيني

اسم المشرف
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الجيزة - جمهورية مصر العربية

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